

HiDyVe

Highly Dynamic Virtual and
Hybrid Validation and Verification

WP210

Ultra Complex and Autonomous
Cyber-physical Systems
State-of-the-Art Analysis

University of Bremen – TZI

Technical Report

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Management Summary

This technical report of project HiDyVe summarises the state-of-the-art in the field of specification, modelling, verification, and validation of highly complex, partially or fully autonomous systems. The main focus is on air vehicles, but relevant facts from the automotive domain and the railway domain are considered as well. A clear distinction between conventional and challenging systems and applications is introduced. While the former class can be developed, verified, validated, and certified using the existing, well-established methods and standards, the latter require new methods, and their certification needs to be based on novel standards. The current state of standardisation and certification aspects is reviewed for both the avionic and automotive domains. It is not surprising that the automotive domain is more advanced with respect to standardisation for safety-critical challenging systems than the avionic domain. Interestingly, however, the automotive standardisation approach covers more types of challenging systems, while novel pre-standards of the avionic domain focus only on the effects of Machine Learning (ML) in safety-critical systems. We review established methods for modelling and Verification and Validation (V&V) of challenging systems and indicate potential solutions for currently unsolved problems.

Preface

Project HiDyVe is funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (**BMWi**). The project consortium is headed by Airbus, with project partners including the TZI at the University of Bremen, dSPACE, and Verified Systems International. The overall project objective is to investigate new **V&V** paradigms that are suitable to cope with the growing complexity of avionic systems, in particular from the perspective of partially autonomous functionality to be integrated into future avionic systems. The project name ‘*Highly Dynamic Virtual and Hybrid Validation and Verification*’ emphasises that the **V&V** approach to be investigated does not only consider static methods, such as reviews and analyses, but focuses on dynamic methods like testing and simulation. ‘*Virtual V&V*’ denotes verification and validation activities performed with test stimulators, simulations and software test oracles only, while ‘*hybrid V&V*’ uses mixed configurations combining Original Equipment (**OE**), that is, real avionic controllers, with stimulators, simulators, and checkers. The Work Package Break-down Structure (**WPBS**) of the project is shown in Figure 1.

HiDyVe

Project
objective

This technical report contains the output of

WP210

WP210 State-of-the-Art Analysis.

In this report, the University of Bremen team has compiled actual research results, information from relevant standards, and best practices already applied in industry today for the purpose of developing and verifying highly complex Cyber-Physical Systems (**CPS**) with partially or fully autonomous functions.

Figure 1: HiDyVe work package break-down structure.

The need for new **V&V** paradigms is driven by four main trends that **Challenges** can be observed in **CPS** in general.

1. **Growing system complexity** which can no longer be captured anymore in monolithic, comprehensive models and specifications.
2. **Evolving system behaviour** after type certification.
3. The utilisation of **multi agent systems** that elaborate plans changing their behaviour at runtime, and
4. The adoption of trained **neural networks** whose true behaviour at runtime can be specified neither deterministically, nor within the logic concepts of the application domain.

It is explained in Chapter 2, why these challenges do not only require “just a little bit more **V&V** effort” as before, but call for novel specification methods and **V&V** paradigms, as well as for novel certification regulations.

While the Artificial Intelligence (AI)-related challenges 3 and 4 above typically occur in the context of autonomous systems development and V&V, challenges 1 and 2 are trends that can also be observed in conventional system developments. This is due to the demand for higher automation, improved capabilities, and increased dependability which results in a dramatic growth (typically exponential, see Figure 2) of software and system complexity. In 2003, the authors of [123] already predicted

Inevitable
growth of
complexity

“As systems become more interconnected and diverse, architects are less able to anticipate and design interactions among components, leaving such issues to be dealt with at runtime. Soon systems will become too massive and complex for even the most skilled system integrators to install, configure, optimize, maintain, and merge.”

source: <https://savi.avsi.aero/about-savi/savi-motivation/exponential-system-complexity/>

Figure 2: Growth of software complexity in commercial aircraft.

The adoption of multi agent systems seems to be inevitable when shifting responsibilities performed before by humans (pilots, vehicle drivers) to machines. The use of **neural networks** and other **machine learning** techniques¹ cannot be avoided, since agent systems need abstracted sensory information describing the state of the operational environment and the system itself.

Importance
of AI-based
systems

The need for a change of **V&V** paradigms to be applied to *any* software-based system utilising **AI** methods is widely accepted today. We quote from the objectives of *The IEEE Third International Conference On Artificial Intelligence Testing (AITest 2021)*².

AI needs
new V&V
paradigms

“...the quality assurance of existing AI application development processes is still far from satisfactory and the demand for being able to show demonstrable levels of confidence in such systems is growing.”

This Document is structured as follows. In Part I, research project HiDyVe is introduced, related international research activities are referenced, and research questions are formulated.

Overview

- In Chapter 1, it is briefly described how **HiDyVe** is embedded into international research activities, all working on highly complex, potentially autonomous, cyber-physical systems of the future.
- In Chapter 2, the main challenges for the HiDyVe project are described in more detail, and a more precise definition of “challenging systems” is given.
- In Chapter 3, the **Research Question (RQ)** investigated by our team in the context of HiDyVe are listed, with references to the associated HiDyVe Work Package (**WP**). These research questions are a result of the state-of-the-art analysis described in this document.

¹Or any other kind of self-adaptive system behaviour

²<http://ieeaitests.com>

In Part II, complex, potentially autonomous systems are discussed, focussing on functional and architectural aspects and formalisms that are suitable for modelling such systems.

- In Chapter 4, functional and architectural aspects of autonomous systems are reviewed. This chapter provides a basic understanding of this challenging system type which is necessary to assess the innovations needed to elaborate trustworthy V&V results for certifiable autonomous systems.
- Chapter 5 addresses the general complexity issue by reviewing approaches to specifying and modelling systems that cannot be represented by comprehensive monolithic models or similar specification documents.

In Part III, we present a survey of methods for testing highly complex and (partially) autonomous systems with sufficient strength, so that certification credit can be justifiably assigned to the executed test suites.

- Chapter 6 introduces related terminology.
- In Chapter 7, the test-related challenges posed by complex autonomous systems are discussed.
- In Chapter 8 complete testing theories allowing to *prove* the correctness of software or system components by testing are explained.
- In Chapter 9, we describe fuzz testing and its advantages for testing software modules.
- The test of configurable systems with large sets of configuration parameters is discussed in Chapter 10.
- Chapter 11 gives a short overview over passive testing and runtime testing.
- In Chapter 12, we discuss the specific challenges involved with testing multi-agent systems.

- In Chapter 13, the impact of machine learning techniques on complete testing theories is explained.

In Part IV, verification and validation approaches for complex autonomous systems and their specific safety-critical components are described.

- In Chapter 14, specific methods for the V&V of autonomous safety controllers are reviewed.
- In Chapter 15, we address probabilistic model checking. The application of neural networks and other AI-based components involving machine learning implies that some software modules can no longer be specified and verified with respect to their full behaviour, but only perform their services with a certain probability. Probabilistic model checking is necessary to validate on the model level, whether the risk implied by these components does not lead to a violation of the risk bounds specified for the complete integrated system.
- In Chapter 16, the state-of-the-art in automated theorem proving is reviewed. There is a common understanding that complex systems with changing configurations and evolving behaviours should be verified by theorem proving rather than of model checking, because the latter only allows for the verification of fixed configurations (or with very few symbolic parameters in the model), whereas the former allows verification of properties that are universally quantified, e.g., over all admissible configurations.
- In Chapter 17, the verification and validation of recurrent neural networks for system control is described.
- In Chapter 18, the specific problem of testing trained neural networks for safety-critical image classification (e.g. for obstacle detection) is described, together with a statistical test approach allowing to calculate residual risks of misclassifications.

- Even with stronger innovative V&V approaches, there will be the need to test more cases than would be possible to check with the original equipment within acceptable time. Therefore, the execution of tests in the cloud is addressed in Chapter 19. The boundary conditions to be fulfilled for achieving certification credit for these tests that have not been executed on the original equipment are discussed.

In Part V, we discuss certification-related challenges posed by safety-critical complex autonomous systems.

- In Chapter 20, an overview about the certification of highly complex, partially autonomous safety-critical systems is given.
- Chapter 21 gives a brief overview on current standards that are relevant for safety-critical complex autonomous systems.
- In Chapter 22, we explain why existing standards are insufficient to cope with the new certification challenges induced by systems applying AI and, in particular, ML.
- In Chapter 23, current standardisation activities in the automotive domain are reviewed. In this domain, issues related to the standardisation and certification of autonomous vehicles are most advanced in comparison to the transportation domains.
- The related activities in the aviation domain are described in Chapter 24, and in Chapter 25 for the railway domain.
- In Chapter 26, we summarise related activities performed in the research communities.
- In Chapter 27, we elaborate on the thesis that we cannot expect universally accepted comprehensive safety standards for the certification of complex autonomous systems. Instead, we advocate catalogues with accepted approaches to the construction of safety cases for specific types of critical system components.

- Chapter 28 briefly describes the goal structuring notation for documenting safety cases.
- Chapter 29 discusses requirements-driven testing and model-driven testing and the associated prerequisites to obtain certification credit for these different test approaches.

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Part I
Project HiDyVe

Chapter 1

Project HiDyVe – Relations to International Research Projects

If we had to start from scratch, the objectives of the HiDyVe project would be far too challenging to be tackled and at least partially solved within three years and with such a small group of project partners. Fortunately, the research fields

Research
strategy
adopt&adapt

- cyber-physical (control) systems (CPS),
- artificial intelligence (AI), and
- safety-critical systems engineering

that provide the foundations for HiDyVe can be considered as mature and well-understood. Even in the relatively new research area of

- autonomous robotics and road vehicles,

a multitude of research results and practical experience reports are available today. Consequently, the general research strategy of HiDyVe is not to open a completely new line of research, but to adopt and adapt existing results from the areas listed above. True to this strategy, the HiDyVe project is “embedded” into a variety of international projects, some of

them performing interdisciplinary research on a large scale. We mention here only the subset of these projects where direct research contacts exist, and an exchange of results has already been planned.

1.1 Assuring Autonomy

is an international large-scale research programme initiated and managed by Lloyd's Register Foundation and the University of York.¹ It is based on the insight that missing assurance (this covers all certification related aspects) and regulations (laws, standards) represent the biggest obstacle for introducing **Robotics and Autonomous Systems (RAS)** into our society. The basis for enabling assurance and providing adequate regulations for widely used **RAS** is created by means of foundational research, demonstrator projects, **training** and education, and the support of an international community of people working in the industrial, academic, and regulatory domains. A noteworthy contribution of this programme is the creation of a publicly available **body of knowledge** related to **RAS**.²

1.2 UKRI Trustworthy Autonomous Systems (TAS) Hub

This research undertaking coordinates the interdisciplinary work of six British research nodes “... *to establish a collaborative platform for the UK to deliver world-leading best practices for the design, regulation and operation of ‘socially beneficial’ autonomous systems. These systems should be trustworthy in principle and trusted in practice by individuals, society and government.*”³

The coordinated research is focused on the solution of three **grand challenges about Trustworthy Autonomous Systems (TAS)**⁴: Three grand challenges for TAS

1. To ensure **TAS** improve rather than harm our physical and mental wellbeing.
2. To ensure TAS safeguard rather than undermine our personal freedoms.
3. To ensure TAS benefit rather than damage our society and the economy.

The work of the six research nodes is structured into the topics

- Governance and regulation
- Functionality⁵
- Verifiability⁶
- Trust
- Resilience⁷
- Security

1.3 RoboStar*

is one of the largest research groups in the world on software engineering for robotics. Its aim is to bring a diverse membership of researchers working in robotics under a single umbrella.⁸. It contributes to the activities of the TAS Hub (resilience and verifiability) and has its own focus projects

¹<https://www.york.ac.uk/assuring-autonomy/>

²<https://www.york.ac.uk/assuring-autonomy/body-of-knowledge/>

³<https://www.tas.ac.uk/aboutus/overview/>

⁴<https://www.tas.ac.uk/grand-challenges/>

⁵<https://tasfunctionality.bristol.ac.uk>

⁶<https://verifiability.org>

⁷<https://resilience.tas.ac.uk/home>

⁸<https://robostar.cs.york.ac.uk>

- RoboCalc: A Calculus for Software Engineering of Mobile and Autonomous Robots⁹
- RoboTest: Systematic Model-Based Testing and Simulation of Mobile Autonomous Robots
- CyPhyAssure: Compositional Safety Assurance for CPS¹⁰
- RoboTIC@ - Information and Communication Technology for Robotics and Applications
- Requirements Modelling for CPS¹¹

1.4 DFG Project CPOT-SM

In parallel to HiDyVe, other members of the research team at the University of Bremen work on the project **Complete Property-oriented Testing With Symbolic Methods (CPOT-SM)** which is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation).¹² In CPOT-SM, test suites with guaranteed error detection capabilities are investigated, with the objective to verify that the System Under Test (**SUT**) satisfies certain properties (typically, these are system or software requirements and refinements thereof). The results obtained in CPOT-SM are used and further refined in HiDyVe, to show that ultra-complex, potentially autonomous, safety-critical **CPS** can be verified by these high-strength testing strategies with acceptable effort.

Property-oriented testing

1.5 Unique Selling Points of Project HiDyVe

It should be noted already here and will be explained in the subsequent chapters that HiDyVe is not just a “me-too-project” doing again on a smaller scale what the projects listed above already cover. Indeed, our project has the following **unique selling points (USPs)**.

The
HiDyVe
USPs

1. The HiDyVe focus is on avionic systems for manned civil aircrafts or smaller air vehicles, with a lesser focus on autonomous train control. In contrast to that, the projects referenced above mainly address robotics and autonomous road vehicles.
2. The HiDyVe view on assurance-related challenges is more general: we plan to address *all* complexity issues of current and future **CPS**, regardless whether these issues have been caused by the introduction of **AI** into system applications or by other complexity drivers (see Chapter 2). The projects listed above have a strong focus on **AI**-related complexity issues.

From the perspective of the three grand challenges defined by the TAS Hub introduced above, HiDyVe contributes solutions to the first challenge

*“to ensure **TAS** improve rather than harm our physical and mental wellbeing”*

Instead of focussing on trustworthy autonomous systems alone, the HiDyVe scope is broader in the sense that it investigates **V&V** and certification challenges presented by arbitrary **CPS** of very high complexity. This will be elaborated in Chapter 2.

⁹<https://www.cs.york.ac.uk/circus/RoboCalc/>

¹⁰<https://www.cs.york.ac.uk/circus/CyPhyAssure/>

¹¹<https://robostar.cs.york.ac.uk/projects/requirements-modelling-for-cyberphysical-systems.html>

¹²project number 407708394

Chapter 2

Project HiDyVe – the Main Challenges

2.1 HiDyVe Application Scenarios

An introduction into the HiDyVe project, a description of the main challenges, and an illustrating example have been given in the YouTube video

[Project intro in YouTube video](#)

HiDyVe–
Highly Dynamic Virtual and Hybrid Validation and Verification
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KipGl4Qgs9k>
presented by Jan Peleska.

Note that the example discussed there has been chosen from the railway domain (autonomous freight train), because it has far fewer degrees of freedom and can therefore be easier explained than the “real” project application scenarios defined by Airbus.

As consortium leader, Airbus has defined three application scenarios whose comprehensive **V&V** will certainly require new verification methodology and a new edition of certification-related standards.

2.2 Formation Flight

Recall that platooning is a technique applied to several trucks driving

[Formation flight](#)

close to each other in a row, with the objective to save fuel or even allow some of the truck drivers to rest, while their trucks autonomously maintain their position in the platoon. **Formation flight** (Figure 2.1) is the avionic analogue to platooning: it allows several civil aircrafts to fly “in line”, with the objective to save fuel. Formation flight should require a minimum of pilot interventions, in the best case it would be autonomously controlled by an avionic system similar to, or an extension of an auto pilot.

Figure 2.1: Formation flight.

2.3 **ATTOL**

Automatic taxiing, take-off, and landing (**ATTOL**) aims at letting **ATTOL** an aircraft perform these activities autonomously, without requiring pilot intervention (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Automatic Taxiing, Take-off and Landing (ATTOL).

2.4 Autonomous Taxi Drones/Vehicles.

The Pop.Up prototype has been developed by Airbus, Audi, and Italdesign (Figure 2.3). It features a passenger capsule which can be attached on top of an electric car chassis or underneath a drone. Without requiring the presence of a driver or pilot, passengers are transported by the autonomously controlled capsule-cum-chassis/drone over streets or through the air to reach their destination.

Fully
autonomous
passenger
transport

This concept could be extended to collaborating surface vehicles and drones (Figure 2.4): a communication and control center could dispatch several drones and vehicle chassis to cooperate with the objective to transport a large group of passengers from some starting point to their destinations. Passengers could arrive at the starting point with other traffic means or already in passenger capsules, but all should be transported to their destination by such capsules. Using distributed multi agent technology, the utilisation of surface vehicle chassis, drones, and capsules could be

Collaborating
autonomous
vehicles

optimised according to different objectives (minimal energy consumption, fastest transport option depending on the current traffic situation, ...).

Figure 2.3: Taxi drones — Pop.Up concept by Audi, Airbus and Italdesign.

Figure 2.4: Collaboration scenario of autonomous surface vehicles and aerial vehicles.

The application scenarios described above have different functional complexity, and they require different levels of autonomous behaviour. We will use them to illustrate different aspects of challenging systems, whose implications for new **V&V** paradigms and novel certification approaches will be investigated in the course of this project.

Use of application scenarios

2.5 Analysis of Complexity Problems

The need for new approaches for **V&V** and certification of safety-critical systems is caused by the exponentially growing application complexity in general, but additionally by the utilisation of new technology – in particular the use of artificial intelligence in avionic systems – which has not been admissible in the safety critical systems domain until today. As analysed in [127], this poses an interdisciplinary challenge, involving many different areas, as shown in Figure 2.5.

Growing complexity plus new technology

Figure 2.5: According to [127], many different problem areas in the field of autonomous vehicles require a coordinated, inter-disciplinary approach to ensure safety.

Note that project HiDyVe is not specialised on analysing the problems caused by **AI** alone – this is already done in many research communities. Instead, HiDyVe aims at addressing *all* issues of application complexity to be expected in the future, as long as these affect **V&V** and certification. Our view on complexity issues affecting **V&V** and certification is expressed in Figure 2.6.

Ultra-high
application
complexity

Definition 1 (Ultra-high complexity)

We use the term **ultra-high complexity** for applications whose complexity prevents the application of conventional **V&V** methods or conventional certification approaches alone. We call the systems containing applications of ultra-high complexity **challenging**. Systems containing components of ultra-high complexity are called **ultra-complex systems**.

To contrast ultra-complex systems with more conventional ones, we use the term **conventional systems** for those systems that can be verified and validated by conventional methods and – in case of safety-criticality – certified according to existing standards.

Conventional
systems

In the subsequent sections, we will analyse the causes leading to ultra-high application complexity and explain in each case why conventional **V&V** and conventional certification approaches do not suffice to provide comprehensive justifications that systems containing these applications are sufficiently dependable to become operational. This requires an introduction of some more terminology.

Figure 2.6: The HiDyVe view on application complexity affecting V&V and certification.

Definition 2 (Conventional system development)
 We use the term **conventional system development** if a Hardware (HW)/SW system is developed according to today’s accepted model-based systems engineering (Model-based Systems Engineering (MBSE)) standards and guidelines.

Conventional system development guarantees, among other things, that the required functional, structural, and non-functional features can be fully captured in formal models (even if in practise, the full degree of mathematical formality is not always applied).

Definition 3 (Conventional V&V)

We use the term **conventional V&V** for verification and validation measures admissible or required according to the current avionic standards RTCA DO-178C [206] or similar standards in the automotive domain (ISO26262 [109]) and railway domain (EN50128 [40]), as well as the current associated standards on system level.

If conventional **V&V** can be applied, it is ensured, for example, that the intended behaviour of a software component *could* always be fully specified with mathematical precision (even if it is not done for many components), if one invested enough time during the specification phase. Moreover, conventional **V&V** provides comprehensive test and analysis results *covering all possible system behaviours* as input to the type certification process.

Definition 4 (Conventional certification)

We use the term **conventional certification** for certification procedures working with the artefacts produced by conventional design and conventional **V&V**, and based on the existing standards listed above.

2.6 Ultra-high Application Complexity Caused by Large Designs

In this section, we address the problems caused by systems with too many applicable requirements and too many interactions between components (see boxes #Requirements and #Interactions in Figure 2.6).

Some of today's applications and many more to be developed in the near future are just too large to be captured comprehensively by conventional development methods. They need to implement too many requirements, fulfil too many constraints, and have too many interactions between their

Cannot
construct
comprehensive
specifications
and
models

components, so that it is infeasible to provide a comprehensive model for its intended functional, structural, and non-functional features. While a decade ago, this would have been considered as a weak excuse, the work on autonomous road vehicles has first detected and responded to this phenomenon. As stated, for example, in [100], functional requirements for autonomous cars need to be specified and modelled more formally as a **library of scenarios**: as elaborated in more detail in Section 5.10, a scenario is a behavioural specification describing how one complex state vector describing both the operational environment and the system (in this case, the autonomous car) is transformed over time into some target state.

Example 1. A scenario could specify, for example, a car A following a slower one B. The car A performs a lane change, overtakes B, and changes back into the original lane. □

One scenario is described as comprehensively as possible, with all physical parameters affecting the behaviour during scenario evolution over time, and with a rigorous specification of the expected behaviour of the vehicle during this scenario. The scenario-based approach differs from conventional functional specifications in the following aspects.

Scenarios differ from conventional functional specifications

1. The full specification is represented by a library of scenarios, instead of one comprehensive functional model.
2. The required behaviour of the target system in a given scenario is usually not captured by a deterministic model. Instead, specifications admit a constrained degree of nondeterministic behaviour.
3. Checking the completeness of the scenario library is currently still a research problem

Large designs result in large test suites. Even for medium-sized designs, it is usually infeasible to perform exhaustive¹ test suites, because their size grows with the square of the number of states in the reference model. For black-box tests, the size even grows exponentially in the number of

Unmanageable test effort

¹A test suite is **exhaustive** if it is capable of uncovering *any* deviation between implementation and specification.

additional states used in the implementation, in comparison to the reference model [46].

Example 2. Suppose that the reference model can be specified by means of a deterministic finite state machine with n states. Suppose further, that the implementation has at most a additional states, and that the discrete input alphabet has A elements. Then up to

$$n^2 \cdot A^{a+1}$$

test cases are needed for an exhaustive test suite. If the model has $n = 10$ states, the implementation at most $a = 3$ additional states, and if the alphabet has size $A = 10$, an exhaustive test suite would contain up to $10^2 \cdot 10^{3+1} = 10^6$ test cases. Of course, the concrete number of test cases depends on the reference model. \square

If a large design consists of many concurrent components, the test suite size grows again exponentially with the number of components involved.

Example 3. Suppose that a large design contains k components of the kind described in the previous Example 2. Then the worst-case size of an exhaustive test suite would be

$$(n^2 \cdot A^{a+1})^k$$

If each component needed 10^6 test cases for an exhaustive test, and if we had $k = 10$ components, an exhaustive system test would need up to 10^{60} test cases. Of course, if we had already performed exhaustive tests on component level, we would argue that the test on system level would no longer need to be exhaustive. Still, the exponential growth indicates that also the number of selective system-level tests to be performed can easily become infeasible for large designs, because the selection size should also grow exponentially with the number of concurrent components involved. \square

When applying one of the existing standards for safety-critical systems development, the scenario-based specification approach presents several obvious problems preventing a conventional certification approach.

Certification
obstacles

- The specifications allow for nondeterministic behaviour of the target system, while the applicable standards require determinism.
- The completeness of the scenarios considered during development and V&V cannot be proven with conventional V&V technology.
- The number of test cases to be performed for a trustworthy, that is, “nearly” exhaustive test is too large to be performed on the target hardware in acceptable time.

We will discuss these problems further in Section 5.10 and indicate possible solutions that would allow for conventional systems certification after all.

It should be emphasised that the necessity to use scenarios for describing the required behaviour of autonomous cars has nothing to do with the fact that AI-based functionality is used for implementing this behaviour: it is simply the ultra-high complexity of the different operational situations applicable to vehicles (whether autonomous or controlled by human drivers) and the physical parameters applicable to each of these situations. For vehicles controlled by human drivers, however, it was never necessary to capture these operational situations, because the responsibility for adequate situation-specific behaviour had been *delegated to the human driver*. Now this **situation awareness** is *delegated to electronic controllers inside the car*, and this results in the necessity to capture the relevant operational situations, together with their applicable scenarios.

An example for a scenario catalogue applicable to the autonomous road vehicle domain is given in https://www.asam.net/index.php?eID=dumpFile&t=f&f=4092&token=d3b6a55e911b22179e3c0895fe2caae8f5492467#_examples. These existing catalogues, however, do not claim to be comprehensive. Instead, they provide guidelines and tools for creating additional ones [172].

Moreover, it should be noted that the necessity to introduce scenarios in place of comprehensive specifications has also occurred in other domains: in [159], for example, a case from the railway domain is discussed.

Need for scenario libraries is independent from AI-based functions

Need for scenario libraries occurs in every domain

2.7 Ultra-high Application Complexity Induced by Systems of Systems

Today, many **CPS** are managed independently, but they are still integrated in larger systems, in order to accomplish additional goals they could not reach alone. The overall system, integrating several **CPS**, is called a **system of systems (SoS)**. The individual **CPS** being part of the overall system are called **constituent systems**. The study of SoS is a well-established branch of systems engineering [149].

The SoS characteristics indicated in Figure 2.6 are defined as follows (see [149]).

SoS
characteristics

Definition 5 (SoS Characteristics)

Operational independence Any system that is part of an SoS is independent and is able to operate serviceably if the SoS is disassembled.

Managerial Independence Despite collaborating with the other members of the SoS, the individual systems are self-governing and individually managed so that they “not only can operate independently, they do operate independently.”

Geographic Distribution The parties collaborating in an SoS are distributed over a large geographic extent. Although the geographic extent is defined vaguely, it is stressed that the collaborating systems can only exchange information and not considerable quantities of mass or energy.

Evolutionary Development An SoS's existence and development are evolutionary in the sense that objectives and functionality can be under constant change, as they can be added, modified, or removed with experience. Thus, an SoS never appears completely formed.

Emergent Behaviour Through the collaboration between the systems in an SoS a synergism is reached in which the system behaviour fulfils a purpose that cannot be achieved by, or attributed to, any of the individual systems.

Example 4. Two or more aircrafts (Aircraft (A/C)) flying in formation flight build an SoS: Each aircraft is “managed” independently by its pilot, so it is a constituent system. They agree, however, to fly in formation, in order to save fuel. This is an emergent behaviour, since it would not be achievable by one aircraft alone. The A/Cs can coordinate their formation flight only by means of communication protocols, so they are geographically distributed. Each A/C has functionality which is developed and maintained independently of each other, so evolutionary development applies. □

Example 5. The multitude of communicating computers inside one A/C does *not* build an SoS, because all of them are centrally managed: first, by the A/C manufacturer, later by the airliner. □

Example 6. The European railway network is an SoS: each national railway system is a constituent, managed independently of the railway systems in other countries. The constituents collaborate in order to create useful emergent behaviours, such as enabling trains to cross borders or being able to buy a ticket in one country for travelling to a city in another. □

Example 7. The use case about collaborating drones/vehicles described in Figure 2.4 could be refined in the following way.

- Each drone is an agent operating for the profit of its individual owner.
- The drone owners agree to collaborate for coordinated missions as described in Figure 2.4.
- Another enterprise provides the infrastructure of the coordination centre for multi-drone/vehicle missions.

This is another example of an SoS. The emergent behaviour is the capability to perform coordinated transport missions that could not be performed by one drone/vehicle alone. □

SoS may induce serious problems regarding conventional certification.

Certification
obstacles

1. Due to the size of collaborating constituent systems, the design complexity problems analysed in Section 2.6 are likely to occur in SoS.
2. Due to the evolutionary development of the constituent systems, it is not possible to specify the SoS functionality completely once and for all before type certification time.

As a consequence, certification as a whole of a safety-critical SoS for civil applications has never been performed until today. Also the novel certification-related standards currently under development (see Chapter 20) address the problem of emergent behaviour only on the small scale of behavioural changes of single applications due to **machine learning**. The SoS aspects are not covered at all. Therefore, we discuss an option for novel certification paradigms that could cover safety-critical SoS with emergent behaviour in the future in Chapter 20.

2.7.1 Ultra-high Application Complexity Induced by Interdisciplinary Complexity

In Figure 2.5, the different disciplines involved in introducing autonomous road vehicles into our society have been indicated. As before, it should be noted that complex inter-disciplinary approaches are also required for other complex systems of the future.

Example 8. From a practical point of view, it would be advantageous to introduce a chip card in Germany where payment functions, social security information, health care information, usage of public transport were integrated. Indeed, in other countries (e.g. Taiwan), cards with similar capabilities have already been introduced. The implementation of such a card system could be realised with conventional technology alone. In Germany however, the interdisciplinary complexity regarding

- legal aspects,
- social acceptance, and

- security (in particular, privacy) aspects

alone would make such undertaking infeasible. □

If safety-critical systems have too complex interdisciplinary dependencies, none of today’s standards would be sufficient to cover all of the aspects involved. Consequently, the certification basis for such systems would be unclear.

Certification
obstacles

The new developments in standards discussed in Chapter 20 address this problem to some extent. Moreover, the larger international research projects in the field of autonomous systems referenced in Chapter 1 are interdisciplinary. In our project HiDyVe, the resources for interdisciplinary work are not available. It is intended to make use of the results produced in the larger projects, as far as interdisciplinary aspects are concerned.

2.7.2 Ultra-high Application Complexity Induced by Technological Complexity – Multi-Agent Systems

While **multi-agent systems (MAS)** are still disregarded in the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (**EASA**) AI Roadmap [55], their utilisation for autonomous systems is widely discussed in the research communities (see, for example, [7, 54, 155, 168, 184, 214]). Application of **MAS** seems to be well-suited, if not even indispensable, when shifting strategic planning, decision making, and reactions to risk occurrences from humans (pilots, vehicle drivers) to machines. As stated in [54], **MAS** are used for autonomous systems to facilitate discrete control decisions to switch between different sets of control functions, to switch between control strategies, and to reason about these discrete decisions.

The
importance
of MAS

Programming **MAS**, however, requires a programming paradigm which includes some quite severe certification obstacles. We explain this using the special type of **MAS** called **belief-desire-intention (BDI) agents** (see [32] for a comprehensive introduction). In such a **MAS**, each **BDI** agent operates on

Programming
BDI
agents

beliefs assumptions about the overall system status,

goals objectives to be reached,

plans coded instructions capable of reaching specific goals, depending on the actual context

actions operations to be called during plan executions

Based on its current belief state, each agent can perform deductions, that is, calculate implications from the system state. To this end, basic means of logic programming (similar to Prolog²) are available. To exploit the full power of BDI programming, agents may inform each other about their current belief state during runtime and exchange or even synthesise new plans at runtime³. Any change of the belief state or any reception of a new plan create events for the agent. These events may trigger new plan executions. Two or more plans for different goals may be executed concurrently, if their context conditions all evaluate to true.

It is immediately clear how MAS with BDI agents would simplify, for example, the programming of collaborating drones working on a joint passenger transport mission, as described in Section 2.1.

However, the following aspects of MAS programming, if exploited to their full extent, would prevent a certification of the MAS with conventional means.

Certification
obstacles

- The BDI agent code does not allow for analysis of the full agent behaviour, because the agent may receive plans to execute at runtime that are unknown at type certification time. Therefore, MAS are evolving systems by their very nature.
- The deductions that may be performed at runtime cannot be associated with a worst-case execution time (Worst Case Execution Time (WCET)). Among other reasons, this is caused by the fact that the maximal number of recursions or loops to be performed for a

²<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prolog>

³To this end, the classical concept of interchangeability of code and data known from early functional programming languages like Lisp is applied [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lisp_\(programming_language\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lisp_(programming_language)).

deduction at runtime cannot be predicted at type certification time, because the nature of the deduction is still unknown.

MAS will be discussed again in more detail in Section 5.4, where adequate modelling approaches for cooperating agents are considered.

2.7.3 Ultra-high Application Complexity Induced by Technological Complexity – Deep Neural Networks

An Artificial Neural Network (**ANN**) [4] (often just denoted as Neural Network (**NN**) in the context of computer science and **AI**) is frequently applied in autonomous systems to evaluate high loads of sensor data, in particular, for image recognition. More generally, they are useful for **classifying** situations depending on large loads of input data, provided that equally large **training** sets for “calibrating” the classification function are available.

From an abstract point of view, NNs are powerful *approximation functions* [4, Section 1.2.3], able to approximate nearly any function $\hat{f} : X^k \rightarrow Y$, where X and Y are subsets of \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{Z} , with input vectors $x \in X^k$ as arguments for \hat{f} . For example, \hat{f} might map the pixel values $x \in X^k$ of a camera image to a classification result stating whether there is a specific traffic sign visible in this image or not. Needless to say, that an explicit representation for a correct classification function \hat{f} cannot be given. Instead, a **NN** f is created and trained to approximate \hat{f} as close as possible.

NNs
approximate
unknown
functions

The approximation principle of **NN** consists in instantiating directed graphs (= “networks”) whose inner nodes are called (**artificial**) **neurons**, whereas outer nodes without incoming edges represent inputs and outer nodes without outgoing edges outputs. A neuron processes weighted inputs represented by incoming graph edges. If $x = (x_1, \dots, x_\ell)$ is the vector of inputs processed by a neuron with associated weights $w = (w_1, \dots, w_\ell)$, then the neuron transmits $\Phi(w \cdot x)$, where Φ is an **activation function** mapping the weighted sum (i.e. scalar product) $w \cdot x$ to the result value to be transmitted to other neurons or as final outputs.

Approximation
principle

Deep neural networks (DNN) are created by instantiating layered graph topologies where neurons transmit outputs to one or more other neurons, before the final output (vector) in Y is written (Figure 2.7). After having fixed the **DNN** topology and the type of activation function, the function f represented by the **DNN** still depends on the weights w_i labelling the graph edges. To this end, the **DNN** is trained with samples $(x_p, \hat{y}_p) \in X^k \times Y$, $p = 1, \dots, n$, with the objective to minimise the deviations between the correct results \hat{y}_p and the calculated results $f(x_p)$. The weights w_i are the free variables to be “calibrated” during this minimisation process. The result of the minimisation still depends on the selected loss function to be minimised. For obvious reasons, the **training** sets need to be larger if the **DNN** contains more weights w_i . On the other hand, the approximation of the true function \hat{f} can be made more precise, the larger the **DNN** is chosen.

Figure 2.7: Graph representation of a **DNN** (from [4, Figure 1.11 (c)]).

The characteristic property of **neural networks** is that they do not possess any specifiable behaviour as long as they are untrained. Only by **training** them, they evolve towards some specific behaviour, such as classification of traffic signs provided by camera images. It is infeasible to trace

Certification
obstacles

the precise classification behaviour to be expected back to the code and data structure of the network structure.

This fact is incompatible with current standards for developing software embedded in safety-critical systems. These standards require each software component to adhere to a well-defined (preferably deterministic) behaviour; and it is mandatory to verify how the software structure will reliably produce this behaviour.

As stated in [192],

*The black-box nature of deep **neural networks** (DNNs) makes it impossible to understand why a particular output is produced, creating demand for “**Explainable AI**”.*

Consequently, the use of DNNs for safety-critical applications cannot be verified, validated, or certified by conventional means. We discuss possibilities for new **V&V** and certification paradigms able to gain trust and give certification credit to **DNN**-based applications in Section 17 and Section 18.

2.7.4 Ultra-high Application Complexity Induced by Evolving Behaviour due to Machine Learning

As indicated in Figure 2.6, the behaviour of both multi agent systems and **neural networks** may be affected by **machine learning** procedures improving the application behaviour not only during the development phase, but also during runtime. Thus, systems containing one or both types of **AI** functionality will exhibit evolving behaviour which changes over time, due to learning effects. This means that it is impossible to comprehensively specify their behaviour *once and for all* during type certification.

In the context of **autonomic computing**⁴, the following so-called self-* capabilities have been identified in [123] to be essential for automated system management of complex software systems.

⁴These are configurable software systems that are able to configure, configure, optimise, repair, and protect themselves in an autonomous way, with minimal or no intrusions to be performed by system management personnel.

Self-configuration. Autonomous system configuration on the basis of high-level policies and rules. Autonomous acquisition or creation of detailed configuration data.

Self-optimisation. Autonomous improvement of system performance and efficiency.

Self-healing. Automated detection, diagnostics, and repair of HW and software problems.

Self-protection. Automatic defence against malicious attacks or cascading failures. Autonomous early warning capabilities to anticipate and prevent system-wide failures.

Obviously, these capabilities are of considerable importance to autonomous systems in general, when interpreted in a slightly generalised way.

Example 9. Self-configuration is desirable for Automated Taxiing, Take-off, and Landing (ATTOL) systems: based on the knowledge of start and destination airports, they should autonomously load the current airport layout data (e.g. accessible runways, required detours during taxiing due to construction sites, ...), without explicit loading and configuration instructions from the pilots.

Self-optimisation is a main objective in any autonomous system component capable of learning, especially in **neural networks**. For example, **neural networks** trained for traffic sign recognition could exchange data about failed recognitions and improve their capabilities by learning about the cause of each misclassification and the correct classification result to be produced in this case.

Self-healing is a capability required in any health monitor that autonomously reacts on system faults or external risks. For example, in the case of cooperating drones working on a joint transportation mission, the fault of one drone could lead to a re-configuration integrating a new drone which is operational.

Self-protection is a prominent feature in all autonomous systems depending on a communication infrastructure to be defended against in-

truders. Typically, the self-protection mechanisms are separated into sub-functions for

- autonomous detection of attacks,
- early detection of threats, and
- activation of defensive measures.

□

The evolving behaviour induced by **machine learning** causes exactly the same certification problems as already discussed in the context of SoS: the application behaviour is not fully determined at type certification time.

Certification
obstacles

Possibilities to cope with this type of ultra-high complexity are discussed in Chapter 20.

2.8 Domain Aspects

2.9 Automotive Domain

The development, **V&V**, and the certification of autonomous systems have been most intensively studied in the automotive domain. On the one hand, there is a very convincing business case for autonomous road vehicles which includes improved safety and significantly improved traffic flow.⁵ On the other hand, when compared to the avionic domain and the railway domain, autonomous road vehicles present the greatest challenge. To explain this just with a few examples:

Autonomous
road
vehicles
present
the
hardest
challenge

- While autonomous aircrafts and trains can rely on “good natured” cooperation of their environment (other aircrafts, control towers, trains, interlocking systems, radio block stations, ...) and communication over well-defined protocols, autonomous cars are operated in a heterogeneous environment.

⁵Note that the validity of these business case aspects has not yet been proven!

- Most elements of this heterogeneous environment are not prepared to communicate with autonomous cars over well-defined protocols: think of pedestrians, cyclists, skaters, and conventional cars, traffic lights and traffic signs.
- Consequently, autonomous road vehicles have the hardest challenge to construct a trustworthy representation of their operational environment. For example, image recognition functions for autonomous road vehicles needs to identify different types of traffic lights and signs, whereas image recognition for autonomous trains is just needed to detect obstacles on the rails.⁶
- Autonomous road vehicles need to cope with far more **unexpected risks** than trains or aircrafts, because their operational environment is far less controlled.

Aspects of the automotive domain are relevant for HiDyVe in the context of the third case study (autonomous taxi drones and cars).

2.10 Robotics

In robotics, the challenges are nearly as high as in the automotive domain, if robots are expected to interact safely with humans in unconstrained environments. Examples are household robots and robots in health care. Just as autonomous road vehicles, this type of robot needs to create representations of complex operating environments, and they need to cope with unexpected risks.

Autonomous robots are not considered in this project. They are comprehensively studied in the projects referenced in Chapter 1.

⁶There is no need for signals in modern railways, since movement authority is sent from radio block stations to trains via mobile communication devices.

2.11 Avionic Domain

When analysing the use cases from the avionic domain described in Section 2.1, our current assessment is as follows.

1. The formation flight application can be developed, verified, and certified by conventional means. This assessment is based on the fact that auto pilots and airborne collision avoidance system (Airborne collision avoidance system (*ACAS*)) could be handled in a conventional way as well.
2. Automatic taxiing, take-off, and landing (*ATTOL*) might possibly be developed, verified, and certified with conventional means, too: unlike autonomous road vehicles, one could expect that *ATTOL* is performed based on fixed protocols and on pre-defined routes through the airport (no spontaneous route changes of the *A/C* due to a traffic jam ...). In such a controlled environment, image analysis would only be needed for the detection of static or moving obstacles. This detection does not require the use of *neural networks* (see also Section 2.12).
3. The full autonomous taxi drone-cum-car use case is obviously at least as complex as the autonomous road vehicle problem. Therefore, this type of systems cannot be developed, verified, and certified by conventional means. The ultra-high complexity will even be increased further if drones and taxis should collaborate to solve more complex transport missions.

It is noteworthy that the problem becomes less complex (but, according to our assessment, still remains ultra-high complex) if only flying drones and not taxiing on roads is considered. In this case, the complexities of *road furniture (also street furniture)* detection with traffic sign recognition, as well as the reactions to spontaneous manoeuvres of other cars with human drivers, cyclists, pedestrians, skate boarders, ... would no longer be present.

It will be one of the main objectives of HiDyVe to investigate whether these hypotheses are correct.

Table 2.1: Grade of Automation definition in the railway domain.

GoA	Definition
GoA 0	No automation.
GoA 1	A train driver controls starting and stopping, operation of doors and handling of emergencies or sudden diversions. Overseen signals due to human errors are safeguarded by train protection systems.
GoA-2	Starting and stopping are automated using advanced train protection systems, but a driver operates the doors, drives the train if needed and handles emergencies. Many <i>automated train operation (ATO)</i> systems are GoA 2. In this system, trains run automatically from station to station, but a driver is in the cab, with responsibility for door closing, obstacle detection on the track in front of the train and handling of emergency situations. As in a GoA 3 system, the GoA 2 train cannot operate safely without the staff member on board.
GoA 3	Starting and stopping are automated, but a train attendant operates the doors and drives the train in case of emergencies. In this system, trains run automatically from station to station but a staff member is always in the train, with responsibility for handling of emergency situations. In a GoA 3 system, the train cannot operate safely without the staff member on board.
GoA 4	Starting, stopping and operation of doors are all fully automated without any on-train staff. It is recommended that stations have platform screen doors installed. In this system, trains are capable of operating automatically at all times, including door closing, obstacle detection and emergency situations. On-board staff may be provided for other purposes, e.g. customer service, but are not required for safe operation. Controls are often provided to drive the train manually in the event of a computer failure.

2.12 Railway Domain

In the railway domain, four *grades of automation (Grade of Automation (GoA))* are distinguished, as defined in Table 2.1⁷.

Automatic vehicle control is a well-established technique in the railway domain. In contrast to the avionic and automotive domain, automatic rail-based solutions became operational already many years ago, but only for

⁷This definition has been copied from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Automatic_train_operation.

Automatic train control is well-established in segregated environments

segregated environments [169]: In these environments, the track sections are protected from unauthorised access, and ubiquitous comprehensive automation technology is available, such as line transmission or radio communication for signalling, precise positioning information, as well as platform screen doors supporting safe boarding and deboarding of passengers between trains and platforms.

In contrast to this, the certifiability of autonomous train control systems with GoA 4 in open railway environments, where unauthorised access to track sections, absence of platform screen doors, and less advanced technology (e.g. visual signalling) have to be taken into account, is still an open problem. This scenario is of high economic interest, and first prototype solutions have recently become available [187], but none of them has yet achieved GoA 4 with full type certification.

We list some noteworthy examples of GoA 4 trains in segregated environments that are operative today.

- The Paris Metro Line 14 which entered service in 1998 is the first driverless metro developed with a rigorous formal methods approach [133].
- Driverless people movers are used in nearly all larger airports of the world.
- In Australia, the first GoA 4 freight train has become operational in 2018⁸.
- In France, the national railway organisation SNCF intends to introduce both driverless passenger trains and freight trains, with first semi-automated routes becoming operational already in 2023⁹.

As suggested by Flammini et al. [65], there should be a clear distinction between *automatic* and *autonomous* train control. The former term 'Automatic' vs. 'autonomous'

⁸<https://www.railfreight.com/technology/2019/01/04/rollout-worlds-first-driverless-freight-train-network-complete/>

⁹<https://www.sncf.com/en/innovation-development/innovation-research/driverless-trains-to-run-in-2023>

(‘automatic’) should be used, if trains are operated without driver or staff supervision, but all behavioural situations (including emergency situations) are pre-defined, so that the train control system has no degrees of freedom with respect to decision making in any of these situations (including system degradation and emergency events). The latter term (‘autonomous’) should only be used if the train’s behaviour emerges from dynamic evaluation of the current state obtained by sensing and perception, and this may lead to new behaviours that were not envisaged at type certification time. As of today, many researchers and practitioners in the railway domain agree that

- automatic train operation ATO can be autonomous (for example, optimisation of acceleration and braking to reduce passenger discomfort and energy consumption), since it does not involve safety-critical decisions, but
- automated train protection (ATP) should be conventionally developed, with behaviours that are completely specified at type certification time. The only part where GoA 4 ATP needs to rely on machine learning and AI-based components is the perception component of the autonomy pipeline, to enable obstacle detection [162].

Apart from the obvious fact that, compared to road vehicles and aircrafts, trains running on rails have fewer degrees of freedom than the former, there are several other aspects facilitating autonomous train control.

Why
autonomous
train
control is
“easier”

- Since the European Train Control System standard (European Train Control Systems (ETCS)) [59] is well-established, virtual signalling information¹⁰ can be transmitted, so that the visual interpretation of signal aspects or anything comparable to road traffic signs has become unnecessary – at least on modernised parts of the European railway network. Therefore, image interpretation is only necessary for the recognition of obstacles.
- Autonomous acceleration and braking control has been integrated in trains for years. At first as an assistance function, nowadays as a

¹⁰so-called **marker boards**: movement authority information transmitted from radio block centres to trains

means to save energy and facilitate the job of the train engine driver. Since the train travels along known routes, the location-dependent maximal speed allowed along these routes is always available.

- Autonomous trains (e.g. freight trains running interleaved with “regular” passenger trains) will not be allowed to start their journey spontaneously: they are integrated into the global time table applicable to all trains traversing the railway network.¹¹ Consequently, there is no need for agent-based systems negotiating starting and arrival times and routes through the network.
- Autonomous trains could be remotely controlled from the interlocking/radio block centre in case of emergencies, for example, if the presence of an obstacle cannot be decided by the autonomous system alone.

Apart for the safety-critical task of obstacle detection, artificial intelligence is of considerable interest for less safety-critical railway applications, such as maintenance and planning¹². In contrast to trains, it is well understandable that autonomous tramways are still considered as a research topic [23]: since trams are usually not strictly separated from other road vehicles or pedestrians, the requirements for online image recognition applicable to trams would be quite similar to that of autonomous cars.

AI
applications
in less
critical
areas

2.13 A Theoretical Distinction between “Conventional” and “Challenging” Systems

The following theoretical considerations are inspired by the automotive standard

ISO 26262
vs. ISO 21448

¹¹This holds at least for Germany.

¹²<https://www.aitrends.com/ai-in-industry/autonomous-freight-trains-powered-by-ai-coming/>

- ISO 26262 – Road vehicles – **Functional safety** – Part 4: Product development: system level [109], and the draft international standard
- ISO 21448 – Road vehicles – Safety of the intended functionality [104].

The former covers development and **V&V** requirements to ensure that safety-related functions (in road vehicles) are implemented *as specified*. This aims at verification of functional correctness. The latter has been created to define measures ensuring that the *intended* safety-related functionality will be available in the vehicle. This aims at validation of safety-related functionality. ISO 21448 deliberately takes into account, that a correctly implemented function could be (among other reasons) insufficiently specified and therefore not perform as originally intended.

A theoretically relevant question is: how can we decide whether an intended safety-related function can be effectively specified and verified to fulfil its intended objective (so we could apply conventional standards like ISO 26262 or RTCA DO-178C [206]), and where does the technology for realising this function prevent us from rigorously validating specifications and implementations, so that measures as compiled in ISO 21448 need to be applied?

Which systems are “challenging”?

We suggest the following criterion for the distinction of “conventional” and “challenging” systems:

- If the **intended** functionality can be specified *before type certification* in a formal logic which is associated with a proof theory allowing to derive that a formal model (or software code written in a semantically well-defined programming [sub-]language) fulfils the specification, the (sub-)system to be developed is “conventional” and can be verified and validated according to conventional safety-related standards like [109, 206].
- Otherwise the system is “challenging”, and new **V&V** measures, as, for example, described and envisioned in [55, 104] need to be applied.

“conventional”

“challenging”

Example 10. Consider a safety mechanism in a level 3 (conditional driving **automation**) autonomous car specified as follows.

Conventional safety mechanism

If the vehicle speed exceeds v_{max} , the autonomous driving functions need to be de-activated, so that the driver takes full responsibility over vehicle control.

We can formalise this specification by introducing a Boolean variable A stating that autonomous driving is active if and only if A evaluates to true, and a variable v denoting the actual speed. The specification can now be formalised using, for example, linear temporal logic (LTL) [47] as

$$\mathbf{G} (v > v_{max} \Rightarrow \mathbf{X}(\neg A))$$

Translated back into natural language this reads “*It is globally true that whenever v exceeds v_{max} , variable A is false in the next step (processing cycle).*”

We can create, for example, a SysML state machine or a function programmed in C and prove, using LTL model checking or Hoare logic that the model or the code fulfils the formula. Crucial to this verification is that the parameters ‘speed’ and ‘autonomous driving function status’ addressed in the specification can be directly specified as model or code variables v , A . Therefore, the model or the code can be traced back to the specification formula in an unambiguous way. Consequently this safety function is conventional. \square

Example 11. Consider now a safety-relevant image recognition function needed for autonomous taxiing of aircrafts in an airport, specified by

While taxiing, the function recognises the dynamic obstacles bus, car, baggage carrier, pedestrian, other aircrafts and static obstacles with probability greater or equal to 99.9991%.

Challenging application: image recognition

The image recognition function is implemented, say, by a **deep learning** neural network consisting of layers of weighted function nodes and edges. As input, the network gets a pixel matrix, and as output, it delivers a classification result “no obstacle – bus – car ...”. The choice of weights

has been optimised during a **training** phase with a set of images showing examples of the obstacles to recognise.

In contrast to the previous example, the intended functionality (the obstacles to recognise) are only represented implicitly in the network. The crucial problem is that no formal logic is available which allows to prove step by step that any pixel matrix containing, for example, a bus will be mapped by the function nodes, edges, and the selected weights to classification result ‘bus’ with sufficient probability.

Consequently, this function is “challenging”. □

Example 12. Consider a multi agent system (**MAS**) used to control one or more autonomous vehicles. As explained in the video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KipGl4Qgs9k>, the agents’ software can be verified in the conventional way, if all plans are pre-defined and encoded inside the agents executing them. Restricted this way, the **MAS** can be regarded as “conventional”.

Conventional
or
challenging:
MAS

If, however, today’s **MAS** technology is fully exploited, agents will exchange plans and even synthesise new plans at runtime and execute them after reception [32]. This means that agents may execute code that was “invisible” at type certification time. Therefore, the evolving behaviour of the agents cannot be specified completely before type certification, and, consequently, also not verified completely before that time. Under these circumstances, the **MAS** has to be considered as “challenging”. Here, the logical problem is more trivial than in Example 11: it is impossible to specify or verify something that is unknown, regardless of the logic that could be applied. At runtime, after having created and exchanged the new plans, they could very well be formalised and verified with a suitable logic and associated proof rules. □

It is interesting to note that, in order to establish justified trust for the two challenging applications from Example 11 and 12, completely different approaches are suggested according to the current state of the art and according to our own investigations. This will be elaborated in more details in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 3

HiDyVe Research Questions

In this chapter, we list the subset of the **RQ** identified in the subsequent chapters that is handled by the research team of the University of Bremen in the context of HiDyVe. The fourth column refers to the HiDyVe work package where (see also the work package break down structure shown in Figure 1) the **RQ** is investigated. Note that some of the research questions are answered directly inside the present document.

Table 3.1: Research questions investigated in Project HiDyVe.

Id	Description of RQ	See Sections	WP
RQ01	How should scenario libraries for complex systems be modelled, and is SysML V2 well-suited for this purpose?	5.9, 5.10	WP220
RQ02	How should the completeness of scenario libraries be verified?	5.10.4, 5.10.5	WP220, WP240
RQ03	Is it possible to perform property-oriented testing of software <i>without</i> an initial model and still obtain complete test suites <i>proving</i> that the SUT fulfils the specified properties?	III	WP240
RQ04	Can the results of RQ03 be generalised for system testing?	III	WP240
RQ05	Will conformance testing become an accepted V&V approach in future standards for safety-critical CPS (recall that currently, only property-oriented testing is accepted).	III, 20, 29	WP230, WP240, WP340

Continued on next page

Id	Description of RQ	See Sections	WP
RQ06	Which boundary conditions need to be fulfilled in order to obtain certification credit for tests performed in cloud simulation environments?	19, 20	WP240, WP340, WP420
RQ07	Can Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) help to identify classification clusters in Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) used for safety-critical image classifications ?	18	WP240
RQ08	Can we establish a sound statistical approach for estimating the residual property for misclassifications in CNN ?	18	WP240
RQ09	Is it possible to establish a sound development work flow for safety supervisors, guaranteeing that the supervisor implementation fulfils its original specification?	14	WP240
RQ10	Can we identify classes of autonomous, safety-critical CPS that could already be certified and become operative today?	4.6, 22.3, 14	WP220, WP240, WP340
RQ11	Is runtime certification an acceptable methodology for complementing type certification of safety-critical CPS that change their behaviour over time and collaborate in tasks previously unknown?	20	WP220, WP240, WP340

Part II

**Complex and Autonomous
Systems**

Chapter 4

Functional and Architectural Aspects of Autonomous Systems

4.1 Autonomic Manager and Managed Elements

In the context of autonomous maintenance for challenging software configurations, the authors of [123] introduced the conceptual model shown in Figure 4.1. This so-called **MAPE paradigm** (monitor, analyse, plan, execute – this is also called the **autonomy pipeline** [199]) has become an “accepted way of thinking” about autonomous systems in general.¹ The overall autonomous system consists of

- **Managed elements.** These may or may not be equipped with **AI** components, but always provide interfaces informing about their local status and accepting configuration and control commands from another layer.

Managed elements vs. autonomic managers

¹It should be noted, however, that this paradigm has at least been implied already in 1986 by the article [33] on mobile robot control. Also, the generic architecture suggested in [188] may be interpreted as an instance of the Monitor, Analyse, Plan, Execute (execution cycle of autonomic managers) (**MAPE**) paradigm.

- **Autonomic managers.** These components apply AI concepts to control their managed elements in the most effective way possible.

The autonomic managers perform processing cycles which are typical for AI applications.

Figure 4.1: Autonomic manager and managed element, as suggested in [123].

1. The **monitor** collects state information from the managed elements. This may lead to an update of a knowledge database.
2. The **knowledge database** contains a static part with pre-defined rules and plans about how to act on the managed elements. Moreover, the knowledge base contains a dynamic part with state information about the managed elements.
3. Based on static and dynamic information stored in the knowledge base, the **analyser** decides whether a new objective should be reached.
4. One or more **plans** are collected from the knowledge base or even synthesised or downloaded from other repositories at runtime, such

Processing
cycle of
autonomic
managers

that the current objectives can be reached by executing the compiled plans.

5. During **plan execution**, actions act on the managed elements that in turn change their state. Some plans need to be executed over a longer time period. Therefore, they are preemptively scheduled over several processing cycles.
6. After the (stepwise) execution of plans, the processing cycle is repeated.

The **MAPE** paradigm has been comprehensively realised, for example, in the concrete architectures of **Belief-Desire-Intention (BDI) Agents**; these are discussed in more detail in Section 5.4,

The **MAPE** paradigm has been widely adopted as the basis of concrete architectures for autonomous systems. It is also referenced in the pre-standard [104] for safety in autonomous road vehicles (see Figure 4.2). This pre-standard is discussed further in Chapter 20.

MAPE
according
to
ISO21448

Figure 4.2: Sense-plan-act model for target system decomposition, as suggested in [104, Figure 4].

In the pre-standard ANSI/UL 4600 [199], the **autonomy** pipeline is more refined and structured into

sensing → *perception* → *planning* → *prediction* → *control*
→ *actuation*.

MAPE
according
to
ANSI/UL 4600

4.2 Refining MAPE for BDI Agents

One of the most popular techniques for implementing the **MAPE** paradigm uses belief-desire-intention (**BDI**) agents, which currently represent the most popular version of multi-agent systems (**MAS**).²

Figure 4.3: Procedural reasoning system of **BDI** agents according to [32].

For **BDI** agents, the knowledge base of the **MAPE** paradigm has been refined into four components, as shown in Figure 4.3.

- Beliefs,
- desires,
- intentions, and

²**BDI** agents have already been mentioned in Section 2.7.2 in the context of ultra-high complexity.

- plan library.

The **beliefs** represent an abstraction of the agent state and its environment, *as perceived by the agent*. The term ‘belief’ emphasises that different agents may have differing, even contradicting, perceptions of the environment state. The **desires** store all objectives that an agent might ever want to achieve. Each desire is associated with a plan from the **plan library**. Each plan specifies the pre-conditions for its execution and the actions to implement it. The **intentions** represent the subset of desires that the agent tries to realise in the current situation.

The **interpreter** implements the **MAPE** processing cycle: it evaluates the sensor data, updates the beliefs in the knowledge base, and revises and executes the plans associated with the current intentions. These executions lead to actions on the agent’s environment. The desires-portion of the knowledge base may also be updated through other agents sending new plans, or through synthesisation of new plans during runtime.

4.3 General System Architecture

The following more concrete, but still partially generic layered system architecture is well-suited to design concrete systems according to the **MAPE** paradigm. We describe these layers in bottom-up direction.

Figure 4.4: Generic system architecture for autonomous vehicles, as suggested in [205].

4.3.1 Physical layer.

The physical layer of an autonomous system directly interacts with its environment via sensors and actuators.³ Sensors deliver raw data to the control layer, such as GPS position data, Light Detection and Ranging device (LIDAR) range information, or camera pixel data. Actuators receive commands from the control layer and directly act on motors, valves etc.

³Further physical means of interaction, like wheels or A/C engines, wings etc. are not considered.

The physical layer realises through its sensors the “low-level portion” of the monitor component in the **MAPE** paradigm. Through its actuators, it realises the lower part of the execute component.

4.3.2 Control layer.

The control layer performs low-level control tasks. Sensor raw data is refined and passed on to the layer above. This refinement will typically involve **AI** methods, such as image recognition with the help of **neural networks**. However, the sensor analysis may also result in direct commands to actuators; for example; as a result of low-level health and safety analysis (see Section 4.5 and 4.6). For example, low-level obstacle detection can be performed without the help of **AI** methods in the control layer, just by observing changes in the camera raw data. Preferably, the interaction between sensor data analysis and actuator control is performed without any **AI** methods, so that the control layer can be verified and certified with conventional methods [127].

Control
layer

The control layer realises the upper level of the **MAPE** paradigm's monitor and execute components.

4.3.3 Tactical layer.

In this layer, the first main objective is to provide **situation awareness**, that is, an abstracted state representation of the system and its operational environment. Here, the application of **AI** methods is prevalent, in order to grasp the advantages and risks involved in the actual situation. The second main objective is to adjust the planning status to the actual situation, for the purpose of achieving mission goals or avoiding unacceptable risks brought up by the actual situation.

Tactical
layer

Situation awareness is roughly equivalent to the knowledge base in the **MAPE** paradigm. The tactical layer realises the lower level of the **MAPE** components analyse and plan.

4.3.4 Strategic layer.

In the strategic layer, the mission⁴ status is analysed on the basis of the current situation, and the mission planning is refined.⁵ The revised mission status is decomposed into a list of smaller tasks⁶ and communicated to the task layer

Strategic
layer

The rule database used by both task planning and mission planning contains, for example, fundamental (that is, situation-independent) rules for decision making.⁷

The strategic layer realises the higher levels of the **MAPE** components analyse and plan.

4.4 Architectural Aspects Supporting Resilience

Recall that *resilience* is the quality of a system to continue its operation (at least in some degraded mode) under adverse conditions. For conventional systems, such conditions are (see Leveson [136] for a detailed exposition)

1. hardware failures (of the system under consideration),
2. software failures,
3. security attacks,
4. hazards and failures in the operational environment.

Achieving resilience for conventional systems is well understood today, the most important methods can be classified as

- fault detection mechanisms (for example, error detection and error correction codes)

⁴To provide an example, a mission could be “*Drive from A to B with minimal energy consumption*”.

⁵For example, the route to reach B could be changed, due to the actual traffic situation.

⁶First drive to A_1 , then to A_2 , and from there to B.

⁷A typical rule could be “*The mission goal shall be aborted if the risk involved in reaching the goal is higher than $\epsilon > 0$.*”

- fault-tolerance,
- safety mechanisms (e.g., fail-safe mechanisms),
- security mechanisms (from password protection to encryption to intrusion detection).

These admissible techniques implementing these methods have been clearly identified in modern standards [40, 41, 101, 102, 103]. For autonomous systems, additional factors with impact on resilience have to be considered:

1. Sensor resilience is needed to ensure the continuous provision of trustworthy input data for the perceptors.
2. Perceptors (often trained by machine learning methods) need to produce trustworthy results for updating the system state, including the perceived environment state.
3. Task planning and mission planning need to produce timely and trustworthy decisions ensuring the uninterrupted and safe continuation of the mission.

The first and second factor achieve resilience by means of sensor fusion, using orthogonal technologies [64, 162]. The verification of trained perceptors is a research topic on its own; it will be investigated in depth in HiDyVe work package WP240 (Test Strategies&Coverage Analysis). Similarly, resilience of task planners and mission planners is a large and challenging research field. This is outside the scope of the HiDyVe project, because we focus on solutions for ultra-complex systems where task planning and mission planning can be achieved with conventional methods, so that safety-critical AI-based techniques are encapsulated in the perception part of the autonomy pipeline. According to our assessment, this is the only option leading to certifiable autonomous systems in the near future.

4.5 Architectural Aspects of Health Monitors (**BITE**)

From today's A/C built with conventional technology it is well-known that

Proactive
health
monitoring

health monitors (also called built-in test equipment (**BITE**)) are necessary to supervise the operational status of **A/C** sub-systems. Within the last 20 years, health monitoring has become an increasingly *proactive* task, aiming at forecasting faults of **HW** components (e.g. malfunction of a smoke sensor), so that these parts can be replaced before they fail during operation. Moreover, **HW**-related problems detected during flight are communicated to ground crews, so that they can prepare maintenance measures even before the **A/C** has reached its destination. With the advent of integrated modular **avionics** (Integrated Modular Avionics (**IMA**)), health monitoring has been extended to systematic supervision of **A/C** controller status.

A characteristic of health monitors is that they perform **passive tests**: they do not intervene with the **A/C** operation, but only provide information about faults and resulting malfunctions.

Obviously, health monitors are needed even more urgently in challenging systems. Their functionality will be significantly extended to support

New tasks
for health
monitors

1. detection of malicious attacks on communication interfaces,
2. detection of deviations from expected behaviour in critical sub-systems,
3. detection of deviations from expected behaviour in emergent SoS behaviour,
4. provision of fault-related data to components ensuring adequate situation awareness, and
5. identification of **root causes** for malfunctions, so that proper fault containment measures can be triggered.

Due to these complex and heterogeneous tasks, future health monitors will be distributed over all layers of the system architecture, as shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Generic architecture for autonomous systems from Figure 4.4, extended by health monitors and safety controllers.

Example 13. Considering again the extended generic architecture for autonomous systems in Figure 4.5, we can identify the following layer-specific health monitors:

1. In the control layer, sensor or actuator faults would be detected and communicated to the tactical layer and to a safety controller (see Section 4.6) residing in the control layer. This health monitor is very similar to those already used in today's A/C: it “knows” nothing about the actual situation the autonomous system is in or about the actual mission to be accomplished. It just detects and communicates local component faults.

Moreover, the health monitor in the control layer could detect (otherwise unidentified) obstacles on the current trajectory of a road vehicle. This does not involve any kind of AI functionality: it suffices to evaluate changes in the pixel clouds provided by camera sensors.

2. In the tactical layer, the health monitor detects deviations in the situation data indicating a malfunction threatening the correct execution of the current plans or even the whole mission. In a formation flight, for example, the health monitor of the tactical layer would check if the local *A/C* really saves fuel in the current formation and inform the strategic layer if this is not the case. Again, a layer-specific safety controller would be informed as well.

The tactical layer would also be ideal to detect security attacks. To identify intrusion attempts and other malicious behaviour in an automated way, it is usually necessary to have some situation awareness. This means that abstracted state information is needed in order to identify and analyse exceptional situations.

3. In the strategic layer, a health monitor would find out, for example, if there is no user-defined mission left whose plans could still be executed, due to a system degradation or due to the unacceptable risks involved in continuing to strive for any of the remaining user-defined mission goals.

Again, the health monitor of the strategic layer may contribute to detecting security-related events, since some attacks to be expected and identified may be mission dependent. Therefore, the health monitor of the strategic layer may switch between different techniques of security screening when switching between missions.

□

Note that the design of effective health monitors has become an aspect of a more general research field called **reliability engineering**, see [220]. This more general research field is motivated by the fact that in the *CPS* of today and the near future, the digital, physical, and human domains interact more closely together, with one domain being able to cause beneficial but often also catastrophic effects in any of the other domains.

4.6 Architectural Aspects of Safety Controllers

In conventional systems, the information provided by health monitors is presented to humans (pilots, A/C ground crews, drivers of conventional vehicles) authorised or responsible to react by performing risk mitigating measures. For systems that are challenging according to our definition in Chapter 2, humans capable of responding to problems communicated by health monitors might either not be available at all (in the case of autonomous systems), or they might be incapable of coping with the flood of information provided by the monitors, or they could not react with risk-mitigating measures in hard real-time. Therefore, automated reactions to critical information provided by health monitors need to be implemented in all variants of challenging systems. The components performing these reactions are usually well encapsulated and separated from other applications, and they are usually called **safety monitors** [70]. In analogy to health monitors, safety controllers are typically allocated in several layers of the systems architecture (see Figure 4.5), because they may operate on different levels of abstracted state data and perform different kinds of risk mitigating measures – typically with higher degrees of sophistication on higher architectural layers.

Safety
controllers

Example 14. In an autonomous road vehicle, the safety monitors of the different architectural layers should perform the following tasks (among others not mentioned here).

1. In the control layer, the safety controller would perform low-level recognition of close obstacles (no AI involved, because the kind of obstacle needs not to be identified) and trigger the brakes automatically if required. This is performed in ignorance of the current mission being executed.
2. In the tactical layer, the safety controller will perform more sophisticated risk mitigation measures based on the situation awareness. For example, it could select between a lane change or accelerating the car, if a faster car approaches on the same lane. For the selection

of risk-mitigating measures, it would assess the risks involved with these manoeuvres and select the most appropriate one. Moreover, the safety controller would always try to select a risk mitigation measure which is in accordance with the current task. For example, it would try not to turn into a highway exit if the current task specifies to stay on the highway.

3. On the level of the mission layer, the safety monitor may decide to abort the current mission if this is no longer achievable from the current situation. The safety monitor may decide on the activation of safety-related fall-back missions, such as the *limp home mode*⁸, or changing into the slow lane and stopping on the curb.

□

The authors of [127] point out that the best solution for a complex system is to create a universal safety controller which can be designed and coded as a conventional application. If such a controller exists, the safety case can be built on conventional development techniques and V&V. Other system components containing AI components are regarded as uncritical system components (e.g. with assurance level DAL-D according to RTCA DO-178B), since they are always overridden by the safety controller. Unfortunately, a centralised conventional safety controller is rarely sufficient for challenging systems. As shown in the example above, high-level safety controllers are needed for complex autonomous systems in order to elaborate more complex risk mitigation actions that can only be performed with situation awareness and the knowledge about the actual mission.

Best case:
conventional
safety
controller

The on-board safety controllers may be extended and connected in the future through cloud technology, following the *digital twin* paradigm. Following [146],

Digital
twins
enhancing
safety

“a digital twin is an integrated multi-physics, multiscale, probabilistic simulation of a complex product and uses the best available physical models, sensor updates, etc., to mirror the life of its corresponding twin.”

⁸The car is still allowed to drive, but with limited speed, and on the shortest route home.

The objectives and the extent of this mirroring can be adapted for safety control. The authors of [75] state

*“More specifically, a **digital twin** is a digital reconstruction of a physical system that operates in parallel with the real system. This concurrency persists throughout the life-cycle of the physical system. Communication between the physical hardware and its digital representation is bilateral, and as a result, both are informed by real-world sensor data, requested actions and decisions.”*

Used in this way, the **digital twin** runs like a **back-to-back test** of the real system, and hazards can be detected by the occurrence of deviations between behaviours in the cloud and in the real world. It should be emphasised that this is still a research field. For example, deviations can be admissible, due to nondeterministic decisions in the real-world system. If nondeterminism is unavoidable, the **digital twin** needs to track all possible behaviours and check whether the actual real-world system behaviour is contained in the set of admissible ones.

Furthermore, the **digital twins** can be applied to run simulated acceptance tests in the cloud, before the real-world systems start collaborating on a new mission with new plans.

Figure 4.6: Online execution of **digital twins** in the cloud – example with two collaborating autonomous systems.

This situation is depicted in Figure 4.6. In the real world, systems 1 and 2 autonomously agree on a collaboration which involves new, jointly synthesised plans. Before starting the mission, the collaboration is tested in the cloud. Only when this acceptance test succeeds, the mission is started in the real world.

4.7 Preferred Architectures for Safety-critical Ultra-complex Systems

As pointed out by Koopman et al. [128], suitable architectures for complex (possibly autonomous) safety-critical systems should encapsulate safety-critical components in specific locations of the overall system architecture and clearly separate them from non-critical ones. It would certainly be infeasible to validate and certify an instance of the generic architecture depicted in Figure 4.5, if *every* sub-component would implement certain

safety-critical system aspects. The best case, as identified again by Koopman et al. [126, 127, 128] is where all safety critical system aspects can be encapsulated in sub-components that *can be designed, implemented, verified, validated, and certified in a conventional way*, since aspects of ultra-complex systems (such as machine learning and agent-based planning) do not apply.

The latter case, however, is usually impossible to realise for the case of autonomous systems, since perception requires the use of trained neural networks. It has been shown for the field of autonomous trains, that safety-critical components depending on trained neural networks, can be encapsulated in the perception component of the autonomy pipeline, whereas safety-critical sensors can be developed with conventional technology [162]. Also, the remaining pipeline components planning, prediction, control, and actuation can be developed with conventional means. Such a distribution of responsibilities for autonomous trains is shown in Figure 4.7

Figure 4.7: Separation of safety-critical and non-critical components in the autonomy pipeline for autonomous trains.

The safety critical aspects of *Automated Train Protection (ATP)* depend only in the perception component on trained neural networks; all other ATP aspects (e.g. braking for the end of movement authority or for an obstacle, transiting to a degraded, non-autonomous mode of operation in case of sensor and perceptor failures) can be conventionally developed. In contrast to that, *Automated Train Operation (ATO)* can apply AI-based functions (e.g. optimisation of braking forces, energy saving by optimised

acceleration [187]), since all effects of **ATO** are monitored and can be overridden by **ATP** (e.g. by triggering the emergency brakes) if they would lead to a hazardous system state.

For the perception part, the danger of classification faults can be mitigated by applying sensor fusion with sensors using different technology [64, 162]. Assuring the trustworthiness of trained neural networks at type certification time is possible with novel methods, to be elaborated in the context of HiDyVe work package WP240 [77].

Chapter 5

Modelling Complex Systems

5.1 Basic Ingredients of Modelling Languages

5.1.1 Core Features of Modelling Formalisms

In this section, we review the modelling features that are typically available in modern formalisms or that are of specific importance for systems of ultra-high complexity. These features are displayed in structured form in Figure 5.1 to Figure 5.5. Modelling languages have been investigated since the 1970s, with the objective to find higher-level abstractions for complex software and complete systems to be developed. With the advent of model-driven development approaches, in particular, **model-based systems engineering (MBSE)**, the interest in modelling formalisms has increased once again [167].

As shown in Figure 5.1, the top-level aspects of modelling languages are the structural, behavioural, and requirements sub-models – they will be explained in more detail below. All formalisms of interest for HiDyVe should at least support the modelling of these three aspects (see Section 5.1.2). Several modelling features are available or should become available in the near future, to support modelling of systems with ultra-high complexity. These are discussed in more detail in Section 5.1.3. Just like programming languages, models have (or should have) a well-defined abstract and

MBSE

Three
main
modelling
aspects

Semantics
– meta
model

concrete syntax and static and behavioural semantics. The term introduced by the **Object Management Group (OMG)**¹ for these kinds of syntactic and semantic rules is **meta model**. More details are described in Section 5.1.4. Finally, a model can have several representations, typically a graphical and several textual formats (e.g. Extensible Markup Language (**XML**), json, textual syntax specified within the meta model of the formalism). This is discussed in Section 5.1.5

Figure 5.1: Modelling language features of interest – top-level.

¹<https://www.omg.org>

5.1.2 Structural, Behavioural, and Requirements Modelling

Any modelling formalism supports at least two aspects of software and systems modelling.

Structural modelling is aimed at specifying the system decomposition and its internal and external interfaces. To foster re-use, parameterised components that can be re-used in several places of a model with different parameter values, and object-oriented concepts like classes and instances thereof are desirable mechanisms for structural modelling.

Structural
modelling

Behavioural (also functional) modelling describes how input data is transformed into output data. This includes the specification of causal dependencies and real-time behaviour. At the lowest level, guard conditions and data transformations need to be described in algorithmic form. The syntax supporting this is called **action language**.²

Behavioural
modelling

When it comes to the representation of requirements, many formalisms regard them as artefacts to be elaborated *before* modelling starts. This has the disadvantage that for tracing model elements back to requirements that induced the existence of these model elements, some extra syntax has to be invented, since requirements are not part of the modelling language. Therefore, modelling formalisms like SysML [154] consider requirements as “first-class citizens” of the language, so that they can be graphically represented and related to other model elements, using the syntax of the formalism.

Requirements
modelling

²Observe that originally, UML and SysML did *not* define their own action language, since actions were originally intended to be specified in the programming language(s) used in a concrete development project. Only in 2017, the *Action Language for Foundational UML (Alf)* [153] was added in the context of presenting a formal behavioural semantics for a subset of UML.

Figure 5.2: Modelling language features of interest – structural modelling.

Figure 5.3: Modelling language features of interest – behavioural modelling.

Figure 5.4: Modeling language features of interest – support for ultra-high complexity.

Figure 5.5: Modelling language features of interest – model representations.

For safety-critical systems, it is also important to specify **probabilistic aspects** of the behaviour, because it is necessary to assess the risk involved with the execution of certain functions, to calculate system reliability and availability. Moreover, exceptional behaviour to be expected from the operational environment needs to be quantified by probabilities. Probabilistic modelling requires at least to extend the syntax of behavioural sub-models; for example, by annotating transitions with probabilities.

Probabilistic models

For security aspects of a system, specialised modelling techniques are used. An overview of the techniques for controlling ac-

Modelling security aspects

cess is given in https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Computer_security_models. **Threat models** describe how malicious agents might proceed to exploit vulnerabilities in IT systems https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Threat_model, and **attack models** describe how attackers may try to get access to encrypted data https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Attack_model. Quite often, security models are represented using arbitrary modelling formalisms. Alternatively, domain-specific languages (see definition below) may be defined to express terms, artefacts, and relationships in the context of security more concisely.

In the 1980s, graphical modelling languages were very popular (remember the diagrams of Tom deMarco's Structured Analysis), until engineers became aware that

- graphical representations do *not* guarantee error-free models, and
- graphical representations become unreadable for complex artefacts.

Therefore, UML and SysML [152, 154], and also Esterel and SCADE [48] regard graphical representations as additional views on models which, in principle, could be expressed by textual syntax alone. This fact is sometimes hidden by tools that only provide graphical editors for certain model components. It should be considered as state of the art, however, to expect alternative graphical and textual model representations in modern modelling languages. We emphasise that the XMI-format used for serialising UML/SysML models and models from similar formalisms is just for storing and exchanging models. User-friendly easy-to edit textual modelling languages are needed to allow for fast textual modelling. The graphical representations should be provided at least semi-automatically by the tools. This is the intention for example, for the new SysML v2 which is currently under construction [193, 194].

Formalisms like UML/SysML already provide some support for modelling systems of ultra-high complexity. A concept adopted from the database world and generalised for systems modelling is the creation of views showing only those aspects that are relevant for a specific group of stakeholders.

Graphical
vs.
textual
model
representations

Views and
viewpoints

Example 15. Restricting a SysML model to block properties, activity variables and data stores yields a **data view** of the model, where all behavioural aspects are hidden. A **viewpoint** is a rule set specifying how a specific view is to be created. \square

The provision of viewpoints and views is advocated in the standard ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 [117]. The SysML standard [154] emphasises that a view is not necessarily again a model represented in the same formalism as the source model: this may be the case, so that the view creation corresponds to a model transformation. Alternatively the view may consist of a collection of artefacts *outside* the modelling formalism, for example, presentation slides, videos, narrative textual representations of the model, or translations into another modelling formalism.

The standard ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 introduces the term **architecture** for the “*fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution*” [117, 3.2]. This means that both structural and behavioural properties are part of an architecture description. This interpretation of the term conforms to modern **MBSE** terminology. It is, however, slightly confusing, because the term ‘architectural design’ has often been used in software engineering to denote the *structural* model, consisting of components and interfaces only.

Architecture

The standard ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 also introduces the concept of **architecture frameworks**, as shown in Figure 5.6, as the collection of “*conventions, principles and practices for the description of architectures established within a specific domain of application and/or community of stakeholders*” [117, 3.4]. In Figure 5.6, an architecture framework is developed for a generic group of stakeholders which have certain generic concerns (this term means here ‘objectives’ or ‘requirements’) that should be fulfilled by the products modelled according to this framework. Moreover, the framework fixes the collection of architecture viewpoints. Each **model kind**, that is, each model category, which is part of this framework conforms to one of the viewpoints. The collection of **correspondence rules** defines the consistency conditions between the models built according to the views under consideration. These consistency conditions may be estab-

Architecture frameworks

lished a priori or verified a posteriori.

Figure 5.6: Architecture framework according to ISO 42010 [117, Figure 5].

Example 16. For most control system models, a **hardware sub-model** and a **software sub-model** will be useful. A correspondence between these two sub-models would be, for example, the mapping of software components to hardware components. In UML, such a correspondence would be expressed by a **deployment** [152, Chapter 19]. \square

The **action language** of a modelling formalism is the sub-language used for the specification of algorithms. The syntactic elements required are similar to those needed for programming languages, that is, Action language

1. Control structures governing the flow of execution,
2. Assignments,
3. Expressions, for example,

- arithmetic,
- Boolean,
- L-values and R-values (expressions allowed on the left or right-hand side of an assignment, respectively),

and the operators involved.

Obviously, the behavioural semantics of a model can only be understood if the semantics of the action language is clear. In UML, it has been decided not to define any action language, because actions and guard conditions in state machines and activities should be specified by the programming language used for the project. This decision – though well-motivated – presents a number of problems.

- A UML/SysML model can only be fully understood in connection with the semantics of the programming language(s) used to specify actions.
- The syntax for accessing objects and their properties in the programming language is usually not fully compatible with the naming conventions used to identify objects, parts, and their properties in UML/SysML.

The **Object Constraint Language (OCL)** [151] can be used as an OCL alternative to embedding programming code into UML models. The OCL, however, is not a “real” action language. As its name suggests, its objective is to specify *constraints* about model elements and not actions. This means that guard conditions, model invariants, and pre-/post conditions of operations can be defined with OCL in an effective way, but it is impossible to specify algorithms. The advantage of the OCL is – when compared to ordinary predicate logic – that it allows to quantify in an elegant way over collections of instances, associations, and classes. Therefore, it may be regarded as an “object-oriented predicate logic”, where model elements can be referred to by their UML identifiers³.

Complex systems often cannot be represented easily by comprehensive

Scenario
specifications

³the so-called fully qualified names

models. Therefore, scenarios are used to specify certain aspects of the required system behaviour [80] or certain aspects to be tested [100]. In their simplest form, scenarios are just use cases as introduced, for example, in UML [152]. More frequently, however, scenarios are specified more formally, so that they can be used for testing. Typical characteristics of scenario models are

- **Termination.** Scenarios describe a well-defined end-to-end activity which is triggered by certain conditions and may be considered as “completed” when certain termination conditions apply.
- **Parameterisation.** Scenarios are frequently parameterised, so that different parameter sets lead to different executions.
- **Multiple actors.** Scenarios typically specify end-to-end activities involving multiple interacting objects.

As will be described in more detail in Section 5.10, scenario modelling requires the description of situations, scenes; these concepts are usually not available in standard modelling languages.

A **product line** (or **product family**) is a collection of similar products. The term is typically used for pure software products⁴ or for HW products with a considerable amount of embedded software. The concrete products of a product line have some common features (this term denotes any structural, functional, or non-functional characteristic of the product) that can be found in each product of the line, and, additionally, some product-specific features. Alternatively or additionally, a concrete product may provide a common feature with specific characteristics. Some features are compatible with each other, others may not be installed in the same product, because this would lead to an unwanted **feature interaction**.

Product
line
specifications

Example 17. Assume that a manufacturer produces a family of tablet computers in different sizes and with varying capabilities. Typically, a web browser and an email application would be part of the tablet family’s core functionality available in each concrete product, and these apps would work

⁴In this case, we talk about software product lines (SPLs).

in the same way for every family member. A GPS sensor with location support in map applications could be a product-specific feature only available in the more expensive members of the product family. A camera, however, could be a core feature available in all family members, but with higher resolution in the pricier products.

A real-world example of an unwanted feature interaction is the interaction between family sharing and trial mode for Apple Music. If a family member buys an Apple Music subscription with the family sharing option, she or he can invite another family members to share the Apple Music feature. If the invited family member, however, just activated the cost-free trial period for Apple Music, family sharing does not work for this member.

□

As illustrated by this example, modelling formalisms for product lines need the following additional modelling features.

- Classification properties for structural and behavioural features specifying whether they are core features or product-specific features.
- Sub-model composition for various features that should be available in a specific family member.
- Rules specifying which features are compatible.
- Parameterised sub-models. The parameters specify the characteristics of a core feature (e.g. camera in the example above) in the specific family member.

5.1.3 Modelling Support for Ultra-High Complexity

Modelling Non-functional Properties

The term **non-functional property** is frequently used for any system characteristic that is neither structural nor functional; examples are

- usability,
- reliability,

Modelling
non-
functional
properties

- availability,
- maintainability, and
- safety & security.

As of today, there is no universally accepted modelling approach for non-functional properties. Their diversity also suggests that different modelling techniques will be required for different (classes of) non-functional properties. In any case, several of them require the specification of probabilities, in particular reliability, availability, maintainability, safety & security. Unfortunately, existing modelling approaches developed for describing probabilistic systems (such as **Markov models**⁵) do not provide sufficient support for structural modelling and for behavioural modelling in situations where probability does not play a role. SysML v1.6, for example, supports the specification of probabilities in activities, but not in state machines. SysML v2 is currently under development, but the definition of risk levels and of probability distributions for random variables is pre-planned.

Probabilistic
models

For autonomous systems, the capability to associate probabilities with behavioural models is very important, because many **AI**-based functions (e.g. image classification) perform correctly only with a certain probability. We expect that future behavioural models will be “interfused” with sub-components whose behaviour is associated with a reliability value less than 100%, even after the component has been comprehensively verified.

Domain-specific Languages

It is well-known that the use of **DSL** increases productivity if the application domain is sufficiently narrow and well-defined [122]: DSLs use the terms of the application domain. Thus, DSL models are easier to communicate to domain experts who are not computer science experts at the same time. Among other advantages, DSLs facilitate code generation, because the generation problem is restricted to the concepts and target platforms used in the application domain. On the down side, DSLs usually cannot

DSL
Definition
Support

⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Markov_model

be used in other domains. Consequently, suppliers producing systems for different application domains need to be familiar with different modelling languages.

In contrast to DSLs, a **wide-spectrum (modelling) language** is a modelling formalism applicable to *any* system development. This requires a certain degree of abstraction, and a mapping from abstract model elements to concrete artefacts of the application domain.

Wide-spectrum languages

Example 18. A domain-specific language for railway interlocking systems [203] uses modelling elements like track segments, points, signals, and trains. Relationships between modelling elements could be “*train resides on track segment*” or “*segment t10 is connected in direction UP to point t11, stem A*” (see Figure 5.7).

In the wide-spectrum language SysML 1.6 [154], the track element types and trains would all be represented by blocks distinguished by the type-specific block properties. A concrete track element or train would be a part, this is an instance of a block. The connection of track elements would be expressed by SysML associations that can be created between any kind of SysML model elements. □

Figure 5.7: A railway track model represented by a DSL [203, Figure 1].

To get the best of both worlds, some wide-spectrum modelling formalisms allow for language restrictions or event language extensions to create DSLs.

DSLs from wide-spectrum languages

Example 19. In UML and SysML 1.6, DSLs can be constructed by

means of the UML **profile** mechanism [152, 12.3].⁶ The profile mechanism allows for specialisation of the modelling language, but not for its extension. In Example 18, the SysML blocks representing trains and track elements could be specialised by specialising blocks with the help of stereotypes «train», «segment», «track», and specifying which properties each of these specialised blocks should have. □

A very simple variant of DSLs created from wide-spectrum languages are restrictions, where only a subset of the modelling language are allowed to be used. This kind of restriction is usually not called a DSL but **tailoring** of the modelling language. Tailoring

5.1.4 Meta Modelling

The **meta model** of a modelling formalism is a specification of all syntactically valid models and their semantics. More precisely, a comprehensive meta model should comprise (see Figure 5.8)

1. an abstract syntax specification,
2. a concrete syntax specification (grammar),
3. a specification of static semantics, and
4. a behavioural semantics⁷ specification.

Components
of a
meta model

The term ‘meta model’ has been introduced in the context of the UML. For programming languages, this term is usually not applied, because compiler developers usually do not think of programs as ‘models’.

Static semantics restricts the set of admissible models further, since for most programming languages and modelling formalisms, it is impossible to formulate all necessary restrictions by syntax rules alone. All static semantic rules can be checked without executing the program or model. Standard examples are type-related rules such as the admissible operands of Boolean

Static
semantics

⁶In fact, the SysML is just a specific profile of the UML.

⁷also called dynamic semantics

and arithmetic operators (“you cannot add a number to a string”). Model-specific rules concern the admissibility of relationships between model elements (“A SysML block cannot be a sub-class of a state machine, but a state machine can be a sub-class of a block”) or model structure (“A SysML state machine cannot have a parameter node, but an activity can”).

Figure 5.8: Modelling language features of interest – meta-model.

Adherence to the rules of static semantics ensures that a behaviour can be defined for the model, with the exception of **runtime errors**: these lead to undefined behaviour of a program or a model during execution, because an undefined execution state has been reached that could not be foreseen during the static semantic checks. Typical runtime errors occurring in executable programs are

Runtime errors

1. failure to evaluate an arithmetic expression, due to illegal operands (division by zero, real-valued root of a negative number, occurrence of overflows ...),

2. access of illegal memory addresses,
3. failure to evaluate array expressions with out-of-range index values,
4. memory leaks due to missing free-operations,
5. failure to meet a deadline, and
6. unwanted endless loops.

The runtime errors listed above can also occur in models, mostly caused by errors when using the action language. Examples for runtime errors that are specific for modelling formalisms are:

1. A UML/SysML model execution is stuck in a transient state machine state, because no outgoing transition guard evaluates to true. This is a modelling error caused by the erroneous assumption that the property valuation leading to all guards evaluating to *false* could never occur in any model execution.
2. A Timed Automata model [47] is stuck in a state because all outgoing transitions have guards evaluating to *false*, and the state invariant represented by a Boolean clock condition changes from *true* to *false*.

The behavioural semantics of programming languages and modelling formalisms is only defined for well-formed models (no violations of syntax rules or static semantics). It specifies how information is processed over time. This comprises, for example,

Behavioural
semantics

- the possible causal sequences of discrete model state changes, events, and actions (these sequences are usually called **computations**),
- the timing conditions for these causal sequences, and
- the continuous evolution of real-valued state over time.

The behavioural semantics can be specified as **operational semantics** or **denotational semantics**. The former provides a set of rules describing how the model can evolve from any pre-state to one or more possible post

Operational
semantics

states. Starting from an initial model state, all possible computations originating from this state can be constructed by applying every possible rule to every reachable state. If the program or model has a finite state space, all reachable states will finally have been visited, and all possible outgoing transitions to post states will have been attached to each state. This leads to the construction of a directed **transition graph** modelling all possible behaviours of the system. The nodes represent system states, and the arrows specify which transitions between states are possible. Systems with unbounded state space are represented by infinite directed graphs with the initial model state as initial node. The (finite or infinite) graphs represent **transition systems**. If their arrows are further decorated with events and actions, they are called **labelled transition systems**. Time-continuous behaviour is usually encoded in the nodes of a transition graph.

Transition
systems

The **denotational semantics** maps a well-formed model to the set of all computations and time-continuous evolutions it is capable of.

Denotational
semantics

A **transformational semantics** assigns behavioural semantics to a model M by transforming it into another model or computer program $\Phi(M)$ whose syntax is already associated with an operational or denotational semantics. The computations of M are defined to be the ones of $\Phi(M)$.

Transformational
semantics

In a behavioural semantics, the concept of simultaneity may be expressed in different ways. In an **interleaving semantics**, only one event may happen at a time, and simultaneity of two events e_1, e_2 is expressed by the fact that both causal orderings $e_1 \longrightarrow e_2$ and $e_2 \longrightarrow e_1$ occur in the model's computations. In a **true parallelism semantics**, computations elements may be represented by *sets of events* which all happen simultaneously, without any causal ordering between them.

5.1.5 Model Representations

Textual representations of mixed graphical/textual models (such as UML or SysML, Simulink/Stateflow) are called **(model) serialisations**, because they provide a textual “left-to-right” definition of the model elements and the connections in between. Some tool providers for graphical

modelling languages (e.g. MathWorks⁸) use proprietary textual formats. For UML and SysML, the **OMG** has applied the **XML Metadata Interchange (XMI)**⁹ format as an **XML**-based standard format for model serialisation. A main standardisation objective was to allow for the exchange of models between tools from different vendors. This, however, never worked properly, since no vendor supported the **XMI** syntax exactly as specified by the **OMG**, and most vendors represented crucial model features in vendor-specific sections of the **XMI** file, using proprietary encodings.

This situation is very unfortunate, since the **XMI** syntax has been used by the **OMG** to provide fully specified meta models of UML and SysML 1.x as so-called **normative machine readable documents**.¹⁰ This would allow for the automated generation of model parsers, if the vendors strictly adhered to this format.

For the new SysML v2, another strategy has been applied. The modelling language is defined with both a graphical and a textual syntax, the latter in the style of a high-level programming language. An open source reference parser is provided, using the Xtext¹¹ **DSL**. Therefore, **XMI** is no longer relevant for SysML v2.

5.2 The Impact of Quality Standards on Modelling Formalisms

One major motivation for using modelling formalisms is to help ensuring the quality of the system to be developed. Hence it is necessary to review quality-related standards and ensure that the applicable quality characteristics can be expressed by the modelling formalisms used to specify a system. In quality standards like ISO/IEC 25010:2011 [115], a multitude of quality characteristics have been identified.

A general distinction of quality characteristics is

⁸<https://www.mathworks.com>

⁹<https://www.omg.org/spec/XMI/2.5.1/About-XMI>

¹⁰See, for example, <https://www.omg.org/spec/SysML/20181001/SysML.xmi> for the SysML 1.6 meta model specified in XMI.

¹¹<https://eclipse.dev/Xtext/>

Quality in use. This term subsumes quality characteristics related to the system when used in its operational environment. The applicable characteristics are depicted in Figure 5.9. Observe that the safety-related quality characteristic is regarded as an aspect of **freedom from risk**. Quality in use is checked by validation measures.¹² Quality in use

Product quality. This term subsumes quality characteristics related to the system under development, as shown in Figure 5.10. Product quality is checked by means of verification and validation measures. Product quality

In Figure 5.11, the quality life cycle is displayed.

Figure 5.9: Quality in use – structured according to ISO/IEC 25010:2011 [115, Figure 3].

¹²Recall that **effectiveness** is defined as the “*accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals*” [115, 4.1.1].

Figure 5.10: Product quality – structured according to ISO/IEC 25010:2011 [115, Figure 4].

Figure 5.11: Quality life cycle model according to ISO/IEC 25010:2011 [115, Figure C.5].

Table 5.1 associates quality characteristics with modelling techniques needed to express these characteristics. The table indicates that the basic modelling features listed in Section 5.1 suffice to specify most of the quality-related aspects of a system to be developed. Exceptions are

Modelling
quality
characteristics

- the “soft” quality criteria like satisfaction and usability, that cannot be captured in a completely formal way, and
- probabilistic models, as needed, for example, to express the risks associated with certain behaviours. These stochastic aspects are discussed in Section 5.3.

Table 5.1: Quality characteristics associated with suitable modelling techniques

Q-Characteristic	Modelling Feature
Effectiveness	Requirements tracing, behavioural modelling
Efficiency	Behavioural and structural modelling
Satisfaction	Checklists, questionnaires
Freedom from risk	Probabilistic models, risk structures and Risk graphs
Context coverage	Requirements tracing, structural modelling
Functional suitability	Behavioural and structural modelling
Performance efficiency	Probabilistic models, Behavioural modelling
Compatibility	Behavioural and structural modelling
Usability	Usability evaluation at design time [8], usability evaluation at runtime [11]
Reliability	Probabilistic models, behavioural and structural modelling
Security	Probabilistic models, behavioural and structural modelling, security-specific modelling techniques
Maintainability	Behavioural and structural modelling
Portability	Behavioural and structural modelling

5.3 Modelling Stochastic Behaviour: Markov Chains

5.3.1 The Need for Stochastic Models

Ultra complex systems require stochastic modelling views for several reasons.

Stochastic models are necessary

- The system's world model, encompassing its operational environment, is inherently stochastic because:
 - The environmental behavior — including human actions, natural events, and aging-related hardware changes — is inherently nondeterministic.
 - The occurrence of unknown operational scenarios has to be taken into account, because sometimes not all relevant operational scenarios were covered during the specification phase.
- The behaviour of certain system components, such as trained neural networks, or collaborative agents can only be predicted with a certain probability.
- Safety and security, as well as system availability and reliability are stochastic entities. The risks of safety or security violations and of system degradations affecting availability and reliability are stochastic quantities as well.

5.3.2 Discrete Time Markov Chains

The most frequently used formalism to model and evaluate stochastic behaviours is Markov Chain (**MC**), with its distinction between Discrete Time Markov Chain (**DTMC**) and **CTMC** [37, Chapter 7]. An alternative formalism is given by Stochastic Timed Automata [37, Chapter 6]. In this report, we only discuss **DTMC** and **CTMC**.

Markov chains

In principle, **MC** are finite state machines where each state can be reached from any other state, but only with a certain probability depending on the source state. More formally, the state space of a **MC** is a (multi

dimensional) random variable $X(t)$ changing over time t . The conditional probability

$$P[X(t_{i+1}) = x' \mid X(t_i) = x] \quad (5.1)$$

to transit from a state valuation x that is valid at time t_i to another valuation x' at time t_{i+1} is called the **transition probability** of the **MC**. The valuation x_0 of the initial state $X(0)$ is also not specified deterministically, but by a probability $p_0(x) = P[X(0) = x]$.

For **DTMC**, time proceeds in discrete steps $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, and the state space is assumed to be countable. Therefore, we can identify the reachable state values by integers $0, 1, 2, \dots$, use indexed random variables X_i to identify the state at time $t = i$, and re-write Equation (5.1) as

$$p_{ij}(k) = P[X_{k+1} = j \mid X_k = i] \text{ with } p_{ij}(k) \in [0, 1] \text{ and } \sum_j p_{ij}(k) = 1 \quad (5.2)$$

for all i, j, k , because for all i and k , the values $p_{ij}(k)$ denote the weights of a discrete probability distribution.

DTMC are **memoryless**. Intuitively speaking, this means that the probability $p_{ij}(k)$ to reach state valuation $X_{k+1} = j$, provided that the pre-state satisfies $X_k = i$, does not depend on the path that had been taken from the initial state to reach $X_k = i$. This is expressed more formally using conditional probabilities as

$$P[X_{k+1} = x_{k+1} \mid X_k = x_k, X_{k-1} = x_{k-1}, \dots, X_0 = x_0] = P[X_{k+1} = x_{k+1} \mid X_k = x_k] \quad (5.3)$$

for all k and all valuations x_i . This allows us to use simplifying equations for the n -step probability

$$p_{ij}(k, k+n) = P[X_{k+n} = j \mid X_k = i]$$

to reach state valuation j in n steps, starting from state valuation i : the **Chapman-Kolmogorov equation** states that

$$p_{ij}(k, k+n) = \sum_r p_{ir}(k, u) \cdot p_{rj}(u, k+n) \quad (5.4)$$

holds for all $k < u \leq k+n$.

If the weights $p_{ij}(k)$ defined in Equation (5.2) are time-independent, that is, constant in k , the DTMC is called **homogeneous**. Then the time-independent matrix

$$P = [p_{ij}]_{i,j=0,1,2,\dots} \quad (5.5)$$

lists the discrete transition probability weights for each state valuation i in matrix row i . Therefore, P is called the **transition probability matrix** of the DTMC.

In homogeneous DTMC, the **state holding time** $V(i)$, that is, the number of time steps to remain in some state i , follows the geometric distribution:

$$P[V(i) = n] = (1 - p_{ii}) \cdot (p_{ii})^{n-1}. \quad (5.6)$$

The intuition behind this formula is as follows: (1) after having reached state i , the probability to stay there for another $(n - 1)$ discrete time steps is p_{ii}^{n-1} , since the DTMC is memoryless. (2) After these $(n - 1)$ steps, we must leave this state, since otherwise $V(i) > n$. The probability to leave state i is always $(1 - p_{ii})$. Both (1) and (2) only hold for homogeneous DTMC.

Setting $\pi_j(k) = P[X_k = j]$, the **state probability vector**

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}(k) = [\pi_0(k), \pi_1(k), \pi_2(k), \dots]$$

specifies all probabilities to be some state $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ at discrete time step k . In particular, $\boldsymbol{\pi}(0)$ specifies the distribution of the initial state. Using induction, it can easily be shown for homogeneous DTMC that the state probabilities for the k^{th} time steps are given by

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}(k) = \boldsymbol{\pi}(0)P^k \text{ for } k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (5.7)$$

This equation solves the **transient analysis** problem whose objective is to answer the question “*What is the probability for the system to be in state i after k discrete time steps?*”.

5.3.3 Continuous Time Markov Chains

For continuous time $t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, the discrete-time property (5.3) stating that CTMC

MC are memoryless is now expressed for arbitrary points in time t_k , that is,

$$\begin{aligned} P[X(t_{k+1}) = x_{k+1} \mid X(t_k) = x_k, X(t_{k-1}) = x_{k-1}, \dots, X(t_0) = x_0] = \\ P[X(t_{k+1}) = x_{k+1} \mid X(t_k) = x_k] \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

Since transitions happen no longer at discrete time steps of constant width, the transition probability matrix P , as introduced for **DTMC**, can no longer be used, and an alternative **CTMC** model representation must be found. To this end, a time continuous transition function is defined by

$$p_{ij}(s, t) = P[X(t) = j \mid X(s) = i] \text{ for } s \leq t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}. \quad (5.9)$$

It expresses the probability that the system will be in state j at point in time t , provided that it has been in state i at a previous point in time s . A continuous-time version of the Chapman-Kolmogorov equation (5.4) can be derived as

$$p_{ij}(s, t) = \sum_r p_{ir}(s, u) \cdot p_{rj}(u, t), \text{ where } s \leq u \leq t. \quad (5.10)$$

Generalising the concept of homogeneous **DTMC**, a **CTMC** is called **homogeneous** if all transition functions $p_{ij}(s, t)$ depend only on the time *difference* ($t - s$), but not on the individual values of s and t . Then Equation (5.9) is simplified to

$$p_{ij}(\tau) = P[X(s+\tau) = j \mid X(s) = i] \text{ for an arbitrary choice of } s \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}. \quad (5.11)$$

The transition matrix

$$P(\tau) = [p_{ij}(\tau)]_{i,j=0,1,2,\dots} \quad (5.12)$$

generalises the transition probability matrix defined for **DTMC** in Equation (5.5). By means of the Chapman-Kolmogorov equation (5.10), the matrix differential equation

$$\frac{dP(\tau)}{d\tau} = P(\tau)Q \quad (5.13)$$

Homogeneous
CTMC

Transition
matrix

with a constant transition rate matrix Q can be derived. It has the initial condition

$$p_{ij}(0) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j, \end{cases}$$

because it is reasonable to assume that a state transition $i \rightarrow j \neq i$ cannot occur in zero time at $\tau = 0$. Using the unit matrix I , this initial condition can also be expressed as

$$P(0) = I.$$

The differential equation (5.13) has the solution

$$P(\tau) = e^{Q\tau}, \text{ where } e^{Q\tau} = I + Q\tau + Q^2\tau^2/2! + Q^3\tau^3/3! + \dots \quad (5.14)$$

is the exponential function applied to matrix arguments $Q\tau$, which is defined using the Taylor series expansion of e^x around zero.

For CTMC, the amount of time $V(i)$ spent in some state i that has just been entered has exponential distribution

$$P[V(i) \leq t] = 1 - e^{-\Lambda(i)t} \text{ for } t \geq 0. \quad (5.15)$$

CTMC
state
holding
time

The term $\Lambda(i)$ can be calculated as $\Lambda(i) = -q_{ii}$, where q_{ii} is the i^{th} diagonal element of the transition rate matrix Q . Intuitively speaking, $-q_{ii}$ is the instantaneous rate at which a state transition out of state i takes place. Therefore, the higher the value of $\Lambda(i) = -q_{ii}$, the higher is the likelihood to leave state i instantaneously. For a fixed value of t , the value of $1 - e^{-\Lambda(i)t}$ increases with the size of $\Lambda(i)$ towards one. Consequently, the probability $P[V(i) \leq t]$ for the state holding time $V(i)$ to be less or equal to t increases with $\Lambda(i)$.

In analogy to $-q_{ii}$ indicating the rate for instantaneous transitions away from state i , the (nonnegative) values q_{ij} , $i \neq j$, indicate the rates for instantaneous transitions from i to j , so that

$$q_{ii} + \sum_{j \neq i} q_{ij} = 0 \text{ holds for all states } i.$$

These insights motivate the name 'transition rate matrix' for Q .

The transition probability P_{ij} to transit from state i to state $j \neq i$,

Transition
probability

provided that a transition $i \rightarrow j \neq i$ happens at a given point in time, can also be expressed by means of transition rate matrix elements:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{q_{ij}}{-q_{ii}} \text{ for } i \neq j.$$

Note that the meaning of P_{ij} differs from that of $p_{ij}(\tau)$ defined in Equation (5.11): the former specifies the probability to reach j directly from i when a transition from i occurs, the latter specifies the probability to be in state j after a time interval of length τ has passed, and the system had been in i at the beginning of this interval.

Recall the state probability vector introduced for DTMC and its Equation (5.7) for calculating the probabilities to be in a certain state after k discrete time steps. This is generalised for CTMC by setting

State probabilities

$$\pi_j(t) = P[X(t) = j]$$

for the probability to be in state j at continuous time point t , and set the continuous time state probability vector to

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}(t) = [\pi_0(t), \pi_1(t), \dots]. \quad (5.16)$$

Given an initial state probability vector

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}(0) = [\pi_0(0), \pi_1(0), \dots],$$

the state probability vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}(t)$ is completely determined by the transition matrix $P(\tau) = [p_{ij}(\tau)]_{i,j}$ introduced in Equation (5.12), as follows directly from Equation (5.11) by setting $s = 0$. This equation implies that

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}(\tau) = \left[\sum_i p_{i1}(\tau) \cdot \pi_i(0), \sum_i p_{i2}(\tau) \cdot \pi_i(0), \sum_i p_{i3}(\tau) \cdot \pi_i(0), \dots \right] = \boldsymbol{\pi}(0)P(\tau).$$

From Equation (5.14) we know that $P(\tau)$ is completely determined by the transition rate matrix, so that

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}(t) = \boldsymbol{\pi}(0)e^{Q_t}. \quad (5.17)$$

This implies the validity of the differential equation

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\pi}(t)}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\pi}(t)Q. \quad (5.18)$$

Since Q is constant for homogeneous CTMC, it induces a suitable graphical representation with nodes representing states i, j, \dots and directed arcs $i \rightarrow j$ labelled by the transition rates q_{ij} , as sketched in Figure 5.12. In contrast to finite state machine models, this resulting time-independent graph does not directly model behaviour, but all (stochastic) behaviours can be derived from this graph, using Equation (5.17) or Equation (5.18).

Figure 5.12: Graph visualisation of transition rate matrix Q and associated CTMC states.

In this graph representation, a node j has incoming arrows from all other nodes i possessing a non-zero rate for a transition to j . The “probability flow” into node j is calculated by inspecting all incoming arrows and building the sum

$$\text{total flow into } j \text{ at time } t = \sum_{i \neq j} q_{ij} \pi_i(t).$$

The total outgoing flow for state j is

$$\text{total flow out of } j \text{ at time } t = \sum_{k \neq j} q_{jk} \pi_j(t).$$

In **steady state analysis**, questions about the convergence of the system to certain states for $t \rightarrow \infty$ are investigated. This means that we are looking for solutions of

Steady
state
analysis

$$\pi_j = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \pi_j(t) \quad \text{for a given state } j.$$

If such a boundary value π_j exists, it is called the **steady state probability** of j . If π_j exists for all j ,

$$\boldsymbol{\pi} = [\pi_0, \pi_1, \dots]$$

is called the **stationary state probability vector** of the **CTMC**. In this case, the derivative

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\pi}(t)}{dt}$$

must converge to zero for $t \rightarrow \infty$, since $\boldsymbol{\pi}(t)$ finally becomes stationary. Therefore, the differential equation (5.18) is reduced to

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}Q = 0 \tag{5.19}$$

for the stationary state probability vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}$.

For **finite CTMC** (these are homogeneous **CTMC** with finitely many states), uniquely defined stationary state probability vectors $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ exist for every initial state probability vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}(0)$. Vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ is calculated by solving the two equations

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}Q = 0 \tag{5.20}$$

$$\sum_j \pi_j = 1. \tag{5.21}$$

5.3.4 Modelling Syntax and Tool Support

As of today, there is no standardised syntax for modelling Markov chains. In particular, common modelling formalisms like UML, SysML, Z, VDM, and process algebras sometimes provide some very basic support for modelling probabilistic behaviour, but none of them has comprehensive support for modelling Markov chains.

The stochastic model checking tool PRISM¹³, however, defines a tool-specific textual syntax for describing Markov models and models designed using related formalisms (Markov decision processes, probabilistic (timed) automata) [132].

Figure 5.13: Sequence chart for the CTMC model described in PRISM syntax in Figure 5.14.

¹³<https://www.prismmodelchecker.org>

Example 20. The sequence chart in Figure 5.13 shows a dual channel system using a voter to ensure fail-safe behaviour. The design of this system is discussed by Peleska et al. [162] and Gleirscher et al. [77].

In Figure 5.14, a part of the associated CTMC model specified in PRISM syntax is shown. PRISM commands are of the form

$$[a]g \rightarrow (\lambda_1: u_{i1} \& u_{i2} \dots) + \dots + (\lambda_n: u_{n1} \& u_{n2} \dots)$$

with an action a , a guard g , and probabilistic multiple-assignments u_{i1}, u_{i2}, \dots applied with rate λ_i . The action $[\text{Perceive}_n^o]$ in line 4, for example, applies when variable s_n has value 2 and variable sen_c has value 1. In this case, the variables per_n and s_n will have post states 1 and 3, respectively, and this assignment happens with a transition rate of $(1 - p_{\neq}^n)\lambda_{pn}$. This is the normal-behaviour case of action $[\text{Perceive}_n^o]$. Alternatively, the post states of per_n and s_n will be 0 and 3, respectively, and this faulty assignment will occur with a transition rate of $p_{\neq}^n\lambda_{pn}$. \square

```

1 module Channeln ... // NN-channel, same structure as conv. ch.
2 [Generate] sn = 0 → (sn'=0);
3 [Sensen] ... // faulty sensor (CS, SSsh) & degrad. check (SSdi)
4 [Perceiveno] sn = 2 ∧ senc = 1
5   → (1 - pfn)λpn:(pern'=1)&(sn'=3) // correct
6   + pfnλpn:(pern'=0)&(sn'=3) // faulty perc. (CP, Psn|Psc, SPr)
7   ...
8 [Communicaten] ... // faulty communication (CC, SC)
9 [Vote] sn=4 → (sn'=5); // synchronise with voter
10 endmodule
11 module Voter
12 r : [0..2] init 0; // voting result
13 f : bool init false; // failure flag
14 [Vote] sc=sn ∧ sc=4 // synchronise on voting stage
15   ∧ (comc = 2 ∨ comn = 2 ∨ comc ≠ comn) // contradict. ch. (UC)
16   → (1 - pfv)λv:(f'=true)&(r'=maxi∈{c,n}{comi}) // forward safe
   result r & raise flag f
17   +  $\frac{p_f^v}{3}$ λv:(f'=false)&(r'=0) // fail on demand (unsafe) ...
18   +  $\frac{p_f^v}{3}$ λv:(f'=false)&(r'=1); // ... with 3 failure modes (Vr1)
19   +  $\frac{p_f^v}{3}$ λv:(f'=false)&(r'=2);
20 [Vote] sc=sn ∧ sc=4
21   ∧ (comc = 1 ∨ comc=comn) // simultaneous fault (S)
22   → (1 - pfv)λv:(f'=false)&(r'=comc) // forward result r, e.g.
   obstacle present
23   +  $\frac{p_f^v}{3}$ λv:(f'=true); // fail spuriously (safe)
24   +  $\frac{p_f^v}{3}$ λv:(f'=false)&(r'=0); // fail spuriously (unsafe)
25   +  $\frac{p_f^v}{3}$ λv:(f'=false)&(r'=2); // ... with 2 failure modes (Vr2)
26   ... // safe fraction of voting fault
27 endmodule

```

Figure 5.14: CTMC model described in PRISM syntax, adopted from Gleirscher et al. [77].

5.3.5 Markov Decision Processes

While Markov Chains are well-suited for modelling stochastic systems where transitions between states are governed solely by probability, they fall short when the system includes decision points – i.e. situations where

an agent or controller must choose between alternative actions. To address this limitation, **Markov Decision Process (MDP)** [37] extend the **MC** formalism by incorporating actions and decision-making under uncertainty.

An MDP is formally defined by a tuple (S, A, P, R) , where:

- S is a finite set of states,
- A is a finite set of actions,
- $P(s' | s, a)$ gives the probability of transitioning from state s to state s' after taking action a ,
- $R(s, a)$ defines the expected reward¹⁴ received after executing action a in state s .

Unlike **MCs**, where transitions are fully probabilistic and passive, **MDPs** introduce a choice: at each state, an agent selects an action from the available set, which then determines the transition probabilities to successor states. This makes MDPs highly suitable for **planning and control in autonomous systems**, where the goal is not just to analyse behaviour, but to **optimise it according to some criterion**, such as maximising long-term expected reward or minimising risk.

MDPs support both *finite-horizon* and *infinite-horizon* objectives and allow for the synthesis of *policies* – functions mapping states to actions – that optimise the expected outcome. When time and rewards are discounted (e.g. using a discount factor $\gamma < 1$), the framework allows for tractable analysis even in long-run scenarios.

From a modelling perspective, MDPs generalise Discrete Time Markov Chains: if each state has only one available action, an **MDP** reduces to a **DTMC**. Similarly, Continuous-Time **MDPs** extend Continuous Time Markov Chains **CTMCs** by associating decisions with rates and transitions.

In the context of ultra complex systems, **MDPs** are instrumental for **design-time planning and run-time adaptation**, especially when uncertainties must be actively managed rather than merely analysed. From

¹⁴Alternatively, the reward R can be replaced by a cost function.

the perspective of autonomous safety-critical vehicles, one of the most important applications of **MDPs** is to **enforce the selection of trajectories through the world model that maintain risk within acceptable bounds** whenever autonomous decisions are required. Model checking tools like **PRISM** support **MDP** modelling and enable verification of both qualitative and quantitative properties, such as the probability of satisfying safety constraints under optimal policies.

5.4 Modelling Multi Agent Systems

5.4.1 Agent Characteristics

As suggested by Bordini et al. [32], agents – whether implemented by software or represented by humans or robots – have the following characteristics.

1. **Autonomy.** The ability to build objectives and to select and perform actions to achieve these objectives.
2. **Proactivity.** The ability to exhibit goal-oriented behaviour, to achieve the previously defined objectives.
3. **Reactivity.** The ability to offer immediate responses resulting from the perception of the environment.
4. **Social ability.** The ability to interact and exchange knowledge with other agents, for the purpose of cooperation, coordination, and negotiation.

Agent
characteristics

Obviously, communicating control systems also exhibit reactivity and social abilities (usually simply called communication mechanisms in the field of control systems). The crucial difference consists in the fact that conventional control systems have *completely preprogrammed* behaviours, while agents can adapt their objectives to be pursued during runtime, based on the acquisition of knowledge obtained from the environment and from other agents. Agents can even learn new actions at runtime, to be performed to reach these objectives.

Collaborating autonomous systems are best represented as **MAS**, where each autonomous entity – including humans – in the collaboration is represented by an agent. Of particular interest are **BDI agents** operating on their current **belief state** about the environment and its own internal attributes. An agent's actions are stimulated by its **desire**, that is, by the goals it wants (or is programmed) to achieve. To this end, BDI agents use **plans** to achieve intermediate goals called **intentions**, leading to actions that are expected to finally result in the fulfilment of (a subset of)

BDI
agents

the *desired* objectives. Plan execution and updates of the belief state by means of actions can be coordinated between agents by exchanging events. Plans may also be exchanged between agents, and they may even be synthesised at runtime by collaborating agents [32, 186]. The **MAPE** paradigm introduced in Section 4.1 can be completely realised with **BDI** agents.

5.4.2 Challenges

The use of **BDI** agents induces new challenges on modelling and semantic expressiveness of formalisms.

Challenges
for BDI
modelling

1. Configurations of collaborating agents are usually not static; they change (sometimes rather quickly) over time.
2. Communication links between agents are dynamically created and destroyed, along with these configuration changes.
3. Spatial relationships between agents and between agents and elements in their operational environment are important to observe; again these relationships change over time.
4. Plans to be executed by some agents may be sent from other agents. Therefore, just the analysis of the agent source code (or model) does not allow to predict an agent's behaviour completely.
5. Plans may be synthesised at runtime, and by several collaborating agents. Again, this prevents a complete understanding of agent behaviour from its source code.
6. Agent behaviour is usually not completely deterministic [85], even if all currently relevant plans are known at a certain point in time: the selection of the next plan to be executed may be nondeterministic, and the content of *future* plans to be executed is sometimes not determined, since these plans are still unknown. Moreover, the set of desires and intentions may change during runtime. Finally, the effects

of the environment on the intended plan execution of an agent are often unpredictable.¹⁵

Since MAS induce new programming and modelling paradigms, the terms **agent-oriented programming (Agent-Oriented Programming (AOP))** [186] and **agent-based modelling** [189], as well as **Agent-Oriented Software Engineering (AOSE)** [81] have been coined.

5.4.3 Semantic Models for Single Agent Behaviour

Archibald et al. [17] advocate to express the behavioural semantics of single agent programs by means of two transition systems describing

1. the agent-level evolution and
2. the intention-level evolution.

Agent state. The execution state of an agent is abstracted by means of a triple $\langle E, \mathcal{B}, \Gamma \rangle$, where

- E is the set of pending external events, still to be processed. These events have been sent by other agents, or they have been generated by the agent's sensor/perceptor modules, representing occurrences in the operational environment.
- \mathcal{B} is the agent's current state of belief base: this is the collection of all facts held to be true by the agent.
- Γ is the set of partially executed plan bodies (more than one plan may be executed concurrently by an agent).

Agent-level evolution. The rules of this transition system describe how the agent changes its execution state with respect to events, plans, and actions.

¹⁵For example, the intention of a robot to open a door may fail due to the door handle being too slippery for the robot's hand.

- Events $e \in E$ can be (nondeterministically) selected to trigger a new plan execution. This agent-level transition removes e from E and adds the plan body associated with e to Γ . Several plans can be executed concurrently in interleaving mode, if the events triggering these plans existed in E .
- A terminated plan execution body is removed from Γ .
- If an action of a plan execution is can be performed according to the intention-level transition rules, the applicable intention-level rules specify the associated changes in the belief state, and the plan execution is updated to the “rest of the plan” that is still to be performed after having performed the action.

Intention-level evolution. The rules for this transition system specify how single active plan executions proceed.

- If an action is enabled according to the current belief state \mathcal{B} , it is executed, and the updates of the belief state associated with the action change \mathcal{B} to a new state \mathcal{B}' , where old beliefs may have been removed and new ones may have been added.
- The actions of concurrent plan executions P_1, P_2 are performed in interleaving mode: If both P_1 and P_2 can proceed with actions α_1 and α_2 , respectively, the choice of α_1 or α_2 is nondeterministic, and the other action can be performed after the first one has been completed.
- If a plan succeeds, it terminates.
- If a plan execution fails and there exists a backup plan, then the backup plan is triggered.

Comparison with operational program semantics. Studying the evolution rules shows that this agent program semantics can be compared to the operational semantics of (concurrent) programs with variables, as described, for example by Apt et al. [10]:

- The variable state of a concurrent program becomes the belief state \mathcal{B} of the agent program.
- The operational rules for changing the program state and updating the variable valuations becomes the action execution rules for the agent program, with associated updates of the belief state, as defined by the intention-level evolution.
- The message passing rules for a concurrent program become the event processing rules of the agent-level evolution.
- The rules for exception handling in a concurrent program become the rules for handling failed plans, as defined by the intention-level evolution.

Probabilistic interpretations. Unlike conventional concurrent program semantics [10], Archibald et al. [17] extend the agent semantics sketched above to **probabilistic behaviour** by allowing for probabilistic selection of originally nondeterministic choices. The possible agent behaviours are then interpreted as a Markov chain, as described in Section 5.3.

5.4.4 Modelling Agent Configurations With UML

Due to its wide-spread application and its possibility to create domain-specific language specialisations, many authors have used the Unified Modelling Language (**UML**) as the basis for designing a modelling language for **MAS** [81]. In principle, UML and SysML offer several language features facilitating **MAS** modelling. This is described in Table 5.2, where desired modelling features for **MAS** are associated with UML/SysML language features. Different authors have proposed slightly differing associations; the ones listed in Table 5.2, however, are the most effective ones, according to our understanding.

Table 5.2: Desirable features for MAS modelling and associated language features of UML.

MAS Modelling Feature	Modelled by UML Language Feature
Interfaces of an agent	Ports
Belief state of an agent	List of UML properties
Single actions	UML activities and state machines
Plan	List of actions
Current goals (intentions)	List of plans
A BDI agent	Instance of stereotyped agent class derived from UML meta class Class, with specific properties like belief state, list of available plans, available actions, current plan execution state represented according to Section 5.4.3.
Spatial relationships agent-agent and agent-environment	Stereotyped associations with attributes describing spatial values (e.g. distance). Deployment diagrams showing containment relationships between agents and environment.
Communication links agent-agent and agent-environment	Stereotyped associations linking agent ports
Configuration snapshot of cooperating agents and their environments	UML instance specification (formerly object diagram) with instances and their slots containing concrete feature values specified by means of value specifications
Evolving configurations over time	Sequences of instance specifications – this is not semantically well-defined!

There is, however, no language mechanism to specify rules for generating admissible sequences of instance specifications. The only available rule in UML is the invariant that every instance specification must be consistent with its applicable class diagrams. This is insufficient in most safety-critical MAS applications, since it has to be shown that the MAS respects certain safety condition in *all* possible states the system might evolve to.

5.4.5 Modelling Agent Configurations With SysML v2

Dynamic change of agent configurations (change of spatial relationships and communication links) – Occurrences, time slices, and Snapshots in SysML v2

5.4.6 Alternative Modelling Approaches

The behaviour of concurrent systems whose participants create and destroy communication links dynamically is semantically represented best by the π calculus [141]. Unfortunately, this calculus is quite complex, so that its chances to be adopted by practitioners in industry are low. Also, the π -calculus does not provide means to verify systems in presence of dynamic plan creation and dynamic exchange of plans.

Semantic
agent-
based
modelling

In absence of changing communication links and dynamically changing plans, MAS consisting of BDI agents can be modelled as networks of communicating hybrid automata [87], as pointed out by Dennis et al. [54]. The authors suggest a strict separation of time-continuous behaviours and discrete decisions, in order to reduce the overall model complexity. Dennis et al. [54] also propose an extension of Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) to specify properties that the agent-based code or model should fulfil. However, they don't propose a solution for modelling dynamic changes of communication channels and dynamic plan elaboration.

According to our own assessment, it will become too complex, or even be semantically infeasible, to extend hybrid automata with respect to these dynamic aspects. Instead, we support the approach of Heiker et al. [85] who suggest to overapproximate all possible behaviours of (BDI-) agents in a MAS by means of Markovian agent networks, each agent acting according to the CTMC paradigm, as explained in Section 5.3.3. Since BDI agents are intrinsically nondeterministic anyway, it seems reasonable to abandon the idea of associating agent-oriented programs with a conventional (operational or denotational) program semantics. As an alternative, the CTMC approximation specifies a superset of the behaviours to expect. The Markov approach allows to quantify the residual risk for the MAS to

Markov
model
abstractions
of MAS

reach an unsafe or otherwise undesired state (Section 5.3). As tool support, probabilistic model checkers like PRISM are available [132]. These also provide textual syntax for writing Markov models.

Heiker et al. [85] also explain how the mutual impact of cooperating BDI agents in a MAS can be modelled by modification of transition rate matrices of the individual agents. The authors, however, do not present a detailed set of construction rules explaining how the CTMC abstraction is to be constructed from given BDI agent code or design.

There have been many attempts to model (and visualise) MAS with specific profiles of UML/SysML [81]. According to our analysis, however, these approaches are insufficient, since

Agent-based design models

- UML is not well-suited to provide graphical models for dynamically changing communication links, topological relations (“Agent A is currently located in Component C”), and dynamically changing behaviours (“Execute Plan P, which has just been received via Interface I”).
- At best, these UML/SysML profiles come with a static semantics, but nobody succeeded so far in formalising the behavioural semantics of MAS, using such profiles.

5.4.7 Probabilistic Bigraphs

To the best of our knowledge, the only modelling approach that both provides powerful graphical means and behavioural semantics to MAS consisting of communicating BDI agents is based on Milner’s bigraphs [142]. A bigraph represents a MAS configuration, and the system behaviour is described by a reaction relation between configurations. The reaction relation can be associated with a stochastic interpretation, yielding a MDP interpretation of the dynamic MAS behaviour. This interpretation has recently been proposed by Archibald et al. [16, 17], together with a formal semantic definition and systematic construction rules for creating MDPs from bigraphs and associated reaction relations.

Milner’s first fundamental insight into MAS modelling was that two

Bigraphs

views are needed to describe a snapshot (or a configuration) of collaborating agents.

- A *topological (i.e. spatial) view* is needed to describe the containment hierarchy of **MAS** components, including their environment. In the bigraph formalism, this view is realised by the **place graph**.
- A *non-spatial relationship view* describing, for example, communication links. This view is realised by the **link hypergraph**. Each system entity in a configuration has a fixed number of links, but they may be **closed** if unused in a certain configuration.

Milner's second insight was to describe behaviour by means of rules for configuration changes, this is called the **reaction relation**. This required a formal capture of the *admissible* configuration changes which was solved by Milner in a fairly intuitive graphical way that can also be captured by algebraic composition rules. Graphical and algebraic representations are equivalent.

5.5 Agent-based Test Environment Modelling

advocated in [12, 13, 14]

5.6 The SAE Architecture Analysis & Design Language AADL

AADL [60]

5.7 RoboChart and RoboSim

The RoboStar research project referenced in Chapter 1 has elaborated two modelling formalisms intended for modelling and simulating autonomous robotic systems.

Two
complementary
modelling
formalisms

- **RoboChart** is the formalism for **platform-independent** modelling (Platform Independent Model (**PIM**)) of behaviour and structure.
- **RoboSim** is the formalism for modelling **platform-specific** (Platform Specific Model (**PSM**)) control software.

Together, these two formalisms conform to the proven approach of model-based systems engineering, where the platform-independent application logic are represented in PIMs and the platform-dependent aspects are specified in PSMs.

5.7.1 RoboChart

RoboChart [143, 144]¹⁶ has been developed recently with the explicit objective to provide a domain-specific modelling language optimised for describing and verifying robotics applications. Since robots are particular instances of autonomous systems in many cases, it is worthwhile to analyse the unique selling points of RoboChart and their applicability to partially autonomous ultra-complex transportation systems. Indeed, it turns out that RoboChart is quite well-suited to model any kind of distributed reactive system.

RoboChart has been inspired by UML/SysML, but, for good reasons, it is far more restricted than the latter. These restrictions allow to define a comprehensive behavioural semantics which in turn enables efficient code generation for model simulations, as well as formal verification by model checking and automated theorem proving.

Example 21. In UML, StateMachines are introduced by sub-classing Behaviour in the UML meta model. Behaviour in turn is a sub-class of Class (which corresponds to Block in SysML). As a consequence, a concrete StateMachine which models the classifier behaviour of a concrete class or block is itself a class, so it is possible to define further properties and operations on the StateMachine level. This leads to considerable complications when creating code generators for UML/SysML models.

¹⁶The reference manual is available under <https://robostar.cs.york.ac.uk/publications/techreports/reports/robochart-reference.pdf>.

In contrast to this, RoboChart allows to define operations only on the level of platforms and interfaces, which facilitates code generation in a considerable way. \square

The syntax and parts of the static semantics of RoboChart are defined by means of a meta model constructed in the style of the UML meta model; but it is far smaller.

Additionally, RoboChart provides syntactic constructs for modelling hardware platforms and their controllers. Collaborating collections of robots (or other kinds of CPS components) communicate over broadcast channels. This facilitates the concise description of behavioural system semantics, because it is unnecessary to specify in detail how point-to-point connections need to be set up dynamically between pairs of collection members.

Dynamic configuration changes of collections need to be specified by enabling/disabling existing collection members. Thus, every possible configuration needs to be envisaged beforehand; there is no concept of dynamic object creation and destruction as in UML/SysML. Again, this facilitates the description of the behavioural semantics and the automated verification, in particular, verification by model checking.

The underlying time model of RoboChart is discrete: conditions (time-outs, deadlines, untimed guards that are typically associated with state machine transitions) are evaluated cyclically on each occurrence of a discrete time tick. This facilitates the transformation of RoboChart models into cyclic control programs – potentially via previous transformation into a platform-specific RoboSim model. Note, however, that the discrete time model does not allow for the specification of time-continuous evolutions, such as differential control equations, as would be possible, for example, in Hybrid Automata [87].

The concurrency model is based on the interleaving of events; the latter are communicated synchronously. Shared variable assignments are modelled by monitors offering set/get operations to these variables.

The behavioural semantics of RoboChart is transformational: A general RoboChart model M_1 is transformed into an equivalent model M_2 using the RoboChart core language only, and M_2 is transformed into a model

expressed in CSP (Communicating Sequential Processes) [92, 174]. CSP comes with a comprehensive behavioural semantics, and numerous verification tools exist for this formalism, in particular, the CSP model checker FDR [67].

5.7.2 RoboSim

Quoting from <https://robostar.cs.york.ac.uk/notations/>,

“RoboSim is a tool-independent language to model simulations of robotic systems by state machines combined to define concurrent and distributed designs that use specified services of a platform. As a diagrammatic notation, RoboSim is more appealing than programming languages and yet akin to notations in current use by practitioners. Distinctively, a RoboSim model can be verified against a UML-like design of a controller.”

In particular, the formalism models verified simulations or robotic platforms [38] and supports physical modelling of the robotic platform [145]. RoboSim is inspired by RoboChart and uses similar graphical notation, with state machines at its core for modelling behaviour. RoboSim, however, has a precisely defined cycle-based execution logic which facilitates the translation of RoboSim models into robotic simulation software. Time is discrete, and it is advanced once per cycle by the specified cycle duration. RoboSim models are interpreted in the same semantic framework as RoboChart models; this enables formal – even mechanised – verification of RoboSim models against RoboChart reference models. Moreover, rules of cyclic executions (e.g. restriction of operation calls per cycle) can be checked directly on the RoboSim model level. As RoboChart models, the semantics of RoboSim models is specified by a model translation into CSP [174].

RoboSim intentionally differs from RoboChart in the following ways: (1) The synchronous event-based communication concept of RoboChart is no longer available in RoboSim, since synchronous communication in RoboChart was intended to provide a suitable abstraction of communication, not to be implemented on the platform-specific level. Instead, writers

to channels deliver their data without being blocked, and after they have yielded the CPU in the current execution cycle, the readers can retrieve the data from the channels. (2) Concurrency in RoboChart is always serialised in RoboSim in an execution cycle, so RoboSim processes need to yield the CPU after have processed an execution fragment. In the current version of RoboSim, only single-core CPU platforms are supported, so a concurrent RoboChart model is always completely serialised in a RoboSim model with one execution cycle.

5.8 The **BIP** Framework

At the Verimag laboratory, the behavior, interaction, priority (**BIP**) component framework has been developed to support a rigorous system design flow [24].

5.9 SysML v2

The general criticism about the current versions of UML and SysML has led to an initiative to define a novel, significantly altered, standard for the systems modelling language, called SysML v2.¹⁷ The key features of this new formalism are summarised in the following paragraphs.

5.9.1 Key Features of SysML v2

Self-contained Semantics. SysML v2 is semantically self-contained; it is no longer defined as a profile of the UML, but as a separate modelling formalism. There are still language elements that have been imported from the UML, but their semantics is defined without reference to the UML, though, of course, consistency between SysML v2 and UML interpretations of these elements has been maintained.

SysML v2
is not a
UML profile

¹⁷Comprehensive documentation of SysML v2 is publicly available on <https://github.com/Systems-Modeling/SysML-v2-Release.git>.

The semantics is (rather) formally defined for a SysML v2 kernel language, and further language elements are introduced as specialisations of kernel language elements.

Textual SysML v2 and Graphical SysML v2. The new formalism comes with a complete textual concrete syntax (see example in Figure 5.15). The diagrams of SysML 1.x still exist in revised form, but they can be considered as an auxiliary visualisation which is helpful for reviewing purpose: they but do not extend the semantic expressiveness.

Textual
SysML v2

Figure 5.15: Example of textual SysML v2: parts and specialisations.

It is described in Section 5.10.3, how the features of SysML v2 are especially well-suited for the purpose of scenario modelling.

SysML v2
for
scenario
modelling

5.10 Scenario-based Modelling

5.10.1 The Need for Scenario Models

The insight that complex systems of the present and the future can no longer be specified “once and for all” by means of comprehensive models has first been published in the domain of autonomous vehicles. There, it is advocated to describe expected system behaviour rather as a library

of **operational scenarios**, instead of one comprehensive structural and behavioural model [198].

This insight, however, not only holds for autonomous systems, but for complex systems of the future in general. Software and systems engineers at Siemens Mobility, for example, state that it seems to be infeasible to represent their novel cloud-based distributed interlocking system design in a single, comprehensive formal model [159].

Definition of Scenario-related Terms. The standard ISO21448 [104] defines the following terms related to scenario specifications. We present these definitions here verbatim.

Scene [104, 3.26] **snapshot**¹⁸ of the environment including the scenery, dynamic elements, and all actors' and observers' selfrepresentations, and the relationships among those entities

Scenario [104, 3.25] description of the temporal relationship between several scenes (3.26) in a sequence of scenes (3.26), with goals and values within a specified situation (3.28), influenced by actions (3.2) and events (3.7)

Situation [104, 3.28] all relevant conditions, options and determinants for the choice of an appropriate behaviour of the system under consideration at a particular point in time

Actions [104, 3.2] single act or behaviour that is executed by any actor in a scene (3.26)

Events [104, 3.7] occurrence at a point in time

Triggering condition [104, 3.29] specific conditions of a scenario (3.25) that serve as an initiator for a subsequent system reaction leading to hazardous behaviour

Use case [104, 3.30] description of a suite of related scenarios (3.25)

¹⁸A particular state of a system, optionally including the state of its operational environment.

5.10.2 Characteristics of Scenario Modelling Formalisms

A suitable formalism for modelling scenario libraries needs to provide all ingredients to specify scenes, scenarios, situations, actions, events and triggers, as well as use cases. This comprises the usual structural and behavioural modelling elements provided by standard MBSE formalisms. Additionally, however, some scenario-specific support is necessary. Important examples for this type of support are [50, 79, 80, 212, 213]

1. language elements for specifying libraries, that is, collections of models,
2. representation of various relationships between scenario models contained in the library,
3. catalogues specifying parameters occurring in scenario models, their ranges, and their dependencies¹⁹,
4. incomplete behavioural specifications describing how scenes evolve into others, without explaining every point on the trajectory leading from one scene to another,
5. instantiation mechanisms for populating scenes, and
6. instantiation mechanisms for re-using scenes and scenarios with different parameter valuations.

Special capabilities for modelling scenarios

5.10.3 Formalisms for Scenario Modelling

ASAM OpenSCENARIO

The ASAM OpenSCENARIO standard [18]²⁰ provides a UML profile for scenario modelling in the automotive domain. Its main objective is to

OpenSCENARIO

¹⁹For example, the values of a scenario parameter *brake force of ego vehicle* in a library for autonomous cars depends on other parameters describing weather conditions, since the latter influence the effect of braking manoeuvres.

²⁰see also <https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openscenario/>

provide a modelling infrastructure for specifying complex driving manoeuvres that involve multiple vehicles. The standard is intended to support virtualised development, test, and validation in the automotive domain, with emphasis on autonomous road vehicles. OpenSCENARIO defines a data model (and associated file formats) to represent scenarios as used in driving and traffic simulators.

Both

- driver actions (such as initiating an overtaking manoeuvre) and
- pre-recorded trajectories of manoeuvres already performed

can be represented. To support the well-organised execution of multiple scenarios, the OpenSCENARIO formalism comprises

- **Entities** – the classes from which concrete instances are created to populate a scenario,
- **Storyboarding** – the sequence of actions and manoeuvres to be executed in a scenario,
- **Stories** – a grouping concept to create a hierarchy in a scenario and execute a storyboard as sequences of story executions,
- **Acts** – a grouping concept for stories,
- **Events** initiating (potentially concurrent) manoeuvres,
- **Triggers** (conditions on the state space) leading to the occurrence of events,
- **Dynamic spawning** of objects during manoeuvres,
- **Action** instances executing the manoeuvre-specific behaviour, initiated by an event,
- **References** to descriptions of the road network,
- **Instantiation** of entities playing a role in the scenarios (vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists etc.),

Modelling
elements
supported
by
OpenSCENARIO

- **Actors** – the instances of entities play a designated role in the execution of a certain manoeuvre.
- **Catalogues and parameter declarations** for instantiating scenarios multiple times.

OpenSCENARIO does not provide a behavioural semantics explaining how the scenes that are part of a scenario should evolve over time in simulations or in a real-world execution of the scenario. This induces the danger that is well-known from semantically weakly defined modelling formalisms: the precise meaning of the scenario specifications remains unclear, so that different simulation tools operating on OpenSCENARIO specifications may execute the same scenario in different ways. Consequently, the scenario simulation results obtained by different tools are not really comparable.

OpenSCENARIO
has no
behavioural
semantics

This fact and the fact that OpenSCENARIO is specialised on road traffic makes the formalism unsuitable for the purpose of specifying scenario libraries for safety-critical applications in the railway domain or the aviation domain. In fact, OpenSCENARIO is also not suitable for safety-critical applications in the automotive domain; nevertheless, it seems to be quite widely used for describing test scenarios involving autonomous road vehicles.

Despite this insufficiency, OpenSCENARIO defines scenario specification features that are helpful for other domains where ultra-high complexity suggests to use scenario modelling instead of monolithic modelling:

Useful
features of
OpenSCENARIO

1. OpenSCENARIO suggests to specify scenarios as collections of entities, manoeuvres, events, actions, conditions, and triggers, and relationships between them. These concepts are well-suited for specifying scenarios in arbitrary domains.
2. OpenSCENARIO defines the “ingredients” of a storyboard in a way that is also applicable and useful in other domains (see Figure 5.16).
 - A storyboard is structured into an **initialisation section** for setting up the scenario and the **story section** containing different groups of actions, each group representing one section (i.e. phase) of the scenario execution.

- Scenarios are reusable in several ways: for example, different storyboards, different parameter instances, different action selections, and different instances of the sets of entities involved lead to different executions of the same scenario.
3. OpenSCENARIO introduces the concept of swarms containing many similar instances of entities for simulation purposes,
 4. **Bulk actions** are defined to act on all entities of a swarm.
 5. The OpenSCENARIO execution framework with its execution patterns for scenarios is applicable to all domains.

Figure 5.16: Storyboard structure, as defined in OpenScenario (from <https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openscenario/>, OpenSCENARIO v1.2.0 User Guide).

Table 5.3: General terms of scenario modelling and their specific representations in SysML v2.

Scenario term	Represented in SysML v2 by language elements
Scene	Individual part definitions representing singleton classes of scenario participants evolving over time, snapshots representing a specific system state.
Scenario	Timeslices representing a portion of the lifetime of an instance between snapshots. then keyword for expressing causal relationships between snapshots. General behavioural modelling elements (actions and states), verification definitions .
Situation	Constraint definitions and constraint usages
Actions	Action definitions , state definitions and associated usages.
Events	Events and associated send and accept constructs.
Triggering condition	Accept constructs for message reception, change conditions , and relative or absolute time conditions (after), and guard conditions .
Use case	Use case
Parameters	Parametrised part definitions or verification definitions
Catalogues	Attribute definitions with constraints , attribute usages with constant value assignments

Scenario Modelling With SysML v2

In contrast to OpenSCENARIO, the new SysML v2 modelling formalism described in Section 5.9 has specific support for modelling scenarios in *arbitrary* domains. This support is provided by the following features of the SysML v2 modelling language.

- Powerful instantiation mechanisms, including parametrisation, re-typing of features, and overriding of features.
- Powerful action and state machine concept allowing for the creation of hierarchy, concurrent execution, and synchronisation.
- Special concept of **verification definitions** to create **test scenarios** with reference to requirements, definition of test objectives and verdicts, and the actors (called **subject** in SysML v2) involved.

General scenario libraries. Table 5.3 associates the general terms of scenario modelling introduced in Section 5.10.3 with SysML v2 language constructs that are suitable for representing each term in a SysML v2 model. The general concept of a library of scenario models does not have a specific language construct in SysML v2, but, as can be seen from Table 5.3, it can be expressed by existing language concepts (individuals, timeslices etc.) in a fairly direct way.

Verification scenarios. The specialised type of **verification scenarios**, in particular, **test scenarios**, however, can be directly expressed in SysML v2 by means of **verification definitions** and **verification usages**. A verification definition is a specialised action definition that

- monitors a set of observable features of a system under test (SUT) without changing them,
- stimulates another set of SUT features, in order to drive the SUT into states from where the test objectives can be checked and to provoke the SUT reactions associated with this objective, and

- finally delivers a **verdict** stating whether the SUT reactions conform to the expected behaviour.

A verification usage is an instance of a verification definition, and all the SysML v2 mechanisms for specialisation can be used to link the verification usage to a specific SUT with specific parametrisation and refined sub-actions tailored to the SUT and to the test objectives under consideration. With these mechanisms, many concrete test procedures can be constructed from one verification definition with small effort.

In Listing 5.1, a simple generic SysML v2 test scenario is shown in textual form as a verification definition. The **subject** keyword (line 3) identifies the system under test which is a drone in this example. The **port** usage in lines 4 — 6 is an interface specification describing how commands can be sent to the drone. The **requirement** keyword allows us to specify which requirements will be covered by the verification definition. The original requirements used in this example represent test requirements. These are shown in Listing 5.2. Each requirement refers to a subject (here, the subjects are general types of drones) and specifies the required property in textual form. Optionally, this may be formalised further by adding constraints specifying logical conditions about some of the subject's features. In Listing 5.1, these test requirements are specialised to the drone that is being tested (lines 8—9), and this specifies the concrete **test objectives** shown in lines 13—16.

The test execution is structured into a sequence of actions. Their execution order is controlled by the statements in lines 49—54: we start with the `startOfTestAction`. If this step is completed without error (if-condition in line 52), the second test step `sendUp` is performed, otherwise, the test is aborted. The `startOfTestAction` is defined in lines 18—21. It just checks whether the SUT is at the required starting point from where it should take off. Test step `sendUp` invokes a terminating state machine `sendUpState` which sends a start command to the drone and terminates after 10 seconds (line 28). This also terminates action `sendUp`, after which the `checkHeightAction` is invoked (line 31). The latter checks test objective `testObj2` which requires that the drone should have reached the desired target height (lines 33—36).

Listing 5.1: Test scenario specified in the SysML v2 textual representation.

```

1  verification def TestScenario1 {
2
3      subject sut : Drone;
4      port toSutPort {
5          out enum cmd : DroneCommands;
6      }
7
8      requirement testObj1 :> testReq1 { part sut redefines drone; }
9      requirement testObj2 :> testReq2 { part sut redefines drone; }
10
11     return currentVerdict : VerdictKind;
12
13     objective testObjective {
14         verify testObj1;
15         verify testObj2;
16     }
17
18     action startOfTestAction {
19         out verdict : VerdictKind = currentVerdict;
20         assign verdict := PassIf(testObj1.AtStartingPoint(d = sut));
21     }
22
23     action sendUp {
24         state sendUpState {
25             entry send DroneCommands::goUp to toSutPort;
26             then waitState;
27             state waitState;
28             accept after 10[s] then done;
29         }
30     }
31     then checkHightAction;
32
33     action checkHightAction {
34         out verdict : VerdictKind = currentVerdict;
35         assign verdict := PassIf(testObj2.AtTargetHight(d = sut));
36     }
37     then terminateTest;
38
39     action terminateTest {
40         send DroneCommands::comeBack to toSutPort;

```

```

41     }
42     then done;
43
44     action abortTest {
45         assign currentVerdict := VerdictKind::error;
46     }
47     then done;
48
49     first start;
50     then startOfTestAction;
51     decide;
52     if currentVerdict == VerdictKind::pass
53     then sendUp;
54     else abortTest;
55 }

```

Listing 5.2: Requirements that are covered by the verification definition above.

```

1  constraint def AtStartingPoint {
2      in d : Drone;
3      d.velocity.num == 0 and
4      d.location.num[1] == 0 and d.location.num[2] == 0 and d.location.num[3]
5          == 0
6  }
7  constraint def AtTargetHight {
8      in d : Drone;
9      d.location.num[3] >= 0.5 [km]
10 }
11 requirement testReq1 {
12     doc /* Drone resides at starting point */
13     subject drone : Drone;
14     require constraint AtStartingPoint { d = drone; }
15 }
16 requirement testReq2 {
17     doc /* 10[s] after start of test, the drone as reached a
18         * hight of at least 0.5[km]
19         */
20     subject drone : Drone;
21     require constraint AtTargetHight { d = drone; }

```

In Listing 5.3, it is shown how the generic test scenario specified in verification definition `TestScenario1` can be instantiated to yield different test procedures:

- We use two different types of drones as SUTs (lines 2—3).
- The generic test scenario is instantiated two times as verification usages in lines 6 and 9. This yields two test procedures, where the test specification modelled in `TestScenario1` is first exercised on SUT `drone1` and then on the other SUT `drone2`.

Note that when creating verification usages from verification definitions, not only the `sut`-feature can be redefined, but also test objectives, actions, and attributes representing specific test parameters.

Listing 5.3: Concrete tests resulting from different drone types and different usages of verification definition `TestScenario1`.

```

1  /* Concrete drones acting as systems under test (SUT) */
2  part drone1 : Drone { redefines drive : SingleRotorDrive; }
3  part drone2 : Drone { redefines drive : MultiRotorDrive; }
4
5  /* Test 1 executes test scenario with drone1 as SUT */
6  verification test1 : TestScenario1 { part drone1 redefines sut; }
7
8  /* Test 2 executes test scenario with drone2 as SUT */
9  verification test2 : TestScenario1 { part drone2 redefines sut; }

```

5.10.4 A Priori Completeness Verification of Scenario Libraries

An obvious drawback of scenario libraries is that they are harder to check for completeness than single, monolithic models. Since the latter cannot be constructed for systems of ultra-high complexity, we need to cope with this drawback in the context of V&V. In any case, it is possible to perform conventional reviews of scenario libraries and tools to check the consistency of their interfaces.

The crucial question, however, remains the following.

How can we check that the scenario library covers all relevant scenes and scenarios that are reachable in the real operational environment?

In the ISO 21448 standard, the harmful consequences of insufficient scenario specifications are discussed and illustrated as shown in Figure 5.17.

Scenario completeness

Harmful consequences of incomplete scenario libraries

Figure 5.17: From trigger conditions to harm [104, p.19].

- Omission of a scenario or incomplete specification of a scenario can both result in unexpected hazard events when this scenario applies in a real-world situation.
- Due to their unexpected nature, the active system safety supervisors cannot react adequately, and so the hazardous events remain unhandled, potentially resulting in an accident.

Since in the context of safety-critical systems, a transition to an unexpected scene or scenario can have catastrophic consequences, it is obvious

that simple structured reviews will not be sufficient to answer this question in a satisfactory way, so that certification credit could be obtained for the library. Instead, Hauer et al. [82] suggest to perform a statistical test regarding scenario completeness, so that the following statement is obtained.

The probability \bar{p} to encounter an unexpected scene or scenario is less or equal than $p \in [0, 1]$, and this statement is correct with confidence level $\text{conf} \in [0, 100]\%$.

Statistical
completeness
statement

Hauer et al. [82] have applied this concept for checking the completeness of test scenarios for autonomous road vehicles; Peleska [159] has demonstrated that this approach is also applicable in other domains, such as railway control systems of ultra-high complexity.

Observe that such a statistical notion of specification completeness is not acceptable according to the standards currently applicable for safety-critical control systems in the avionic or railway domain. There, it is expected that a specification is complete and consistent “with probability 1”, after a thorough **V&V** campaign according to the highest safety integrity levels (DAL-A or SIL-4) has been performed. Consequently, scenario-based system specifications can only be applied in these domains after such a change of standards has been implemented.

Standardisation
considerations

The mathematical approach for obtaining such a completeness probability with associated confidence level is based on the **coupon collector’s problem (CCP)** that is well-known in the field of statistics. The variant needed for investigating scenario completeness is based on the results obtained by Flajolet [63]. This **CCP** variant considers n different types of coupons in an urn, such that drawing a coupon of type $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ from the urn with replacement has probability p_i . The **CCP** considers the random variable X denoting the number of draws necessary to obtain a coupon of each type at least once. The expected value of X is calculated by [63]

Coupon
Collector’s
Problem
(Coupon
Collector’s
Problem
(CCP))

$$E(X) = \int_0^{\infty} \left(\prod_{i=1}^n (1 - e^{-p_i x}) \right) dx.$$

For validating scenario completeness, an executable prototype of the

Application
of CCP to
checking
scenario
completeness

scenario library, or an initial implementation of the target system is needed in addition to the scenario library consisting of models Sc_1, \dots, Sc_n . Then input sequences (test cases) for the system prototype are generated at random. These test cases are run against the prototype embedded in (a simulation of) its operational environment, and this yields (timed) input output/sequences π that take the role of a coupon in the **CCP** that has been drawn from the urn. Now π is matched against the scenario specifications. If one Sc_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ is found such that π matches to this scenario's input/output language, this corresponds to "having drawn coupon number i from the urn". Let p_i be the probability for π to match to scenario Sc_i . If the scenario library were complete, the sum over these probabilities would yield 1, that is,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1.$$

If during these random tests a sequence π is found that does not match to any scenario, four cases are distinguished.

1. If the input sequence generated at random should cannot occur in the real operational environment, for example, because physical constraints prevent certain event to occur in the generated sequence, the test is discarded.
2. If the input sequence is adequate, but none of the n scenarios is prepared to process this sequence, the library needs to be extended, and the protoype must be updated. After that, the test campaign is re-started.
3. If π should *not* be in the input/output language of the system, a test failure has been discovered, and the target system is fixed. After that, the tests are run again.
4. If π is a legal input/output sequence, the scenario library is incomplete and needs to be extended, either by extending an existing scenario, or by adding a new one. After the extension, the tests are run again.

We are now interested in the question when we have tested enough, so that the likelihood of having missed some scenario is sufficiently small. Recall that the number of test cases to be performed until every scenario Sc_i has been covered at least once is represented by random variable X .

While $E(X)$ gives us an idea of the order of magnitude of the number of samples needed to cover every scenario Sc_i at least once, we need a (higher) value of samples \bar{S} required to discover all members *with sufficiently high probability*. This means that we are looking for a natural number \bar{S} such that $P(X < \bar{S}) = \tau$ is close to 1. Following Hauer et al. [82], we split the testing activities into different verification runs V_k , $k = 1, \dots, m$, each run containing at least as many test cases such that every known scenario is covered at least once. Then the probability $P(X < S)$ can be estimated for any value $S \in \mathbb{N}$ by

$$P(X < S) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{\ell=1}^S \text{occ}(\ell), \quad (5.22)$$

where $\text{occ}(\ell)$ denotes the number of verification runs V_k where all scenarios have been covered by ℓ test cases. Note that $\text{occ}(\ell) = 0$ for $\ell < n$. We select \bar{S} as the smallest S such that the value of $P(X < S)$ calculated by Equation (5.22) is greater or equal the desired value of τ . The number m of verification sets V_k to be used in Equation (5.22) determines the confidence that we can have in the estimate for $P(X < \bar{S})$; minimal values for m achieving a given confidence value can be calculated as described by Hauer et al. [82].

If each verification run V_k contains a sufficiently large number of test cases, the runs can also be used to estimate the probabilities p_i of some sequence π to match with scenario Sc_i . Suppose now that all verification runs have been successful, but that the scenario library is still incomplete. This means that a missing scenario Sc_{new} exists that has not been covered yet by any of the π obtained in the verification runs V_k . Suppose that the missing scenario is matched by an observation π with probability p_{new} . Then we would have to re-scale the occurrence probabilities p_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$

Probability
for
execution
to trigger
an
unknown
scenario

by $p'_i = (1 - p_{\text{new}})p_i$, such that

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n p'_i\right) + p_{\text{new}} = 1.$$

Since Sc_{new} has not been observed in any of the verification runs V_k , its matching probability p_{new} must be smaller than each of the p'_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, because all scenarios Sc_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ have been matched at least once in *every* V_k , $k = 1, \dots, m$. Consequently, the test runs V_k also yield an estimate for the probability p_{new} that an execution π will occur during system operation that will trigger the unknown scenario Sc_{new} . This complements the estimate for $P(X < S)$ in Equation (5.22).

The most important open problem with the application of the **CCP** [Open issues](#) to the verification of scenario completeness is that naively generated random test cases are often implausible for **CPS**, because they just represent **robustness** tests. Plausible sequences of inputs to the system under test need to fulfil rules that are unlikely to be met during unconstrained random generation. Consequently, it is necessary to set up rule bases or create nondeterministic reference models implementing these rules. The test cases are then constructed by random selection from the set of input sequences fulfilling these rules.

5.10.5 A Posteriori Completeness Verification of Scenario Libraries

Hungar [100] advocates a complementary concept for verifying scenario completeness. This is based on testing, and the tests are executed *after* the system and its safety supervisors have been implemented.

- The same input sequences as used in Section 5.10.4 are now sent to the system implementation running in a simulation environment.
- Then a risk assessment is made, based on the number of input sequences executed and the number of harmful simulation outcomes caused by insufficient or missing scenario specifications.

5.11 Modelling Risk

This section provides an overview of the aspects to consider when modelling complex systems for the purpose of risk assessment and, moreover, for the purpose of designing controllers for risk mitigation [69].

5.11.1 Modelling Systems for Risk Assessment

Consider a **world** where several actors (agents, e.g. a system and its environment) perform actions. These actions can affect entities (e.g. humans, animals, environmental objects, assets) and result in effects comprising various desired (thus rewarded) and undesired (thus costed) outcomes. Undesired actions may exploit vulnerabilities of humans or animals, injure these, cause damage to the environment, or decrease the value of an asset from the viewpoint of an observer (e.g. assessors). Some entities are, thus, subjected to protection.

World
model

Now, consider variables through which assessors can observe the action effects according to the types of these variables. The resulting product type yields the state space of the world under consideration. The choice and performance of an action by a capable actor in a state will have one of potentially several alternative effects. The uncertainty about which effect is observed (as an event and reified in a successor state) can be described by non-deterministic or probabilistic choice of this actor's environment. Furthermore, we use the notion of a **situation** to refer to both an initial condition (i.e. a subset of the state space) and an evolution assumption (i.e. a set of action sequences or **plans** potentially enacted by any of the actors).

States of
a world
model

5.11.2 Modelling Risk

Risk in a situation can then be characterised as the possibility of undesired outcomes (e.g. loss, injury, damage) of one or more (planned) actions (whether nominal, faulty, or malicious) with uncertain effects when performed by any of the actors in that situation.²¹ Each situation combined

²¹If there is no choice and the effects of all actions are determined then we need not

with one of its hypothesised effects yields a **scenario** that forms a coherent unit for risk quantification. A scenario then denotes a subset of the evolution assumption (e.g. the choice of a particular plan) leading from the situation's state subset to the corresponding effect. For example, Kaplan and Garrick [121] associate a likelihood to each such scenario and costs to the undesired outcome included in the associated effect.

Scenarios

Because real-world state spaces and action systems can be complex, risk assessment needs to focus on critical states and events, particularly, **mishaps** (e.g. severe accidents or **incidents**) and their causes or causal factors known as **hazards** (errors, faults, failures). Consequently, practitioners start with predicting or learning from mishaps and identify hazardous states (e.g. errors, faults) as well as actions (e.g. failures, **incidents**, accidents) leading to the hazard and mishap states. The causal relationship between hazard and mishap is often refined into a causal net. Hence, scenarios will often not only be situation/effect pairs but **hazard/mishap pairs** or, more generally, fragments of the hypothesised causal net in form of **causal factor pairs**. A wide range of risk analysis techniques for different purposes has been developed in the past five to six decades [58, 125, 135].

Mishaps
and
hazards

Risk assessment in practice is often even further simplified using tabular techniques [116] where each scenario is classified along likelihood of occurrence and severity (e.g. of damage) scales. Additionally, hazards are usually identified to be those states where hazard control actions can still be applied to reduce either the likelihood or the severity of a mishap. As a simple but powerful instrument, Kaplan and Garrick [121] propose **risk curves** to assess risk along a cumulative scale within the envelope of “probability of any damage at all” and “maximum possible damage”.

5.11.3 Challenges in Risk Modelling

For complex autonomous multi-agent systems in unstructured environments, the mentioned simplifications and tabular techniques have shown their limits. Precise **compositional risk modelling** is required in order to perform trustworthy risk assessments that can be used for formal veri-

talk of “risk”, “opportunity”, or “chance” because the exact outcomes are known.

fication of control systems and even be calculated by these systems during operation. This modelling includes the combination of causal factors of a different character and dependencies between causal factors.

5.11.4 Risk Quantification

From an observer's viewpoint, risk of a scenario can be assessed by

Quantitative
assessment
of risk

1. the likelihood of a reachable hazard or, similarly, the likelihood of exposure of a vulnerable entity to this hazard,
2. the likelihood of an **accident** reachable from this hazard, and
3. the severity of this undesired outcome [131, 135].

As suggested by Kaplan and Garrick [121], this triplet can be estimated for any number of scenarios and compiled into a compound risk assessment.

5.11.5 Risk Mitigation

From an actor's (or controller's) viewpoint, risk can be further assessed by taking into account

Risk
mitigation
by
controllable
actions

4. planned behaviour of the actor in a situation,
5. predicted behaviour of the actor's environment in that situation, and
6. the actor's ability to make plan changes for escaping high-risk scenarios.

This viewpoint can be used as a refined view determining or explaining the mishap likelihood and severity from the observer's viewpoint. Risk can thus be influenced by an actor and its controllable actions (i.e. its capabilities).

5.11.6 Risk Mitigation by Automatic Control

As described in Section 4.6, safety controllers are used to make decisions about risk-mitigating actions, with the objective to minimise the risk of an **accident** occurring as a consequence of a hazard [71]. Also, the synthesis of new plans, as well as building new configurations of safety-critical systems of systems requires risk assessment at run-time, in order to determine whether the new plan or the collaboration in a new configuration is sufficiently safe [28, 29]. The effect of all possible controller actions needs to be assessed in a quantitative way regarding the risk that is involved.

Safety
controllers

For quantitative (or probabilistic) risk assessment and controller design, it is beneficial to refine the discussed scenario models and safety control concepts into a Markov model as introduced in Section 5.3.2. However, the transfer of all the relevant knowledge into such a model (i.e. suitable abstraction from the real-world, refinement of control actions to a suitable level) is far from straightforward as well as subject to a range of modelling limitations and uncertainties. As of today, there is no standardised way for modelling the risk-related impact of safety controllers.

Design of
Safety
Controllers

5.11.7 Structured Specification of Safety Controllers

However, a structured approach to the specification of safety controllers has been proposed in [70, 71]. There, a specification language called **risk structures** is advocated. A risk structure is built from a set of risk factors and dependencies between these factors suitable for describing a causal net. Moreover, a risk structure is always associated with an application process whose risk it describes. **Risk factors** come as labelled-transition-system patterns (see Section 5.1.4) capturing hazard-specific response properties that can be instantiated during the translation of results from hazard analyses and risk assessments [58, 125, 135] into a risk model. After conjoining the specified risk factors, a risk structure simply corresponds to a compound property in the response fragment of temporal logic [138]. Risk structures are associated with a graph representation (Figure 5.19) derived from the LTS-representation of the composition of all involved risk factors. Each risk factor f (Figure 5.18) models the life cycle of the occurrence and mit-

Risk
structures

Figure 5.18: Template of a risk factor according to [74]

igation of a particular hazard and its associated risk. Separating nominal, endangered, and mitigated modes of operation (the nodes labelled with f_0 , f_a , and f_m), the factor template in Figure 5.18 describes

- *hazard occurrence* (the arcs labelled with e^f and \bar{e}^f),
- *hazard mitigation*, allowing a non-essential/methodological separation of direct mitigation from mitigation with recovery (the arcs labelled with m^f , m_d^f , and m_r^f), and
- *mode behaviour* (the arcs labelled with o_n^f , o_e^f , and o_m^f).

The information provided with the risk factors allows the extraction of a state machine representing a safety controller, for example, by

1. associating pre-/postcondition pairs or guarded commands to the risk factors' non-self-loop transitions and
2. generating a safety controller and checking the embedding of that controller into the world model against the risk structure.

In Figure 5.19, a risk structure is developed for an automated-driving-assistance scenario, where each *risk state* (i.e. each node in the graph) corresponds to a combination of inactive, active, or mitigated vehicle software (L) and sensor (A) faults and reduced driver vigilance (R). The arcs

Figure 5.19: Graph representation of a 3-factor risk structure according to [71] for handling certain hazards in automated driving

labelled with f^A and f^L are merely variants of e -transitions indicating faults rather than generic hazards (cf. Figure 5.18). Arcs labelled with \approx_f hint at the possibility of comparing risk states according to certain criteria (e.g. mitigated hazards), as highlighted in more detail in [71]. The selection of suitable risk-mitigation actions and the (manual) design of a safety controller can then be performed by means of path analyses on (refinements of) the graph in Figure 5.19 when composed with the application process.

5.11.8 Synthesis of Safety Controllers

As an alternative to the manual design of safety controllers, it is explained in [70, 75], how safety controllers can be synthesised (i.e. automatically generated) from risk structures based on transition system refinements and strategy synthesis for Markov decision processes (Section 5.3.2) including these refinements. A result of such a synthesis, called a policy or strategy, is depicted in Figure 5.20.

In this 5-factor example, the safety controller extracted from the policy is designed to handle certain collision hazards in a human-robot collaboration scenario. The Markov model for this scenario includes sensor uncertainties and erroneous human behaviour for precise but robust assessment and synthesis. Importantly, the resulting Markov policy contains the information to derive source code for safety controllers to be deployed on, for example, micro-controllers or robotic control platforms. In particular, the entirety of the green transitions in Figure 5.20 would be converted into, for example, a C# or C++ code fragment embedded into a real-time controller execution framework. There is preliminary tool support available for describing risk structures, synthesising and testing such controllers [68].

With safety controller design and assurance in mind, risk structures aim at filling the abstraction gap between risk assessment and design of safety controllers and between pragmatic qualitative risk assessments with hazard lists and probabilistic risk assessment using stochastic models. For a full account of the presented concepts with more technical details, we refer the inclined reader to [74, 75].

Figure 5.20: Graph representation of a set of deterministic mitigation strategies (fragment shown) derived from a risk structure and embedded into a world model according to [75]. Grey nodes represent the world state space reachable from a defined initial state. Green edges denote mitigation options of the safety controller; red, black, and blue edges denote assumed actions of the monitored system and other agents in the environment.

Part III

Ensuring Test Strength

Chapter 6

Some Terminology Related to Testing

In the context of this report, the following approaches to testing are relevant.

Property-Based Testing (PBT)¹ checks whether the **SUT** fulfils a specified property (e.g. a requirement). **PBT** is typically used for functional tests verifying the **SUT** behaviour or structural tests verifying its interfaces. Testing against requirements, as is mandatory according to the current standards in the transportation domains [40, 113, 206], is a variant of **PBT**. Property-based testing

Model-based Testing (MBT) checks whether the **SUT** conforms to a reference model – this is also used for functional and structural testing. Model-based testing

Performance testing checks whether the **SUT** fulfils some non-functional properties, such as throughput or **robustness** under high loads. In the context of autonomous systems, the term **performance** is also used for the degree the **SUT** fulfils the Safety of the Intended Functionality (**SOTIF**) [104, 199], so performance testing checks the effectiveness of the implemented function for its intended purpose. In the remainder of this chapter, the term ‘performance’ will be used in this sense. Performance testing

¹also called **Property-Oriented Testing (POT)**

In the context of **MBT**, different **conformance relations** defining whether an **SUT** is correct with respect to its reference model are used.

Equivalence between model and **SUT** holds if the **SUT** “behaves exactly” as the reference model. Depending on the testing goals and the underlying theory, ‘exactly’ can have different meanings, all of them can be formalised in a mathematical way. A popular equivalence definition is **language equivalence** which means that the **SUT** performs exactly the same sequences of inputs and outputs that are possible according to the reference model [94].

Conformance
relation
'equivalence'

Reduction (also called **refinement**) holds if the interface language of the **SUT** is a subset of the interface language of the model. Intuitively speaking, reduction ensures that the **SUT** “only performs I/O-sequences that are allowed according to the model.” Consequently, reduction preserves all safety properties fulfilled by the model.

Conformance
relation
'reduction'

Important variants of the reduction relation are

Quasi reduction allows the **SUT** to show arbitrary behaviour in cases where the reference model does not state what should happen [91].

Strong reduction requires that the **SUT** does *not allow* inputs that are unspecified in certain model states [178]. This variant of reduction is relevant for systems where certain inputs are disabled in specific operational situations.

The quasi reduction relation is quite important in the context of scenario models: since each model of the library just describes what should happen in a certain operational situation, these models are incomplete. Unspecified behaviours in one model should be covered by another model which is part of the library.

Strong reduction is the preferred conformance relation, for example, for user interfaces (certain buttons or menus are unavailable in some GUI states) or mechatronic systems (e.g. another credit card cannot be inserted into the card reader, if there is already one in the slot).

Chapter 7

Test-Related Challenges for Systems of Ultra-high Complexity

As will be reviewed in the sections below, testing strategies with guaranteed fault coverage¹ exist already since the 1970s and have been thoroughly investigated. Ultra-complex systems (see definition on page 13), however, pose new challenges to testing, specifically on system-level:

- The expected functional behaviour of system components whose behaviour is based on **machine learning** cannot be specified by conventional models, as discussed in Section 2.5. Main challenges
- If the system behaviour evolves over time, it is impossible to create a reference model describing the desired system behaviour once and for all in a comprehensive way at type certification time.
- Instead of test case derivation from one comprehensive model, test cases need to be created from a library of scenario models.
- Ultra-complex systems often collaborate at runtime in changing configurations, with conceptually unbounded configuration spaces (see Example 25 below).

¹the capability of a test suite to uncover certain types of faults

- Multi-agent systems synthesising contracts and plans at runtime cannot be tested once and for all at type certification time, since the contracts and plans to be synthesised during system operation is unpredictable.
- Complex parametrisation lead to a combinatorial explosion of parameter combinations to be checked.

As a consequence, conventional testing approaches deriving “useful” test cases from specifications, in particular, models, are much harder to apply or even – in the case of trained **neural networks**, for example – no longer adequate. Moreover, there is a growing need for **stochastic testing** for the situations where the required relations between inputs to the **SUT** and expected outputs cannot be specified in some formal logic, and, therefore, not verified by means of a proof theory. Though software-based, these components need to be considered as black boxes, where inputs are only transformed into correct outputs with a certain probability. This is similar to investigating hardware reliability, and currently not accepted by the conventional standards for safety-critical transportation systems, such as EN50128 or RTCA DO-178C [40, 206]. The most prominent example for software components requiring statistical **V&V** are those based on **machine learning**, in particular, **neural networks** for image classification.

The need
for
stochastic
testing

Araujo et al. [15] give an overview of testing methods and tools currently applied for testing autonomous robots and road vehicles. From this publication, it can be concluded that in the research communities, stochastic approaches (for example, based on Markov chains and **MDP** or Stochastic Petri Nets) to testing are currently investigated. Furthermore, many specific testing obligations for autonomous road vehicles, (collaborating) robots, and multi-agent systems in general have been investigated. As Araujo et al. point out, however, this has not yet led to an accepted unified testing theory: instead, the new approaches are applied to particular problems. Also, no widely accepted tool support is available for these approaches, though numerous prototype tools exist.

For autonomous road vehicles, commercial testing and simulation tools have reached the market. These, however, do not yet come with a the-

Commercial
tools for
testing
autonomous
road
vehicles

oretically well-founded methodology that has been published and can be checked with respect to their actual test strength.²

²https://www.ni.com/de-de/solutions/transportation/adas-and-autonomous-driving-validation.html?cid=Paid_Search-7013q000001Ugs4AAC-Consideration-GoogleSearch_129581992754&gclid=CjwKCAjwrZ0XBhACEiwA0EoRD9GqVfAuNXTp9g8BHGYL6zrqFlKSviIS7K79dbKfvFh-nUtafrQibhoCu3YQAvD_BwE, https://btc-embedded.com/de/use_cases/scenario-generation/, https://www.googleadservices.com/pagead/aclk?sa=L&ai=DChcSEwiNvtq5vKD5AhXH4ncKHTf_C7cYABABGgJlZg&ae=2&ohost=www.google.com&cid=CAESa-D2jed1G-wEKMy6C-00U6vGQkU3Xy10mvZzzRZoF61pRKmkTTFurc-3M4gKpZe6neEGe3988IPCNODnHlwlkLe-ERmx4B_VUwkIam2SOLv1DkUi4xGvSON0mbwmNIDPtxtbKtQeKS1gRnJw&sig=AOD64_2FrzvuNq2ied2-tg7g-3_8VDrf0g&q&adurl&ved=2ahUKEwj6wdK5vKD5AhUqVfEDHVeMBOsQ0Qx6BAGiEAE&nis=8&dct=1

Chapter 8

Complete Testing Theories

A testing theory is a method for generating test cases from models or property specifications, such that the resulting test suites guarantee a certain fault coverage. This means that the test suite is guaranteed to uncover SUT errors of a certain kind, as long as the SUT fulfils some well-defined hypotheses. A fault domain \mathcal{D} is a set of models representing correct and faulty SUT behaviours.

Though, as discussed in Section 7, these theories do not solve all testing challenges for ultra-complex systems, it will turn out that they play an important role in the verification of safety supervisors, provided that certain architectural principles can be enforced, as described above in Section 4.7.

8.1 Conformance Testing

In conformance testing, the SUT is required to fulfil a conformance relation with a reference model, as indicated in Section 6. A test suite is called **complete** with respect to fault domain \mathcal{D} , reference model M , and conformance relation \leq , if

Complete
conformance
test suites

- every SUT conforming to M passes the test suite (this feature is called **soundness**), and
- every SUT violating the conformance relation to M fails at least one test case of the suite, provided its true behaviour is represented by a

member of the fault domain (this feature is called **exhaustiveness**).

For black-box testing, the assumption about the fault domain is essential, because it cannot be checked explicitly whether the test suite has covered the relevant **SUT** states and transitions. For grey-box or white-box testing, the question whether the true **SUT** behaviour is contained in the fault domain can be answered by static analysis of the software code and by monitoring the embedded **HW/SW** execution environment [72].

A detailed description of the “classical” Finite State Machine (**FSM**)-based conformance testing methods for language equivalence is given by Huang et al. [160].

For practical purposes, the restriction to finite state machine models is too limited, since many more complex **CPS** operate on conceptually infinite inputs (e.g. sensor values for real-valued physical observables) and outputs. It turns out, however, that equivalence class testing theories can be applied to these more complex systems, so that their reference models may again be abstracted to finite state machines. Complete test suites for the latter then induce likewise complete suites for the original complex **CPS**. This is discussed further below in Section 18.

Example 22. One of the first and simplest complete conformance testing methods is the so-called **W-Method** [46, 201]. The reference models used here are Mealy state machines with finite state space, finite input alphabet, and finite output alphabet. The **W-Method** produces test cases for checking language equivalence. Let M be a finite state machine (**FSM**) that is deterministic and minimal and has n states. Then the fault domain for the **W-Method** contains all behaviours expressible by **FSMs** over the same alphabets with at most $m \geq n$ states.

The **W-Method** creates test suites of the form

$$\mathcal{W}(M) = V \cdot \left(\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-n+1} \Sigma_I^i \right) \cdot W,$$

where

- V (the so-called **state cover**) is a set of input sequences reaching every state of the model M ,

- $\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-n+1} \Sigma_I^i$ (the so-called **traversal set**) is the set of all input sequences from length zero (empty sequence) to $m - n + 1$, constructed over all elements of the input alphabet Σ_I , and
- W (the **characterisation set**) is a set of input traces α , such that each pair of states from M can be distinguished by at least one $\alpha \in W$.¹

Every input sequence $\tau \in \mathcal{W}(M)$ is a concatenation of an input sequence of V , followed by a (possibly empty) sequence contained in the traversal set, and suffixed by an input sequence from the characterisation set W .

As an example, consider the reference model A in Fig. 8.1 which has two states. Consider further an **SUT** behaviour represented by **FSM** B shown in the same figure. State cover, traversal set and characterisation set are constructed as shown in the figure. It turns out that B is *not* language equivalent to A , so the **SUT** violates this conformance relation. This can be seen, for example, by applying input sequence $0.0.0.1 \in \mathcal{W}(A)$ to A and B : application to A results in output sequence $a.b.a.a$, while application to B results in output sequence $a.b.a.b$.

¹Input sequence α distinguishes states s_1 and s_2 of M , if application of inputs α to state s_1 result in an output sequence β that differs from output sequence β' obtained when applying α to s_2 .

Figure 8.1: Simple application of the W-Method.

□

Complete testing strategies for reduction and its variants (strong reduction, quasi reduction) have been presented by Hierons et al. [89, 91], Petrenko et al. [164, 165], and Sachtleben et al. [178, 179].

8.2 Property-based Testing

In industry, testing of CPS is usually performed by a hybrid approach, involving both properties and models. Requirements are specified as properties, and models are used as starting points of system and software design [158, 161]. It is checked by review or by model checking that the models reflect the required properties in the correct way.

Due to the complexity of large embedded systems like railway and

In industry, both models and properties are specified

avionic control systems, testing for model conformance only happens on sub-system or module level, while testing on system integration level or system level is property-based, though models are available. In particular during regression testing, test cases are selected to check specific requirements (i.e. properties), and hardly ever to establish full model conformance. Indeed, standards for safety-critical systems only accept test suites whose cases can be traced back to individual requirements [206, 209].

A property testing strategy is called **complete** for a set P of properties, if

- every **SUT** fulfilling the properties of P passes the suite (again, this is called **soundness**), and
- every **SUT** violating one or more properties of P fails at least one test case of the suite (**exhaustiveness**).

Complete test suites for property-based testing

If a reference model fulfilling the properties exists, the test suite construction can be simplified. Interestingly, however, complete test suites for model-based property-oriented testing often require more test cases than test suites for language equivalence [95]. Since language equivalence implies that *all* properties fulfilled by the model are also fulfilled by the SUT, the conformance test for language equivalence is preferable in such a situation.

In most applications it is acceptable or even desirable to uncover also errors that are not related to the property under test, but show that the **SUT** violates the conformance relation. A property-based testing strategy is therefore called **exhaustive** if

- every **SUT** passing the test suite fulfils all properties of P , and
- every **SUT** failing at least one test case in the suite violates language equivalence (this may or may not imply that it violates a property of P).

Exhaustive test suites for property-based testing

Observe that violating a property of P always implies that the **SUT** is not language equivalent to the reference model.

Krafzcyk et al. [98, 129] have presented exhaustive model-based property-oriented testing strategies for **symbolic finite state machine (SFSM)** models. This model type corresponds to a restricted variant of UML state machines. References to other (heuristic, non-exhaustive) approaches to property-based testing are given by Huang et al. [97], where also a safety-related specialised variant for property-based testing is presented.

For complete or exhaustive testing strategies, properties need to be specified in a formal logic, such as **linear time logic (LTL)** [47]. These formal property specification languages are not that widely adopted in industry, where requirements are often specified in natural language combined with informal drawings. The SysML v2 modelling formalism (Section 5.9) allows to combine informal requirements specifications with formal constraints, so that it becomes at least possible to associate formal specifications with informal ones.

Formal
property
specifications

8.3 Complete Testing Theories for Partial Models

When testing against scenario libraries, reference models are typically **incomplete**, because specific sets of inputs are not applicable for the given scenario in a certain state. In these situations, it is desirable to use incomplete models and conformance relations accepting arbitrary **SUT** behaviour for undefined model inputs in specific states. These conformance relations exist, and they are called **quasi equivalence** or **quasi reduction** [90, 91] in the world of **FSM** models and **I/O conformance (ioco)** when event-based models with labelled transition system semantics are used [200]. Tretmans [197] favours an updated variant of the ioco relation, called **uioco**.

Incomplete
scenario
models
and
associated
conformance
relations

Complete testing strategies for this type of conformance relation exist [90, 91]. They exploit the idea that inputs in a model state where no reaction is specified need not be tested, since arbitrary **SUT** reactions are admissible. Of course, the required **SUT** reactions should be specified in and tested against another scenario model. This highlights again the importance of scenario completeness discussed in Section 5.10.4.

8.4 Trustworthy Equivalence Class Construction

As pointed out in Section 8.1 above, testing against FSMs is often too restrictive, since this requires finite (and reasonably small) enumerations of all possible inputs and outputs. Fortunately, many system models using conceptually infinite interface domains and quantifier free first order expressions as guard conditions and arithmetic expressions in output assignments can be abstracted to FSM models by means of equivalence class construction techniques [98]. Then complete test suites can be derived from these FSM abstractions and refined again to concrete test suites for the SUT by selecting concrete representatives from each class. It has been shown that this process preserves completeness, as long as specific, sufficiently fine-grained equivalence class partitions are chosen [93, 94].

Complex systems can be abstracted to FSMs

For these more general reference models (e.g. symbolic finite state machines), the fault domains need to be extended: assumptions about the potential guard and expressions mutations used by faulty implementations need to be made [98, 166]. This suggests a complete grey-box software testing approach to be applied on module level, where the expressions used in the implementation can be extracted by means of static analysis, and other hypotheses related to the underlying fault-domain can be checked as well [72, 76].

Practical evaluations show that the construction of equivalence classes results in complete test suites of manageable size for systems of medium complexity (e.g. airbag controllers, railway interlocking sub-system controllers, speed monitors) [99]. This shows that safety-critical subsystems or modules can usually be verified using complete test suites.

8.5 Application of Complete Testing Theories to Systems of Ultra-high Complexity

As pointed out in Section 7, testing ultra-complex systems requires new testing methodologies. This does not mean, however, that existing methods

have become useless. It just has to be understood where and when to apply conventional testing strategies and new ones, respectively. This insight applies, in particular, to complete testing theories. Since these require considerable effort, both for test suite generation and test suite execution, they are typically applied to safety-critical sub-systems or modules of a larger system.

As discussed in Section 4.7, it is often possible for ultra-complex autonomous systems to segregate the system architecture into components that can be developed in a conventional way and those where modules applying AI techniques and/or based on machine learning are deployed [83]. For example, the autonomy pipeline

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{sensing} \rightarrow \textit{perception} \rightarrow \textit{planning} \rightarrow \textit{prediction} \rightarrow \textit{control} \\ & \rightarrow \textit{actuation}, \end{aligned}$$

might apply AI-based methods in safety-critical perceptor modules, but otherwise only in uncritical components. If such a design paradigm can be enforced, the safety-critical part of the ‘planning → prediction → control → actuation’ sub-pipeline should be tested using complete methods, since they guarantee complete software correctness, equivalent to correctness proofs or software model checking.

Use
complete
testing for
safety-
critical
‘conventional’
modules

In Section 18 it is explained that at least for some classes of NN-based perceptors, a highly reliable estimate for the residual error of classification results can be obtained by means of statistical tests. Summarising, this means that safety-critical autonomous systems can be realised with sufficient reliability and, therefore, certified already today, if the restricted architectural paradigm described in Section 4.7 can be enforced.

Chapter 9

Fuzz Testing

9.1 The Fuzz Testing Technique

Fuzz testing is a random testing technique for software. Originating from the 1990s [140], it has become very popular in the last decade, due to its numerous success stories in the field of security testing. The basic idea of fuzz testing is to execute software components repeatedly with varying randomised inputs until a bug is discovered. Bug discovery is usually achieved by inserting property specifications like preconditions, postconditions, or invariants into the code, so that the program stops whenever such an assertion is violated. Therefore, fuzz testing is a typical **PBT** technique.

The most popular variant of fuzz testing today is **Coverage-Guided Greybox Fuzzing (CGF)**, where random inputs are more systematically mutated (typically by using genetic algorithms) in order to maximise the code coverage achieved during these software tests [30, 137]. Therefore, **CGF** may be considered as a specific variant of **adaptive random testing** [44]. The attractiveness of **CGF** is justified by the following facts.

Coverage-guided fuzzing

- **CGF** has impressive test strength in many application domains [175].
- **CGF** can also be applied to large and arbitrarily complex software packages, where model checkers would fail due to state explosion problems.

- **CGF** does not require complex reference models, just assertions that can be gradually enhanced during test campaigns.¹

From a practical perspective, the LibFuzzer [1] library integrated with the LLVM compiler (“clang”) is the most popular **CGF** variant suitable for use in an industrial context.

9.2 libFuzzer – Interface to the SUT

The libFuzzer requires a C-procedural interface to the SUT. Typically, this is realised as a wrapper calling the SUT provided via the fuzzer interface. The library expects the SUT to be reachable by means of a user-provided interface

libFuzzer
interface

```
1 int LLVMFuzzerTestOneInput(const uint8_t *Data, size_t Size) {
2   map Data to real inputs of the SUT;
3   call the SUT;
4   return 0;
5 }
```

If used for testing C⁺⁺ code, users need to provide an interface

```
1 extern "C" int LLVMFuzzerTestOneInput(const uint8_t *Data,
2                                       size_t Size) {
3   map Data to real inputs of the SUT;
4   call the SUT;
5   return 0;
6 }
```

Typically, this interface is provided by the test harness, so that the SUT code remains unchanged. When the LLVMFuzzerTestOneInput() function returns, the LLVM fuzzer calls the function again, but now with a new input data chunk Data with random contents and random length Size. This goes on until the function terminates (a conditional call to exit() can be made after the SUT has been called) or crashes anywhere in the SUT code, for example, due to a segmentation fault, due to an arithmetic exception, or due to a failed assertion².

Example 23. Suppose you wish to test the following function getMin()

¹In the most trivial case, no assertions are provided at all. Then the fuzz tests simply checks whether the software crashes for certain inputs.

²Recall that in C and C⁺⁺, logical checks can be inserted into code using the assert macro (see ASSERT(3) in the manual pages)

which is meant to return the smallest value in a buffer of integers. The length of the buffer (number of int-cells provided) is passed as the second parameter. For the boundary case where the buffer length is 0, we wish to return the maximum signed integer (just for the sake of this example).

```

1 #include <limits.h>
2 #include "mylib.h"
3
4 int getMin(const int* buffer, size_t numIntElements) {
5     if ( numIntElements == 0 ) return INT_MAX;
6     int idx;
7     int min = buffer[0];
8     for ( idx = 1; idx < numIntElements; idx++ ) {
9         if ( buffer[idx] < min ) min = buffer[idx];
10    }
11    return min;
12 }
```

Suppose further that this function resides in file `mylib.c`, and that the prototype is declared in header file `mylib.h`. To separate the test harness from the SUT, we create an additional file `testharness.c` where the fuzzer interface is implemented:

```

1 #include "mylib.h"
2
3 int LLVMFuzzerTestOneInput(const uint8_t *Data, size_t Size) {
4     size_t idx;
5     // Adapt data to SUT input format
6     const int *buffer = (const int*)Data;
7     size_t numIntElements = Size/sizeof(int);
8     // Call the SUT
9     int result = getMin(buffer, numIntElements);
10    return 0;
11 }
```

Here, the mapping from the byte-data buffer `Data` provided by the fuzzer to the int-buffer required by the SUT is straight forward: it just requires a cast to the int-datatype and a transformation of byte-length to int-length of the buffer. In other situations, the following more complex transformations will become necessary:

- Mapping of the `Data` buffer into the components of an input structure of the SUT.
- Padding the rest of a structure with default values if `Data` is shorter than the structure.

- Mapping of the Data buffer into several input parameters and global variables representing the SUT input interface.

Moreover, if the Data buffer is longer than the SUT input interface, one execution of `LLVMFuzzerTestOneInput()` should lead to *several* SUT calls, each call using a new portion of Data as input. \square

9.3 Fuzz Testing Against Complex Properties

It is not only possible to verify simple assertions like preconditions, postconditions, and invariants with CGF: for more complex properties, typically expressed by temporal logic formulae, these formulae can be transformed into **observer code**. An observer is an additional software checker that is called each time after the software under test has been activated by the fuzzer. Checking the effect of the actual software invocation in relation to the sequence of previous program states, the observer detects violations of the formula to be checked and signals an assertion failure.³

Observers
for LTL
formulae

Given an LTL property, the Büchi automaton accepting the LTL formula can be generated using the tool `ltl3ba` [19] which can present its results in the machine-readable **Hanoi Omega Automata (HOA)** format [20]. This enables the automated generation of an observer detecting violations of the specified formula.

Automated
observer
generation

9.4 Model-based Fuzz Testing

To guide or restrain the generation of random inputs during fuzz testing further, models can be used. For example, the grammar of a textual input language for a program to be tested can be used as a model that restricts the text strings that would otherwise be generated in a completely randomised

Models
restraining
the
random
input
generation

³An initial concept for this approach and an associated tool chain have been described in the technical report http://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_fuzzing.pdf

manner by the fuzzer, resulting mostly in meaningless robustness test data, since the probability to create strings adhering to a given grammar at random is very low [156].

Alternatively, behavioural models could be explored at random, following the **CGF** principle, but now applied to model coverage and not to code coverage. This approach has not been investigated in depth yet. It seems, however, quite promising for large behavioural models, where the generation of complete test suites would be infeasible.

[CGF on behavioural models](#)

Chapter 10

Testing Parameterised Systems

The behaviour of a parameterised system not only depends on the timed sequence of inputs, but also on environmental parameters (such as time of day or weather conditions) and configuration parameters (e.g. number of seat rows in the economy class of an aircraft, to be evaluated by the aircraft cabin controller). Parameters may be viewed as inputs to the system that only change slowly or not at all during a system execution.

Parameters
influencing
system
behaviour

Ultra complex systems that are specified by libraries of scenario models are typically parameterised systems. Each scenario model is associated with a tuple of parameters influencing the expected system behaviour in the respective scenario. Parameters are supposed to remain constant while the scenario is executed.

Parameterised
scenarios

Example 24. Consider a scenario model specifying how an autonomous road vehicle should behave when travelling along a highway route in different weather conditions: environment parameters like temperature, sun/rain/snow/fog influence the speed limit to be observed by the vehicle controller. Additionally, the speed limit is influenced by the vehicle-specific parameters ‘tyre equipment’ (e.g. summer/winter tyres) and ‘2-wheel drive’/‘4-wheel drive’). □

It is desirable to have test automation support available for identifying which parameter value combinations would be used in several test executions of the same scenario. If the scenario model is complete in the sense that the influence of all parameters on the expected system behaviour has

Identifying
relevant
parameter
combinations

been fully specified in the model, then the relevant parameter combinations can be determined automatically by means of the input equivalence testing methods discussed in Section 8.4. Again, this results in complete test suites in the sense of Section 8.3.

It may be the case, however, that there are so many parameters to be considered that the number of equivalence classes is too high to be tested in acceptable time and with reasonable effort. For these situations, non-exhaustive heuristics have to be applied [130]. One of the most effective heuristics for this purpose is *n-wise testing*, in particular, pairwise testing ($n = 2$).

N-wise testing is a software or configuration testing technique that focuses on systematically covering all possible combinations of values for n input or configuration parameters at a time. The core idea is based on empirical evidence showing that most software faults are triggered by interactions between a small number of inputs – typically two to six. In pairwise testing, all possible pairs of parameter values are tested. For higher values of n , the approach ensures that every possible n -way interaction is exercised at least once in the test suite.

N-wise testing is particularly effective in reducing the number of test cases needed compared to exhaustive testing, while still maintaining strong fault detection capability. It is often applied in domains with large configuration spaces or numerous input variables, such as embedded systems, configurable software, and safety-critical applications. Tools and algorithms for n -wise test generation (e.g. covering arrays or even orthogonal arrays [49]) aim to produce minimal yet thorough test sets that achieve full n -wise coverage.

Example 25. Consider a system of systems with collaborating robots and drones. There, it would not be advisable to limit the number of drones and robots that are allowed to cooperate. Alternatively, the limits would be so high (say, “*up to 50 drones and up to 10 robots*”), that already the possible start configurations could not be exhaustively tested. This assumption of limits, for example, would result in

$$2^{50} \cdot 2^{10} = 2^{60}$$

N-wise testing

Combinatorial test case explosion caused by configuration changes during runtime

initial configurations. Then, the number of potential changes to be performed during the mission would have to be considered. If an upper bound $c \in \mathbb{N}$ for the number of configuration changes per mission is assumed, this would result in

$$2^{60c}$$

test cases for an exhaustive check of configuration changes. For example, if $c = 5$ and the average time between configuration changes is 10 seconds, this would result in 2^{300} test steps requiring approximately 10^{83} years to be executed in the real world. The testing effort increases even further, when the duration between configuration changes plays a role. \square

The situation is different, when the influence of certain parameters on the system behaviour is not completely known, so that the dependencies cannot be explicitly modelled. Here, the model is still incomplete, and **exploratory testing** is required to investigate the relationships between parameters and actual system behaviour. This testing approach is applied in situations where it is still impossible to provide concise models of the expected system behaviour. Similar to physical experiments, exploratory tests require simultaneous learning, improvement or refinement of test design, model refinement, and test execution.¹ To the best of our knowledge, there does not exist yet a systematic approach to exploratory testing of autonomous, or, more general, ultra complex systems. There exist, however, specialised applications to test the effectiveness of machine learning in classification networks [219].

Exploratory
testing

¹see Cem Kaner's presentation <https://web.archive.org/web/20130612043734/http://www.kaner.com/pdfs/QAIExploring.pdf>

Chapter 11

Passive Testing and Runtime Testing

Passive testing is a general term for test methods that do not stimulate or influence the **SUT**, but only monitor the **SUT**'s behaviour. Thus, passive testing tools just execute test oracles, that is, checkers comparing the actual **SUT** behaviour to its expected behaviour and raise errors when discrepancies are detected. Passive testing

For avionic systems, for example, passive testing is continuously performed during flight by means of **BITE**, with the objective to detect subsystem or component errors early, so that hazardous situations can be avoided and post-flight maintenance be made more effective [3, 86]. BITE

The terms **runtime testing** or **runtime verification** are used for passive testers in software-based control systems [25]. Runtime testing is a very active research field; important research questions are: Runtime testing

- How can property specifications be effectively transformed into test oracles [25]?
- To what extent can past error-free executions provide statistical or empirical confidence in the correctness of future runs [36]?
- How can runtime monitors be designed to minimize performance overhead and avoid timing side effects [170]?

- Can runtime verification be combined with autonomous fault recovery or self-healing mechanisms [119]?

Chapter 12

Testing Multi-Agent Systems

To date, no complete testing theory exists for general, unrestricted **MAS**. This is primarily because such systems violate the fundamental assumptions—such as a bounded state space and finite input/output alphabets—that underlie most formal test theories [31]. These violations arise from several core characteristics of **MAS**:

- **Dynamic plan generation and exchange:** Agents in a **MAS** can generate new plans at runtime and communicate them to others. As a result, it is difficult to define a fixed, a priori specification of agent behavior that remains valid throughout system execution [215].
- **Concurrency and non-determinism:** Plans may execute concurrently across multiple agents. The resulting state interleavings – particularly when plans interact or contradict one another – are difficult to predict or enumerate, leading to a combinatorial explosion in possible execution paths [31].
- **Dynamic agent population:** Agents may join or leave the system dynamically. This causes the configuration – and hence the system’s state space – to evolve over time, rendering the state space effectively unbounded [66].

No complete theories for testing MAS

Recent work suggests that these challenges can be partially addressed through techniques such as runtime verification [22, 57], statistical testing,

or learning-based testing frameworks. However, comprehensive and scalable solutions for MAS testing remain an active area of research [148, 218]. As shown, for example, in [150], it is possible to formalise MAS in specific domains. Also, it is shown there how formal testing theories can be elaborated for MAS in such domains. However, the results presented in [150] do not cover the exchange of plans between agents or the run-time construction of new plans to solve new problems.

Chapter 13

The Impact of Learning Techniques on Complete Testing Theories

Machine learning ([ML](#)) can be applied to

- support/improve/facilitate the testing process of an [SUT](#), or
- create sub-components of a target system replacing manual programming with training a neural network that determines the sub-component's behaviour.

Somewhat surprisingly, the first application of [ML](#) leads to testing theories that are provably complete (Section [13.1](#)). The second type of application, however, complicates the [V&V](#) process, as will be explained in Section [13.2](#).

13.1 Black-Box and Grey-Box Checking

Black-Box and Grey-Box Checking are applied to the verification of software components.

Black-box checking combines testing with machine learning and model checking [[157](#)]: tests are applied to learn a finite state machine (FSM) model of the SW module's *true* behaviour. Then model checking is

[Black-box checking](#)

applied on this model to verify whether the desired module properties are fulfilled. In contrast to model-based testing, where test engineers need to create comprehensive models of the *expected* module behaviour, the black-box checking approach is more attractive, since users only need to specify properties to be checked against the module's behavioural model which has been learnt automatically.

The original seminal paper of Peled et al. [157], however, emphasised the feasibility of the approach and less its suitability in practice: The restriction to learning FSMs makes it only suitable for software modules with small interface types, like enumerations with few values. Moreover, the application of complete testing methods to decide on the termination of the learning process has not been optimised. As a result, the black-box checking method as published by Peled et al. [157] is only practically applicable to SW modules with low complexity: small interfaces and few internal states.

These deficiencies have been investigated and significantly improved by Brüning et al. [34, 35]. (a) Instead of FSMs, **symbolic finite state machines (SFSM)** with interface types of arbitrary size, guard conditions controlling the processing steps, and arithmetic output expressions are learnt. (b) An equivalence class calculation principle has been elaborated that allows to abstract the – conceptually infinite – interface type sizes to finitely many equivalence classes, with only a single representative per class, preserving the full fault coverage guaranteed by the original method. (c) An initial fuzz testing [1] phase has been added to the learning process. This is exploited to distinguish as many internal module states as possible. This reduces the number of test cases needed in the initial checks for model completeness in a considerable way. (d) The learning and testing algorithms have been replaced by the latest, most efficient variants available today. (e) Runtime monitors are applied to detect the violation of safety properties, even before a model checking procedure is executed. (f) Performing some fairly simple static analyses of the code for deciding on an upper bound for the number of possibly distinct internal module states, extracting branching conditions, and identifying output expressions is sufficient to conclude that passing the test and model checking phases results

Grey-box
checking

in a comprehensive *proof* that a module satisfies the specified properties.

Since this improved module verification procedure involves static analyses of the code, we call it **grey-box checking**. Compared to the original black-box checking method [157], grey-box checking significantly improves applicability to software modules with real-world complexity [34].

13.2 ML in Target System Development, Testability, and Explainable AI

Despite the success of **ML**-based applications, their use in safety-critical contexts is still a challenge for **V&V** and certification:

V&V
challenges
for
ML-based
applications

- In many **ML**-based applications, such as, for example, **CNN** for image classification, the (usually very large) input space cannot be formally partitioned into subsets representing well-defined objects of the Operational Design Domain (**ODD**) in a simple way – these applications are ultra-complex systems in the sense of our definition on page 13.
- Trained **NN** models cannot be easily analysed with respect to causal dependencies between inputs, intermediate layers, and outputs, because the effects of inter-neurone and inter-layer connections, and the effects of weights calibrated during the training phase cannot be intuitively understood by humans.
- Applications using **ML** continuously during their operational phase¹ cannot be certified once-and-for-all before entry into service, since their behaviour may change significantly during operation, due to these learning effects. The continuous **ML** process during operation induces new risks, since adversarial attacks may try to change the behaviour to the worse instead of improving it. Moreover, the learn-

¹For example, to optimise their behaviour with respect to changing conditions in the operational environment.

ing process can introduce new **AI-hallucinations**² that impair the overall system safety.

These considerations have stimulated numerous research activities in the last decade; the commonly used term and abbreviation for these activities is **XAI** [52]: Today, many **ML**-based applications can provide reasons for the outputs (such as image classification results) they produce. Plausible explanations increase the trust in the trained application. Explainable
AI

ML-based applications can be verified and validated with different types of approaches. To impose a structure on the latter, we suggest the following attributes. A
structure
for known
V&V
approaches

1. Model considerations

- **Model-agnostic (black box)**. The **V&V** method does not require the analysis of the internal model (e.g. the **CNN**) obtained during the **ML** training phase.
- **Model-aware (grey box/white box)**. The **V&V** method takes the structure and the parameter values of the trained model into account.

2. Statistical vs. non-random tests vs. formal specification and verification

- **Statistical tests** operate on samples of the input space, check the associated outputs and estimate stochastic parameters (mean values, failure probabilities etc.) to be true for the *whole* input space with a certain confidence.
- **Non-random tests** operate on samples of the input space and ensure fault coverage by means of coverage criteria (structural coverage, equivalence class coverage etc.).
- **Formal specification and verification** is based on formal logical relationships between the *whole* input space and the associ-

²An AI hallucination is when an AI generates false or fabricated information that appears plausible but is not based on real data.

ated expected outputs. Then it is proven that these relationships are respected by the system to be verified.

By their very nature, statistical tests do not aim at completeness, but only at “*low error probabilities determined with high confidence*”. Complete non-random test theories can only be applied if a formal relationship between inputs and expected outputs can be constructed. This is possible, for example, for NNs implementing physical control algorithms, but impossible for CNNs used for image classification. Obviously, formal verification can only be applied if this formal relationship between inputs and expected outputs can be comprehensively specified.

In the subsequent sections until the end of this chapter, different V&V approaches covering all the attribute values discussed above will be referenced.

Part IV
Verification & Validation

Chapter 14

V&V for Safety Controllers

14.1 V&V Challenges

It is an accepted engineering practice to encapsulate the safety-critical supervision and control functions of a cyber-physical system in dedicated safety controllers that are strictly separated from processors or computers processing non-critical applications. Today's standards for "conventional" safety-critical systems [40, 206, 206] require that the V&V of safety controllers shall be performed and completed once-and-for all as a prerequisite to entry into service.

This, however, is no longer possible if systems

1. applications change their safety-relevant behaviour over time, or
2. the safety controller depends on sub-systems (e.g. smart sensors) applying machine learning during operation (so-called **post-deployment learning**) to optimise their effectiveness, or
3. the safety controller itself applies machine learning to improve its supervision and control functions.

When V&V cannot be completed before entry into service

In cases 2 and 3, the software of safety controllers is even "uncertifiable" according to the conventional standards: Since the software depends on machine learning (e.g. learning the weights of neural networks) in these two cases, its behaviour will only be adequate *with a certain probability*

in most cases.¹ This contradicts the requirements of the a.m. standards that the existence of residual software errors can be neglected since the verification phase was sufficiently thorough.

The new standards for the V&V of autonomous systems [104, 199], however, take the cases 2 and 3 into account and suggest suitable V&V methods for obtaining certification credit. Today, however, these novel standards are not yet applied in practice in Europe. Therefore, safety controllers are currently developed according to the following guidelines that try to keep the design of safety controllers as close as possible to the conventional approaches allowing for V&V according to the conventional standards.

New standards for V&V not yet applied in Europe

14.2 Safety controllers that do not depend on machine learning

In the simplest case, only applications that cannot affect safety apply machine learning, so that safety controllers – including their sub-systems – can be designed, verified, and validated in a completely conventional way. An example for this approach are ATO and ATP for trains with human train engine drivers [162]: A safety controller implements ATP by checking that the train never goes too fast and respects the boundaries of its current movement authority. In contrast to that, the ATO only contains non-critical functions. For example, an ATO function can apply ML for optimising the train’s energy consumption. This may lead to acceleration requests for the train. These, however, are routed through ATP and therefore only implemented if compatible with the current bounds of velocity and movement authority. The ATP functions can be verified according to [40].

ML only in non-critical applications

¹Note that there are some machine learning methods that can produce results (i.e. models) that are completely correct. An example is learning the state machine behaviour of a control algorithm discussed above in the context of grey-box checking (Section 13.1). The majority of ML methods, however – in particular those resulting in neural networks – only produce models that are approximations of the true model.

14.3 Safety controllers with sub-systems depending on machine learning

In the second case, where the safety controller depends on ML-based sub-systems, two scenarios arise:

- The ML phase is finished before entry into service (pre-deployment learning).
- ML is continuously applied after entry into service (post-deployment adaptation).

Pre-deployment learning and post-deployment adaptation by ML

The safety controller itself can be designed and validated with conventional means, but it depends on a sub-system implemented with the help of ML.

The first variant of ML application should be verified and validated by showing *before* entry into service that the residual error probability of the sub-system is acceptable for the tolerable hazard rate of the safety controller. V&V needs to be based on the novel standards [104, 199] since the software of the sub-system will behave correctly only with a certain probability, so that also the safety controller is associated with a residual risk for failing to ensure the safety of the intended functionality.

Sub-systems whose residual error probability is too high can be fused with redundant components using diverse technologies, so that they can be expected to fail in a stochastically independent way. Gleirscher et. al. [77], for example, have elaborated this approach for the case of a sensor fusion performing obstacle detection for GoA-4 freight trains: It can be shown that by combining stochastically independent obstacle detection sensors of different type the tolerable hazard rate of Safety Integrity Level (SIL)-3 can be assured.

Sensor fusion

For the second variant, it needs to be checked continuously during operation that ML has no ill effects on the sub-system behaviour: It has to be emphasised that continuous ML does not guarantee that the sub-system behaviour will always change for the better.² For these cases, online V&V is required to ensure that continuous learning won't impair safety.

²A striking example for this fact is the recent observation of new "improved" large language models actually *increased* the number of AI-hallucinations [139].

A promising approach for this V&V approach is to utilise **digital twins** [62, Chapters 2, 14, 15]:

- A digital twin resides in a cloud server farm, continuously processing the same inputs as the “real-world” safety controller.
- Continuous ML is only applied by the digital twin, with the objective to prepare for a new model revision (e.g. a set of new weights for a neural network implementing the sub-component behaviour).
- When a new – presumably better – model version has been prepared in the cloud a validation is performed, also in the cloud.
- Only if the validation is passed, the new model is downloaded into the sub-system of the real-world safety controller.

Post-deployment adaptation in digital twins

Note that this approach does not really result in *continuous* changes of behaviour in the real-world safety controller: Continuous ML is only performed in the cloud, while the real-world safety controller gets a new model revision only after it has been validated.

An example for this situation could be an autonomous freight train, where the ATP system is still conventionally designed, but depends on a sub-system detecting obstacles on the track [162]. Suppose that this sub-system has been trained to detect obstacles by means of a neural network interpreting camera images. Suppose further that before entry into service, it has been shown³ that the NN has an acceptable residual error probability. Suppose further that the NN should be improved by ML during operation. To this end, the digital twin would process the same images as the real-world safety controller⁴, but also apply them to fine-tune the weights of the NN currently used even further. When a new NN model results from the fine tuning process that is expected to be better (fewer false positives, fewer false negatives than the predecessor model), the new model is validated in the cloud, using the test method described in Section 18. When failing the

Example: autonomous freight train

³for example by using the V&V methods for CNNs described in Peleska et al. [163].

⁴It could even process additional images processed by other trains to increase the learning effect (so-called **distributed federated learning** [53]).

test, the new model is discarded. Only when passing the test, the improved model is downloaded into the safety controller's sub-system.

14.4 Safety controllers applying machine learning

In the most challenging case, the behaviour of the safety controller itself is based on ML (case 3 listed above). As in case 2, it has to be distinguished whether ML is only applied for controller software construction before entry into service, or whether ML is continuously applied during operation to optimise the controller's behaviour.

Pre-deployment ML and post-deployment adaptation by ML applied in the safety controller

Note that the application of ML for safety controllers is quite attractive in principle, though – to the best of our knowledge – such controllers are currently not applied for safety-critical systems, due to the V&V challenges discussed below. These main benefits from ML are:

1. ML could help to create complex state machine behaviour that would be very hard to design in a manual way [6].
2. ML applied during operation could help to continuously improve the reactive controller capabilities in critical situations, learning from the outcomes of previous reactions to hazardous events. This possibility is particularly attractive if distributed federated learning can be applied for safety controllers operating in fleets (e.g. all autonomous freight trains or all autonomous road vehicles of similar type): The continuous ML process can be performed in the cloud, so that the hazardous events experienced by *any* fleet member can be taken into account.

Potential benefits from ML

Despite these potential benefits, safety controllers derived from ML processes are not admissible in Europe, at least not for SIL-4 systems: Since their monitoring and control tasks are generally far more complex than those of their sub-systems (such as smart sensors, see case 2), it will be much harder to determine the risk of controller malfunction in a reliable way. Moreover, the definition of trustworthy tests for measuring this risk

Complexity issues preventing ML application for safety controllers

is usually considerably harder than for sub-components performing simpler tasks that are easy to specify precisely.

There are, however, specific variants of controller design by ML where trustworthy V&V is possible, even if safety control tasks are complex:

1. If a safety controller performs control tasks that require the solution of complex differential equations, their explicit manual design can be replaced by training recurrent neural networks (Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)). These can be verified with high precision [118, 216]. The verification of RNN is an active research field.
2. It is even possible to perform online learning (again, possibly in a digital twin in the cloud) to further improve an operative RNN [204].

When ML for controller design can be recommended

14.5 Safety controller synthesis

An alternative approach to safety controller development avoids ML. Instead, it aims at synthesising safety controller code from world models specifying the potential hazards the controller should protect the system against. Using stochastic model checking, it can be verified whether the residual risk for a hazard to lead to an accident in presence of the synthesised controller is acceptably low [72, 76].

Chapter 15

Tool Support for Probabilistic Model Checking

As discussed extensively in this report, some system components in ultra-complex, potentially autonomous systems fulfill their intended functionality only with a certain probability. This has long been recognized for hardware, but it also applies to software components in these systems. Moreover, operational environments are always subject to probabilistic events; this applies not only to the occurrence of hazards, but also to the behaviour of humans interacting with the system.

The methodology for a probabilistic approach to the risk assessment of safety-critical systems typically uses Markov chains or Markov decision processes as models (see Section 5.3 and Section 5.11). The most popular tool supporting probabilistic model checking is PRISM [132]. Based on Markov models, it enables the calculation of the probabilities of traces that lead to hazards and ultimately to accidents within a given world model.

Probabilistic
component
behaviour
–
probabilistic
events in
the
environment

PRISM

Chapter 16

Automated Theorem Proving

While tool-supported model-based testing and model checking have become increasingly accepted verification technologies for the industrial verification of safety-critical systems, tool-based proof assistants are mainly used in academia today. We expect that this will change in the near future for several reasons.

1. Proof assistants have become much easier to use in recent years, and they are able to perform quite complex chains of reasoning in a fully automated way.
2. In the fields of collaborative robotics and systems of systems in general, the dynamic changes in system configurations typically result in combinatorial explosions when trying to perform model checking with a realistic upper bound for the configurations that could occur during operation.

Model checking fails for changing system configurations

Sachtleben et al. [180], for example, have demonstrated the feasibility of mechanised formal verification for railway interlocking systems controlling rail networks of arbitrary size, with changing configurations of trains traversing the network. This would be impossible for model checking approaches. The scalability of theorem proving here stems from its ability to handle universally quantified properties without dependence on set cardinality. In contrast, model checking typically requires explicit or symbolic traversal of set elements, tying complexity directly to their size.

Chapter 17

V&V for RNN Used for System Control

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are typically used for complex control tasks, natural language processing, or time-series prediction [4, Section 1.6.4]. They perform classifications of variable-length sequences. Typically, they have a prohibitively large or even infinite state space, and their expressive power is greater than that of a **Deterministic finite automaton (DFA)**. Applied to control tasks, the **transition function**

Neural networks for control tasks

$$f : \mathbb{R}^k \times \Sigma \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$$

of an RNN processes inputs from Σ and performs associated state changes, depending on both the actual state which is a vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^k$ and the input $a \in \Sigma$.

Just as with **NN** used for image classification (e.g. CNNs), we have the problem that the interpretation of the state space and the variables and weights occurring in the implementation of f cannot be traced back to the problem domain. However, the application to (safety-critical) control problems allows for a rigorous **V&V** approach, due to the following reasons.

1. The state space \mathbb{R}^k can be associated with an abstraction function

$$g : \mathbb{R}^k \longrightarrow D$$

Rigorous V&V for RNN

mapping sets of states to (finitely many) values of the problem domain D .

2. The safety-related properties of the RNN may be specified by means of LTL formulas [47] *in the terms of the problem domain*. For safety formulas, these may be represented by a DFA A [21]¹.
3. Using random input sequences $\sigma \in \Sigma^*$ and applying f successively to these inputs and associated state changes, a DFA H *approximating* the true behaviour of the RNN can be learned, using well-known techniques from automata learning [9].
4. If the language of H is not contained in A , either
 - (a) an error in the RNN has been found, or
 - (b) the approximation H of the RNN is still too coarse.

In the first case, the RNN needs to be fixed. In the second case, standard techniques for refining H can be applied, so that it approximates the true behaviour of the RNN in a more precise way.

5. With a given hypothesis about the distribution of input data, the remaining probability that the RNN may show behaviours differing from the approximation H can be estimated.

This concept has been proposed and elaborated in more detail in [124, 134]. It allows us to *prove by testing and refining approximations* that the RNN fulfils its required control property A *with a certain probability*. In the terms for the classification of V&V methods introduced above, it is a hybrid V&V approach using statistical tests and formal specifications.

Just as in applications of **neural networks** for image recognition, it has to be justified that the selected input data sequences have a distribution that is representative for the “real distributions to be encountered in the wild”. This task, however, is easier to solve in the case of control applications than in the case of image recognition: for control applications, the alphabet Σ is

¹For liveness formulas, a Büchi automaton would be necessary to encode the formula, and this would lead to a considerably more complex learning process than the one presented in [9]. However, liveness formulas are hardly ever used in a safety-related real-time context. In particular, they can always be transformed into a more precise safety formula involving timing conditions.

specified in the terms of the application domain, so that the probabilities for the occurrence of an input value can be easier validated.

Chapter 18

V&V for DNNs Used for Image Classification

18.1 V&V Challenges

In contrast to RNNs used for control applications as discussed in Section 17, the use of deep **neural networks** (DNN), in particular, **CNN**, for image classification poses a significantly harder **V&V** challenge, with critical open problems. The validation of trained **NN** is a focal point of research on autonomous systems and **AI** in general [185]. Typical safety-critical applications are perceptors in the autonomy pipeline, such as camera-based traffic sign recognition for road vehicles and obstacle recognition functions used for collision avoidance in autonomous road vehicles, trains, drones, and future aircrafts (e.g. for **ATTOL**).

Trained **DNN** for image recognition are a typical instance of ultra-high application complexity, as discussed in Section 2.7.3 (see also Example 11): as of today, there exists no logical approach to *proving* that a trained **DNN** will classify a non-zero percentage of images from arbitrary instances of the respective classes occurring in the real world correctly. The main cause for this problem is that there exists no method for identifying all possible pixel matrixes of a camera image representing a real class instance.

Consequently, the performance¹ of a trained **DNN** for image classifica-

¹This term is used in the sense of the standards ANSI/UL 4600 and ISO 21448 [104,

tion can only be assessed by means of a stochastic testing approach. This means that **statistical tests** need to be applied to show with a certain confidence that the probability for misclassifications is less or equal to an acceptable residual probability $p > 0$. The conventional verification of the software implementing the **DNN** is only able to check whether the graph of the **DNN** with its layers, neurones, weighted connections, and activation function is correctly represented. The emerging functionality, however, not only depends on this implementation correctness, but on the selection of training samples affecting the final weight assignments.

The elaboration of trustworthy statistical tests estimating the residual error probability of a trained **DNN** is still an open research problem, currently investigated by many research groups worldwide. This research challenge is so important, because such a statistical test would yield an **end-of-test criterion** for the trained **DNN**: the performance of the **DNN** can be considered as adequate, as soon as the tests assert a sufficiently small error probability with sufficiently high confidence.

When deciding about PASS/FAIL outcomes of classification results during these statistical tests, it does not suffice to provide experimental evidence that – after having completed the learning phase – only a very small percentage of misclassifications have occurred [192]. Indeed, it is also necessary to provide evidence that correct classifications were all based on *the correct reasons* and not based on misconceptions learned during the **training** phase that accidentally led to correct classifications because of the **training** samples used.

Recall that for image recognition, the distribution of pixel values to be chosen for **training** pictures is much harder to validate since small changes in the pixel matrix may seem insignificant to the human eye, but may change the classification result [84]. This phenomenon is called **brittleness** in classification **NN**. With the knowledge about the intrinsics of the **DNN** used and the neural network **training** applied, image alterations (so-called **adversarial examples**) can be carefully crafted to induce misclassifications. Some of these alterations, however, can also occur accidentally, for example, due to specific whether and light conditions. Therefore, even in absence of

[199]: the **performance** of a function is its effectiveness for its intended functionality.

malicious agents producing adversarial images, it cannot be neglected that brittle **DNN** might produce safety-critical misclassifications.

Expressing the problem of brittleness more formally, we observe that the classification function performed by the **DNN** is **not continuous** from the perspective of a suitable topology (or metric) to be applied to the application domain: a change of a pixel matrix which is considered small from the perspective of the application domain can lead to a jump (i.e. a misclassification) in the function value.

There has been extensive research on **description logics** [51, 147] that are suitable to express and reason about image information. This does *not* help, however, to prove that a **DNN** classifies a pixel matrix in the correct way, since description logics refer to abstracted image contents only, and not to the low-level information on which these abstractions are based.

As outlined in [84], one of the main reasons that trained **DNN** may become so brittle is that their training just “tweaks parameters” without introducing understanding about the classified objects. A misclassification discussed in [192], for example, concerns a neural network correctly identifying a hat, because there is a human face underneath. This classification result is considered to be a failure, since it indicates that hats that are not placed on human heads might not be correctly detected by this **DNN**. These observations suggest to use *hybrid AI models that combine ML-based AI with symbolic AI*. Symbolic AI uses and reasons with rules about the world and its objects, as well as the relations between them.

18.2 Test Objectives

In the light of the discussion in Section 18, the applicable standards for autonomous safety-critical systems, such as ANSI/UL 4600 and ISO 21448 do not define any end-of-test criteria for neural networks used for image classification. They do, however, list a set of qualitative criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of a trained **DNN**.

1. A quantitative metric indicating the performance of the trained **CNN** needs to be defined, and its application with the associated PASS/-

Qualitative
V&V
criteria
imposed
by
standards

FAIL criteria has to be justified [199, 8.5.2.2]. This includes the determination and justification of an acceptable residual risk level [104, D.2.4].

2. A correct classification result can only be accepted during V&V if it has been obtained by the DNN for the correct reasons [104, D.2.4].
3. The tests need to cover the full ontology of objects specified for the ODD. This should be checked by mapping the classification result to an element of an object ontology created for the objects to be classified [199, 8.5.3.2, 8.5.3.3, 8.5.3.4].²
4. The ontology needs to be sufficiently detailed to cover the distinctions made by the trained DNN, which may be more fine-grained than the distinctions made by humans [199, 8.4.2.4].
5. Tests need to show that no overfitting has occurred during the training phase [199, 8.5.2.2].
6. Tests need to show the absence of brittleness in the trained DNN [199, 8.5.3.2].
7. The V&V data set has to include a sufficient number of objects whose misclassification could result in a high-severity accident, even if their occurrence probability in the ODD is low [199, 8.5.3.2].

Quantitative metrics. Typical metrics to satisfy Item 1 are false positive and false negative rate, precision/recall, and ROC curves (see Appendix B). Alternatively, the ISO 21448 emphasises the suitability of statistical parameters (such as the mean value and variance of the misclassification probability, together with upper confidence limits). There exist, however, currently no concrete boundaries for acceptable values of these statistical parameters. Moreover, trustworthy statistical test procedures have been discussed in the research communities, but they have not been consistently defined

²This also provides evidence whether the classification result has been obtained for the correct reasons.

and approved by the applicable standards until today. We will therefore discuss these open questions in more detail in Section 18.4.

Determining reasons for classification results. Item 2 has been extensively researched in the recent past, under the general notion of XAI [181]. Based on causal theory, Chockler et al. [45, 192] provide explanations for classification results; an explanation is a minimal subset of super pixels (a group of neighbouring pixels) “causing” the classification result for an image v . The super pixels may be located in different regions of the image, so that the cause is given by a collection of different image parts that are jointly responsible for the classification result. The authors’ approach is based on the following definition of cause:

Determining
reasons:
XAI

An image pixel (or a super pixel) p_i is a **cause for classification result** o if and only if there exists a subset P_j of pixels satisfying

A
definition
of cause

- $p_i \notin P_j$
- Changing the colour of any subset $P'_j \subseteq P_j$ to the background colour does *not* change the classification result.
- Changing the colour of all pixels in $\{p_i\} \cup P_j$ to the background color changes the classification result.

The responsibility of p_i for the classification result o is then defined by

$$r(p_i, v, o) = \frac{1}{(k + 1)},$$

where v is the image containing (super) pixel p_i , o is the classification result, and k is the size of the smallest pixel subset P_j showing that p_i is a cause for the classification result. The responsibility of p_i has maximal value 1 if the smallest P_j is empty. This means that p_i *alone* can cause the classification result.³ Conversely, if p_i causes o only *in combination* with other (super) pixels p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k , the responsibility of p_i becomes smaller,

³Note that even then, other pixels can also cause the classification result, so a pixel with responsibility 1 does not imply the absence of further causes for the classification result.

since a set P containing at least p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k is required to show that p_i is a cause.

Figure 18.1: A classification result ‘car’ obtained by correct reasons.

Ribeiro et al. [171] provide explanations by approximating the “true” CNN behaviour locally (i.e. on some parts of the image) with an interpretable model. Both approaches are **model agnostic** in the sense that they produce explanations without knowledge about the internal structure of the trained CNN. Zeiler et al. [217] map the feature activations performed by a CNN back into the input pixel space, thereby identifying the “essence” of the original image that was responsible for the classification result. The Google Vision AI⁴ provides a list of features with percentage values expression confidence. The high-confidence features represent the reason for the classification result (see Fig. 18.1).

These XAI approaches also help to ensure the V&V criteria listed in Item 3 and Item 4 above, because the indicated reasons should be directly mappable to the ontology. If this is not the case though the classification result is correct and well-justified, this indicates that the ontology is not sufficiently fine-grained. In Fig. 18.2, for example, the feature ‘Automotive Parking Light’ was essential for the classification result ‘car’. This feature might be missing in the ontology detailing the features of cars in the ODD, since it seems less significant from the human perspective.

⁴<https://cloud.google.com/vision>

Figure 18.2: A classification result ‘car’ has a determining feature ‘Automotive Parking Light’.

Detecting overfitting. Recall that **overfitting** refers to the effect that some trained **CNN** may perform excellently on the training data set but fail frequently for other inputs that are not contained in the training data. Overfitting is usually the result of training sets containing too few samples in comparison to the number of parameters available in the **CNN** [4, 1.4.1,4], [182]. The absence of overfitting is verified by means of large verification sets that have no or only very small overlap with the training set. More detailed approaches for avoiding and detecting overfitting are presented in the references above.

Overfitting

However, the suitability of the verification set needs to be justified as well: it has to be shown that the verification set does not contain only images associated with the same **classification cluster**⁵, or a very small number thereof. If this were the case, the large size of the verification set

⁵A **classification cluster** is a set of image frames representing objects of the same type, that are classified by the **CNN** *for the same reasons*, that is, the discriminant function achieves its classification result from the same label values, and from equivalent image portions. The term has been introduced by the standard ANSI/UL 4600 [199]. Classification clusters correspond loosely to the concept of **input equivalence classes** applied in software and systems testing.

would not be significant, since it does not cover all variants of decision making leading to a classification result.

Again, the XAI methods described above help to justify the effectiveness of the verification set: the set needs to cover the full ontology of the objects to be classified, and this is checked again by mapping the classification reasons obtained from the CNN to the ontology.

Detecting brittleness. Kroening et al. [190, 191] have designed and implemented a model-aware grey-box testing method and associated tool support for covering the structure of a DNN according to various coverage criteria. Their tool *DeepConcolic* is effective for detecting adversarial examples of image classifications indicating brittleness of trained CNN: a pair of images represent an adversarial example if one is classified correctly, while the other gets an erroneous classification though it is “close” to the first image in a norm (L^p norm) that adequately reflects our human understanding of closeness. The absence of brittleness is verified by testing that no adversarial examples can be found though the CNN structure has been extensively covered, so the coverage achieved yields an end-of-test criterion for testing for the absence of brittleness. Though this does not correspond to a full proof of non-brittleness (which is impossible according to the current state of the art), the coverage argument is similar to the code coverage-related arguments admissible according to standards like RTCA DO-178C and EN50128 [40, 206] for the verification of conventional software.

Detecting
brittleness

Augmenting the verification set. Meeting the V&V requirements discussed above obviously requires large verification data sets. Apart from the necessity to obtain large libraries of real-world images taken from the ODD, it is advisable to increase the data set by mutating existing images, simulating, for example, different weather or lighting conditions, or by creating adversarial images. The method to increase training or verification data sets by adding mutated versions of existing data is called data aug-

Data
augmentation

mentation [4, 8.3.4].⁶ An effective method to generate such images is to apply Generative adversarial network (GAN) [78].

18.3 Data Set Partitioning for Training and V&V

The performance of a trained CNN for image classification is reflected by its capability to generalise: this is the ability to perform correct classifications on image data *outside* the training data set. To ensure proper generalisation capabilities, there is a general agreement that image data sets should be carefully partitioned into three disjoint sets as follows [4, 104, 199].

Training data set. This set of image samples is used to train the CNN.

Validation data set. This set of image samples is used to validate the effectiveness of the training performed so far. The CNN performance on the validation data set may give rise to improvements of the underlying model structure and enhancements of the training process.

Verification data set. This set of image samples is used to check whether the *completely trained* CNN has acceptable performance.

Whereas the verification data set must always be disjoint from both training and validation data sets, there are methods to optimise the CNN performance by systematically exchanging samples between training and validation data sets. The **cross validation** method uses a joint pool P of image samples for training and validation, and partitions this pool in multiple different ways

$$P = T_i \cup V_i, T_i \cap V_i = \emptyset, i = 1, \dots, k$$

into different training data sets T_i and verification data sets V_i . Then the training result T_j that has the best generalisation capabilities with respect to validation data V_j is used as the final trained CNN instance [4, 4.3.1].

⁶During the training phase of an CNN, data augmentation is also regarded as an appropriate means to avoid overfitting.

18.3.1 Input Equivalence Classes in Classification CNN

Consider a **CNN** for image classification with finitely many image classification types $t \in T = \{t_0, \dots, t_k\}$. For our running example of a **CNN** for obstacle detection on a railroad track, a binary classification **CNN** with

$$T = \{t_0, t_1\}, \quad t_0 = \text{no obstacle detected}, \quad t_1 = \text{obstacle detected}$$

would suffice.

Let $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots\}$ denote the finite (though very large) space of image frames to be classified. Let $f : \mathcal{V} \rightarrow T$ denote the unknown image classification function corresponding to the trained **CNN**. Then \mathcal{V} can be partitioned into $|T| = k$ finite **input equivalence classes** $E_0, \dots, E_k \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, such that all elements v in each class E_t , $t = 0, \dots, k$ are classified as $f(v) = t$. More formally, the equivalence classes fulfil the standard rules inducing an equivalence relation $\sim \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ on \mathcal{V} :

Image
classification
function

$$\bigcup_{t=0}^k E_t = \mathcal{V} \quad (18.1)$$

$$\forall i, j \in \{0, \dots, k\} \quad \cdot \quad E_i \cap E_j = \emptyset \quad (18.2)$$

$$\forall t \in \{0, \dots, k\}, v \in E_t \quad \cdot \quad f(v) = t \quad (18.3)$$

$$v \sim v' \equiv \exists t \in T. v \in E_t \wedge v' \in E_t \quad (18.4)$$

Equivalence
classes

Benfenati and Marta [26, 27] have developed a theory about how to determine or at least approximate equivalence classes with a model-aware approach. They consider an arbitrary **DNN** as a sequence

$$M_0 \xrightarrow{\Lambda_1} M_1 \xrightarrow{\Lambda_2} M_2 \xrightarrow{\Lambda_3} \dots \xrightarrow{\Lambda_{n-1}} M_{n-1} \xrightarrow{\Lambda_n} M_n,$$

DNN
represented
by sequences
of manifolds
and smooth
mappings

where the spaces M_i are differentiable manifolds represented as subsets of \mathbb{R}^{n_i} , and the Λ_i are smooth mappings between these manifolds.

For an image classification task, M_0 would have a very large dimension: a discrete pixel matrix of dimension $224 \times 224 \times 3$, for example, could be represented by

$$M_0 = ([0, 255] \times [0, 255] \times [0, 255])^{224 \times 224},$$

where a triple $(r, g, b) \in ([0, 255] \times [0, 255] \times [0, 255])$ represents an RGB value, and 224×224 pixels each have to be associated with such a triple.

The last manifold M_n would be an interval of \mathbb{R} , representing the classification values or classification probabilities. The intermediate manifolds represent the internal layers of the **CNN**.

If we use the “ordinary” Euclidean metric g^n on $M_n \subset \mathbb{R}$, then a singular Riemannian metric

$$g^0 = (\Lambda_n \circ \dots \circ \lambda_1)^*(g^n)$$

is introduced on M_0 by means of the pullback operation induced by the mappings Λ_i . This metric is singular in the sense that different points $v_1 \neq v_2 \in M_0$ may have zero distance from each other according to g^0 . This is because the last manifold M_n only has dimension 1, while the other manifolds have higher dimensions. Given a point (an image frame) $v \in M_0$, all points $v' \in M_0$ with distance zero from v are classified with the same value as v .

For a given type of **DNN**, the metric g^0 calculated via the pullback mechanism leads to an *exact* representation of equivalence classes, if all sub-functions used in the **DNN** layer are smooth. This means, in particular, that

- only smooth activation functions are used, and
- pooling uses smooth functions.

For example, *softplus* activation functions could be used, and pooling could be performed by means of the average function [4]. This would lead to smooth inter-layer mappings Λ_i .

For typical **CNN**, however, the Rectified Linear Unit (**ReLU**) activation function is used which is not differentiable at zero and would have to be approximated by the smooth *softplus* function. For pooling, the maximum function $\max(x_1, \dots, x_\ell)$ is used which is not differentiable on the hyperplanes $x_{i_1} = x_{i_2} = \dots = x_{i_m}$. To obtain smooth mappings Λ_i between manifolds, the maximum function has to be approximated by a *softmax* function [4].

Observe that the correct and complete identification of input equiva-

Singular
Riemannian
metric on M_0

Approximation
of classes
for typical
CNN

Knowledge
of classes
is not
enough to
verify
SOTIF

lence classes for a trained CNN does *not* suffice to ensure SOTIF: for this objective, it has to be ensured that all image frames v contained in class E_t are really classified correctly by type t . In the terms of manifolds and metrics introduced above, SOTIF is ensured if

for every correctly classified class representative $v \in E_t$, all image frames v' reachable from v on a curve of length zero are correctly classified by type t .

18.4 Statistical Tests to Ensure SOTIF

Item 1 of the list of verification objectives discussed on page 179 in the previous section states that a quantitative assessment of the CNN performance is necessary for obtaining certification credit of a classification CNN performing safety-critical tasks. The main objective of this assessment is of course the determination of the SOTIF which could be measured, for example by the false negative rate or the recall of the verification suite performed. Subordinate test objectives are to determine the false positive rate or the precision of the verification suite – these metrics are related to availability (see Appendix B).

Quantitative
assessment
of CNN
performance

As discussed in Section 18, the SOTIF of a classification CNN cannot be formally proven, but must be assessed by means of statistical tests, because they can provide end-of-test criteria and help to justify the verification data set. The main objective of such a statistical test is to provide estimates for stochastic parameters related to the residual probability of misclassifications that could still occur with the trained CNN. For example, a test could yield

- estimates for mean value μ and standard deviation σ of the probability to encounter a misclassification in a sample of m images,
- an upper confidence limit $U \in [0, 1]$ for this mean value, so that the true mean value satisfies $\mu \in [0, U]$ with a high probability $1 - \alpha$.

An alternative, more direct, way to assess the misclassification probability is given as follows.

1. Let $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots\}$ be the very large but still finite space of images representing objects to be classified (e.g. an obstacle on the railway track), and $\mathcal{W} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots\}$ the finite space of images where all objects of interest are absent (e.g. no obstacles on the track). Let

$$\mathcal{O} = \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{W}$$

denote the population of all pixel matrices representing camera images.

2. Let $X : \mathcal{O} \longrightarrow \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a random variable specified on population \mathcal{O} by

$$X(o) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if the CNN produces a false negative on } o \\ 1 & \text{if the CNN produces a false positive on } o \\ 2 & \text{if the CNN produces a true negative on } o \\ 4 & \text{if the CNN produces a true positive on } o \end{cases}$$

3. Let $F(x) = P(X < x) \ x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be the **cumulative distribution function** of X . Note that, if F were known, all **V&V**-related questions about the quality of the trained **CNN** could be answered:
 - The probability for a safety-related misclassification (i.e. a misclassification violating the **SOTIF**) is $F(0)$.
 - The probability of an unnecessary availability or Quality of Service (**QoS**) reduction due to a false positive is $F(1) - F(0)$.
4. Using Monte Carlo methods on a reasonably large sample set of images $S = \{o_1, \dots, o_n\}$, the cumulative distribution function F can be estimated by the **sample cumulative distribution function**

$$\hat{F}(x) = \frac{|\{o \in S \mid X(o) \leq x\}|}{n}. \quad (18.5)$$

The Fundamental Theorem of Statistics (Theorem of Glivenko and Cantelli) states that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |F(x) - \hat{F}_n(x)| = 0$ with probability one [177, p. 68].

It has to be observed, however, that Equation (18.5) only results in a good estimate for F , if

- the images in sample set S have been independently selected, and
- the sample set S is representative for the whole population.

In a **CNN** for recognition of obstacles on railway tracks, for example, the independence of the image selection for S would be violated if the colour of the first road vehicle representing an obstacle on the track would determine the colour of all further road vehicle selections. The sample set would not be representative, if the obstacles types to be expected in the **ODD** would not be fully covered by representatives $o \in S$. Moreover, S needs to cover the more fine-grained classification clusters applied internally by the **CNN** to obtain a classification result.

18.5 Sensor-Perceptor Fusion and Stochastic Independence

Publicly available results on classification correctness of **CNN** (see, for example, Ristić-Durrant et al. [173] reporting on obstacle detection techniques for trains) indicate that, as of today, one trained **CNN** alone cannot reach the correctness level required for safety-critical applications with **SIL** 4. Also, it is not advisable to apply non-redundant sensors for safety critical applications like obstacle detection. As a consequence, it seems advisable to apply redundant sensor-perceptor channels together with a fusion strategy ensuring enhanced safety in comparison with a single-channel sensor-perceptor component [83].

The need for sensor-perceptor fusion

Of course, the desired safety enhancement is best if the the two channels are stochastically independent with respect to their classification results, so that the misclassification probability of the sensor-perceptor fusion is the product of the per-channel misclassification probabilities. For trained **CNN**, the justification of stochastic independence is non-trivial, even if different training sets and different model structures have been applied,

since some of the hidden **DNN** layers in different **CNN** may still contain common misclassification causes.

A promising approach to justify stochastic independence between differently trained and differently structured **CNN** for the same classification purpose is to compare the reasons for the (mostly identical) classification results obtained by both **CNN**: following the explanation concepts described on page 181, we can extract the highest-responsibility causes from an image frame v , as obtained by each of the **CNN**. Applying the methodology advocated by Chockler et al. [45, 192], each set of such causes can be represented by a sparse “cause matrix” of super pixels, where only the pixels with highest responsibility are represented by non-zero values, while the pixels with low responsibility for the classification result are represented by zeros. Then both **CNN** are evaluated with the same set of n images. This leads to cause matrices M_1^1, \dots, M_n^1 obtained from the first **CNN**, and cause matrices M_1^2, \dots, M_n^2 obtained from the second **CNN**. Then a χ^2 -test [177] can be applied to check the stochastic independence of both matrix sequences.

Testing
for
stochastic
independence

Chapter 19

V&V in the Cloud

19.1 Why Cloud Support for V&V is Unavoidable

Ultra-complex systems require far more tests than conventional ones to ensure safety and to obtain trustworthy values for the residual risk of hazards and accidents to occur. This holds for both

The need for testing in the cloud

- **verification** tests ensuring that the system conforms to a given specification, and
- **validation** tests showing that the system's capabilities are adequate for its purpose.

In [120] it is stated that

“Autonomous vehicles would have to be driven hundreds of millions of miles and sometimes hundreds of billions of miles to demonstrate their reliability in terms of fatalities and injuries.”

and

“Under even aggressive testing assumptions, existing fleets would take tens and sometimes hundreds of years to drive these miles—an impossible proposition if the aim is to demonstrate their performance prior to releasing them on the roads for consumer use.”

Consequently, it will no longer be possible to perform all necessary system-level tests with original equipment and in the real-world operational environment.

Moreover, the large archives with test results to be expected cannot be simply replicated and stored on local workstations to be evaluated and checked for suitability to obtain certification credit. Such testing volumes exceed the computational, storage, and coordination capabilities of local infrastructures. Instead, a centralised repository is needed that can be accessed by verification teams, validation teams, and, finally, certification teams. In conclusion, a supporting technology is needed that allows to

Huge amounts of test data to be expected

- execute many **V&V** tests concurrently,
- store large amounts of test-related artefacts in a way making them accessible to the authorised stake holders,
- easily extend the computational power and the storage capacity when needed, and
- provide traceability and consistent auditability of test results across organisational boundaries.

According to the current state of technology, **server farms in the cloud** provide the technology to implement these objectives:

Server farms in the cloud

- Tests can be executed concurrently, encapsulating the **SUT** in **virtual prototypes** and using **simulations** for the operational environment.
- Test-related artefacts – from test cases and procedures to test execution logs – can be stored in **cloud-native repositories** [2].
- Cloud operating systems and associated service layers¹ allow to abstract from the technical details of cloud operation, so that a server farm appears as a collection of remote centralised services that can be easily operated from local clients.

¹for example, **kubernetes** <https://kubernetes.io>

- For organisations concerned with data sovereignty or compliance², private or hybrid cloud models offer the scalability of cloud computing while maintaining strict control over sensitive data.

Summarising, testing ultra-complex systems without cloud-based infrastructure is not only inefficient — it is fundamentally infeasible given current technological and regulatory demands.

Since system tests in the cloud are necessarily executed without the real target system hardware and without the native operational environment, the so-called **reality gap** needs to be closed:

Closing
the reality
gap

- Target system **HW** is not used when testing in the cloud. We depend on simulators calculating address maps and simulating instruction execution on registers perform this exactly as will be done on the real **HW**, and with trustworthy timing information.
- Tests involving environment data always depend on this data being representative for what is to be expected in the native operational environment of the SUT.

The means for closing the reality gap are discussed in the two subsequent sections.

19.2 Virtual Prototypes

When performing system-level **V&V** tests in the cloud, a crucial challenge must be addressed to obtain certification credit:

The need
for virtual
prototypes

The system hardware must be replaced by simulation software running in the cloud that is accurate and reliable enough to reveal HW/SW integration faults as they would manifest on the real embedded hardware.

²**Compliance** in this context refers to the adherence to legal, regulatory, and industry-specific requirements governing data protection, safety, security, and traceability throughout the testing and certification process.

Such simulation software – called **Virtual Prototype (VP)** (sometimes also **Virtual Platforms**) – replicates the behaviour of specific hardware architectures, including instruction sets, memory models, and I/O timing. A virtual prototype serves as a virtual execution platform, allowing the system software (compiled for the real-world target hardware) to run unmodified on cloud infrastructure. It effectively sits between the target software and the cloud operating system (which typically runs on a different architecture), enabling hardware-independent, scalable testing in the cloud.

The development of VPs is an active research field [88], and there are also commercial VPs provided for various HW architectures, as, for example:

Tools
providing
VPs

- ARM Fixed Virtual Platforms (FVPs),
- Simcenter Embedded Software Designer, and
- Cadence Virtual System Platform (VSP)

simulate several architectures, like ARM, x86, PowerPC, or RISC-V.

However, for obtaining certification credit, it is mandatory that VPs are **qualified** according to the standards on which the certification will be based [40, 105, 206]. Otherwise errors in a VP could mask SW errors or HW/SW integration errors in the target system to be verified and validated in the cloud. Qualification objectives of particular importance are:

Tool
qualification
for VPs

- ensuring bit-level accuracy of instruction set simulations,
- Timing accuracy (since VPs running on a cloud platform have different timing characteristics than the target system),
- handling non-determinism in hardware interactions, and
- demonstrating traceability and justifiability of abstraction choices.

Several commercial VP providers offer **tool qualification kits** that can be tailored to specific VP applications in safety-critical contexts. Tool Qualification (**TQ**) for VPs is an active research field [5]. There is, however, no

universally accepted approach to **VP** qualification. Due to the complexity of modern architectures, the **TQ** effort for a **VP** is quite high. Therefore, the cloud-based testing approach to safety-critical **CPS** is only justified if the underlying business case promises considerable returns of investment (as, for example, for autonomous road vehicles), and if the architecture simulated by the **VP** will remain stable for a longer time period.

19.3 Further Simulation Support

VPs only simulate controller architectures. Ultra-complex **CPS**, however, will need far more simulation support before they can be justifiably tested in the cloud. For example:

- Environment simulations are needed for a multitude of aspects, such as
 - user interactions,
 - behaviour of systems in the operational environment communicating with the target system, and
 - weather conditions.
- Physical simulations are required to calculate the effect of actuations performed by the **SUT** on the environment and the associated feedback on the **SUT**'s input sensors.

Again, these simulations need to be qualified. A particular **TQ** challenge is to justify the **completeness** of simulations, for example,

Do the simulated camera images fed into the obstacle detection system of an autonomous vehicle tested in the cloud cover sufficiently many obstacle types, weather conditions, and lighting effects?

In principle, these types of justification can be performed by tracing **V&V** tests back to a comprehensively structured **ODD**. The effort for this, however, is huge.

Summarising, cloud-based V&V for safety-critical CPS is justifiable only when the business case offers a compelling Return of Investment (ROI)—such as in domains where the cost of physical testing or time-to-market delays significantly exceeds the tool qualification effort. However, this economic rationale clashes with scenarios where ultra-complex safety-critical systems are developed for non-commercial reasons – for instance, due to political, regulatory, or public service demands. These systems typically cannot be verified and validated without cloud-based infrastructure, yet the available V&V budgets are limited due to the absence of strong ROI drivers. This inherent conflict poses a serious challenge: the need to assure system safety competes directly with constrained funding, risking either insufficient qualification or compromised certification readiness.

Part V
Certification

Chapter 20

Certification Aspects – Overview

In the automotive, avionic, and railway domains, the advent of **AI**-based applications in safety-related system components has been anticipated and accepted as inevitable. Before autonomous systems in these domains can become operative, however, they need to be certified with respect to their safety and security. The need for certification is even higher than for conventional systems, because autonomous systems need to perform additional tasks that are responsibilities of humans (drivers, pilots, ...) in conventional systems (see Chapter 22 and Koopman et al. [127]).

Utilisation
of AI
inevitable

The certification of safety-critical systems depends on standards, and none of the transportation domains (aviation, automotive, railways) has yet come up with an internationally accepted standard regulating the development and **V&V** of robotics and autonomous systems (**RAS**) in any of these three domains. Therefore, this chapter and the ones to follow focus more on current standards and their potential future extensions than on the certification process itself.

Current
standards
do not
suffice

Chapter 21 lists the most important standards currently valid in the transportation domains. In Section 22, we summarise the well-known main reasons why current standards do not suffice to certify autonomous **RAS**. In Section 22.3, we describe an interesting, but unfortunately small subclass of autonomous systems that can be certified on the basis of today's standards. In Chapter 23, we review the ongoing standardisation activi-

Overview

ties related to autonomous vehicles in the automotive domain; these are significantly further advanced than the related activities in the aviation and railway domains. The novel standardisation efforts in the former are described in Chapter 24, and for the latter in Chapter 25. The certification-related contributions of research communities are discussed in Chapter 26.

We conclude this part in Chapter 28 with an explanation how complex safety cases can be presented in a semi-formal way, in order to produce concise justifications why certification credit can be awarded to a complex V&V campaign.

Chapter 21

A Brief Overview of Current Standards for the Transportation Domain

In the aviation domain, the current standard for the certification of electronic software-based control systems (avionic systems) is [Aviation domain](#)

RTCA DO-178C Software Considerations in Airborne Systems and Equipment Certification [\[206\]](#)

with its supplements

RTCA DO-248C Supporting Information for DO-178C and DO-278A [\[207\]](#),

RTCA DO-330 Software Tool Qualification Considerations [\[208\]](#),

RTCA DO-331 Model-Based Development and Verification Supplement to DO-178C and DO-278A [\[209\]](#),

RTCA DO-332 Object-Oriented Technology and Related Techniques – Supplement to DO-178C and DO-278A [\[210\]](#),

RTCA DO-333 Formal Methods Supplement to DO-178C and DO-278A [\[211\]](#).

We expect that RTCA DO-178C will be extended in the future to provide guidelines for development and **V&V** of autonomous control systems. Currently, neither autonomous systems nor the use of **AI**-based software is addressed in this standard.

In the automotive domain, the current applicable standard for safety-critical control systems in non-autonomous cars is the ISO 26262 standards family. Automotive
Domain

ISO-26262-1 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 1: Vocabulary [105],

ISO-26262-2 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 2: Management of functional safety [107],

ISO-26262-3 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 3: Concept phase [108],

ISO-26262-4 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 4: Product development: system level [109],

ISO-26262-5 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 5: Product development: hardware level [110],

ISO-26262-6 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 6: Product development: software level [111],

ISO-26262-7 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 7: Production and operation [112],

ISO-26262-8 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 8: Supporting processes [113],

ISO-26262-9 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 9: ASIL-oriented and safety-oriented analyses [114],

ISO-26262-10 Road vehicles – functional safety – Part 10: Guideline [106].

This standard is currently complemented by new standards specialising on autonomous vehicles and application of **AI**; this is further described in Section 23.1.

In the railway domain, the current standards are

Railway
domain

EN 50126-1 Railway Applications - The Specification and Demonstration of Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS) - Part 1: Generic RAMS Process [41],

EN 50128 Railway applications - Communication, signalling and processing systems - Software for railway control and protection systems [40],

EN 50129 Railway applications - Communication, signalling and processing systems - Safety related electronic systems for signalling [42],

EN 50159 Railway applications - Communication, signalling and processing systems - Safety-related communication in transmission systems [39].

Just as the RTCA DO-178C standards family, the EN 50xxx standards do not address autonomous systems or **AI**-based applications. Indeed, the application of **AI** in software components is explicitly discouraged or even forbidden [40, Table A.3].

The CENELEC standardisation body that was responsible for the creation of the EN 50xxx standards, however, as announced in 2021 that standards will be updated to allow for the use of **AI**.¹ More details about this are discussed in Chapter 25.

¹<https://www.cenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2021/briefnews/2021-04-21-european-standards-support-eu-ambitions-on-artificial-intelligence/>

Chapter 22

Insufficiency of Current Standards

It is current knowledge that full-fledged autonomous systems cannot be certified on the basis of existing standards [61]. The main reasons for this fact can be classified as

- technical reasons,
- legal reasons, and
- ethical reasons.

Why current technical standards cannot provide a certification basis for complex autonomous systems

22.1 Legal and Ethical Insufficiency of Current Standards

As motivated in Figure 22.1, current standards for conventional systems could ignore the topic of compliance with laws, regulations, rules¹, since these responsibilities can be delegated to humans (drivers, pilots, ...). Additionally, trained humans can be expected to make appropriate decisions to mitigate risks or to react in hazardous situations in a way conforming to

Current technical standards can ignore capabilities of responsible humans

¹Rules could be, for example, company guidelines or best practices.

the ethical convictions of our society.² In particular, trained humans can be expected to have internalised the ethical rules for damage reduction³ in situations where accidents cannot be avoided.

Moreover, trained humans can be expected to assess risk in an appropriate way and to be capable of risk-benefit considerations.⁴ Finally, the responsible humans can be expected to improve their skills through learning, thereby continuously reducing the risk of entering hazardous system states.

Figure 22.1: Conventional system control by humans.

As depicted in Figure 22.2, the observation of laws, regulations, rules, and ethical behaviour, as well as risk/benefit considerations and learning capabilities, need to be ensured by the technical system itself, as soon as they operate with full **autonomy**. As shown below in Figure 26.2, it

Aspects to be covered by a new generation of technical standards

²Of course, we know that this expectation is only fulfilled in general, but exceptions such as the one documented in https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Germanwings_Flight_9525 are considered as “sufficiently unlikely”.

³A typical ethical rule is “*avoidance of loss of human lives has priority over damage cost reduction.*”

⁴For example, the risk of damaging a car blocking access to a burning building can be accepted by the driver of the fire fighting vehicle, since the benefits of timely fire extinction are higher than avoiding damage of the car.

is therefore suggested to structure autonomous systems certification into several activities that cover the demonstration that conformance to rules, ethical decision making, and adequate risk/benefit evaluation, as well as management of and learning from **incidents** and accidents are properly implemented. As a consequence, the new generation of standards needs to provide sufficient conditions to decide when the conformance of an autonomous system with these aspects has been adequately demonstrated, so that the system is fit for entry into service.

Figure 22.2: Autonomous system control.

22.2 Technical Insufficiency of Current Standards

Most classes of autonomous systems could not be realised without the application of **AI**. The current technical standards for safety critical aspects of transportation systems listed above, however, do not address the application of **AI** at all, or even discourage it for the following reasons.

1. Software components based on trained **neural networks** or any other software applying **machine learning** techniques cannot be formally

3 critical certification obstacles for RAS

verified to be correct, since their behaviour depends on the *training/learning* phase and produces correct results only with a certain reliability value less than one.⁵

2. The safety-related behaviour of ultra-complex autonomous systems cannot be fully specified *before* type certification, because behavioural changes may occur due to learning effects or due to the new plans being synthesised and executed during runtime. Changes of plans may be caused, for example, by system configuration changes: Collaborative autonomous systems will change their component behaviour due to components entering or leaving the system configuration.
3. The implementation of rule-based behaviour is strongly suggested to ensure conformance to laws, rules, as well as ethical behaviour as discussed above [61]. The implementation of rule-based modules, for example by using *BDI* agents discussed in Section 2.7.2, however, introduces a new programming paradigm. This paradigm differs significantly from programming languages like C, C++ or Ada currently used for programming safety-critical control systems. In particular, the time needed for plan executions is very difficult to predict, and the calculation of conclusions from the rule base and the current belief established by situation awareness, cannot be performed in hard real-time.

It is important to emphasise that the three aspects listed here are extremely difficult to verify, so that new generations of standards will have considerable problems to define concrete criteria for the decision to declare an autonomous system as trustworthy and therefore fit for entry into service.

It is therefore questionable whether the stack of standards and pre-standards described in Section 23.1 is really adequate to ensure trustworthiness of autonomous systems.

⁵Think of a classification module for road traffic signs.

22.3 A Restricted Class of Autonomous Systems that can be Certified Today

There exists a very restricted subclass of autonomous systems which can be certified on the basis of existing standards.

Restricted class of autonomous systems can be certified with current standards

If the safety supervisors of an autonomous systems can be specified with conventional methods and implemented with conventional technology, and if the safety supervisors are segregated from the rest of the (application) system in a trustworthy way, then the safety of the integrated system can be demonstrated by conventional means, because the ultra complex AI-based application has no impact on the safety of the overall system.

Autonomous systems of this kind have been advocated by Koopman et al. [127], and an important class of these restricted systems has been investigated by Gleirscher et al. [70]: The safety of collaborating humans and robots can be ensured by conventional sensors (e.g. switch status of ON/OFF switches and light sensors) and evaluated by a discrete safety supervisor implementing a safety assurance strategy that has been fully elaborated and shown to minimise risk *before* the system becomes operative. The robotic controller implementing the AI-based robotic behaviour can be strictly segregated from the controller running the safety supervisor.

Obviously, this class of systems does not need to ensure conformance to laws or ethical behaviour in its safety supervisor. Unfortunately, autonomous vehicles are outside this class, since the recognition of traffic signs, pedestrians, cyclists, other cars etc. has to rely on AI-based image recognition. The same holds for the autonomous taxiing application for aircrafts. In the railway domain, autonomous passenger trains depend on AI-based image recognition to identify passengers standing close to the train on platforms. As a consequence, the safety supervisors of these system types need to apply at least one of the three technologies identified as certification obstacles in Section 22.2.

Autonomous vehicles are outside this class

Chapter 23

Standardisation Activities in the Automotive Domain

23.1 A Comprehensive Stack of Existing (Pre-)Standards for Autonomous Vehicles

Koopman presents a stack of standards for autonomous vehicles that is endorsed by the US Department of Transportation (US Department of transportation (DOT)) (see Figure 23.1).¹

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=xCIjxiV048Q&feature=youtu.be>

Figure 23.1: Stack of standards for autonomous, as presented by Koopman <https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=xCIjxiV048Q&feature=youtu.be>.

We explain the listed (pre-)standards shown in Figure 23.1 in bottom-up fashion. The **Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards (FMVSS)**² specify basic safety requirements for vehicles in general, without special reference to autonomous cars. The **New Car Assessment Programme (NCAP)**³ extend the **FMVSS** for modern car assistance systems like speed assist and automated emergency braking systems; again, without reference to fully autonomous cars (see Appendix A for the five **automation** levels defined for vehicles by the **NHTSA**).

Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards (USA) (FMVSS), New Car Assessment Programme (NCAP) SAE J3061, SAE 21434

The standards on the next layer up are concerned with cyber security: since fully autonomous cars will depend on **Vehicle to everything (V2X) communication**, security vulnerabilities of this communication represent severe safety threats. SAE J3061 provides guidance to security as it relates to cyber-physical vehicle systems.⁴ ISO/SAE DIS 21434 is a draft standard specifying “... requirements for cybersecurity risk management regarding engineering for concept, development, production, operation, maintenance,

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Federal_Motor_Vehicle_Safety_Standards

³<https://cdn.euroncap.com/media/17718/euro-ncap-assessment-protocol-sa-v61.pdf>

⁴https://www.sae.org/standards/content/j3061_201601/

and decommissioning for road vehicle electrical and electronic (E/E) systems, including their components and interfaces.”⁵

The middle layer is represented by ISO 26262 which covers “conventional” functional safety. This standard has been established in the automotive domain since about 2009 and is the automotive equivalent to RTCA DO-179C and EN 50128. ISO 26262

The next layer up is concerned with proper autonomous driving. It refers to ISO 21448 [104]: *Road vehicles — Safety of the intended functionality*. This pre-standard complements ISO 26262 by taking into account the impact of “modern” AI-based technology, such as **machine learning**, used in connection with sensing and situational awareness. The ISO/TR 4804:2020 standard complements ISO 21448 with respect to cyber security of autonomous systems. Its guidance extends that of SAE J3061 and SAE 21434 with respect to automated driving. ISO 21448,
ISO/TR 4804

The ANSI/UL 4600-2020 Standard for Evaluation of Autonomous Products is intended as UL 4600

“... a generalized autonomous system standard framework using light autonomous road vehicles as a concrete example.” [199, 1.2.1]

To the best of our knowledge, this is the only international standard

- claiming to be applicable to all autonomous systems domains, and
- stating requirements for setting up a safety case in the context of autonomous systems assurance.

In particular, it addresses the following important safety-relevant aspects that are not covered by today’s standards for conventional systems: an acceptable safety case needs to document the safety-related effects of

1. incorrect sensors,
2. inaccurate, incomplete, or biased **training** data for system behaviours based on **machine learning**, and

⁵<https://www.sae.org/standards/content/iso/sae21434.d1/>

3. erroneous simulation models.

These requirements are new; they *extend* the safety case construction for conventional systems. The safety-related considerations required for safety cases of conventional systems need to be performed as well.

A **safety case**, is defined in UL 4600 as follows (the term *item* is used in UL 4600 for the target system to be certified).

Definition 6 (Safety Case)

The safety case shall be a structured explanation in the form of claims, supported by argument and evidence, that justifies that the item is acceptably safe for a defined operational design domain, and covers the item's lifecycle.

The UL 4600 requires all evidence supporting the safety case to be presented in a well-defined format and adequately typed. UL 4600 also requires the safety case to be represented in a structured manner. To this end, the **Goal Structuring Notation (GSN)** described in Section 28 is a suitable means. For a sufficient safety case, comprehensive safety requirements need to be elaborated, addressing the following aspects.

1. Safety of the intended functionality (as covered by ISO 21448 [104]),
2. safety of unintended functionality (certain functions must be blocked in specific operational modes),
3. functional safety as in conventional systems, typically derived from a hazard analysis,
4. fault tolerance mechanisms mitigating the safety threats posed by internal system faults,
5. fault tolerance mechanisms mitigating the safety threats occurring in the environment, and

6. safety of life cycle-related operations (software updates, maintenance, ...).

The completeness of the safety requirements collection needs to be demonstrated by means of a comprehensive (beyond just functional safety) hazard analysis: every hazard must be addressed by at least one safety requirements. Hazards need to be paired with safety integrity levels.

The standard explicitly addresses the fact that autonomous systems may act on the basis of **belief systems**, such as the current location of the system, the safety of the current state, or assumptions about the environment. It is required to elaborate on **epistemic defeaters**, that is, events indicating that certain beliefs are no longer well-founded or even invalid.

Belief
systems
and
epistemic
defeaters

Example 26. The autonomous ego vehicle drives on a country road with one lane in each direction. A slow van is driving in front of the ego vehicle, and another car is approaching from the distance in the opposite direction. Based on the current camera evaluations, the ego vehicle has the belief that the van is the only vehicle in front. Therefore, overtaking the van involves an acceptable risk, since the approaching car on the other lane is still sufficiently far a way.

The next camera frames, however, show a shadow on one side of the van contours. This shadow might indicate that there is another car in front of the van. This event is an **undercutting defeater** of the belief that there is only one vehicle in front of the ego vehicle. As a result, the risk of overtaking is increased, since the belief about just one car in front has been questioned.

A few camera frames later, a second vehicle in front of the van is clearly identifiable. This event represents a **rebutting defeater**, that is, the *negation* of the original belief “*only one vehicle in front*” is now to be entered into the ego vehicle’s belief database. □

Moreover, epistemic defeaters need to be used in safety arguments to indicate clearly which conditions might invalidate the safety argument.

Example 27. Suppose that the software of a safety supervisor has been proven to be correct by means of a complete test suite, as described by

Gleirscher et al. [72]. The correctness proof, however, is only valid if certain hypotheses about guard conditions and about the number of states in the reference model and in the implementation are fulfilled. Invalidity of this hypothesis would be an **undercutting defeater** of the correctness assumption: the software may still be correct, since all tests in the suite have been passed, but the argument that passing the test suite corresponds to a correctness proof is no longer valid. \square

The UL 4600 standard seems to be the first to define explicit rules for checking the conformance of AI-based functionality. In some cases these checks are surprisingly strict and – from our perspective – quite helpful.

Example 28. In UL 4500 [199, Section 8.4], certification-related evidence for (AI-based) **perception functions** is described. Roughly speaking, perception functions are those functions needed for appropriate situation awareness of an autonomous system. Examples are sensors and associated evaluation software for localisation, obstacle recognition, and identification of any relevant object in the system environment. In the case of autonomous vehicles, examples for the latter are different kinds of pedestrians, cyclists, other vehicles, traffic signs and other road furniture, as well as street furniture (benches, trash bins, street lamps, . . .). Perception functions frequently result in object detections with associated classifications, for example, *“This is a traffic sign of type ‘stop sign’.”*

For perception functions involving classification, it is required that **ontologies** are specified as domains of the classification results [199, Section 8.4.2], and it has to be justified via inspections (reviews) that the ontologies used are large enough for the design space. For the classification of humans in the environment of an autonomous vehicle, for example, it would not suffice to set up an ontology distinguishing just ‘adults’ and ‘children’. The distinctions ‘disabled person’, ‘road worker’ and others will also be important.

Moreover, for checking the conformance of perception functions with the standard, it is also required to verify the mapping result from sensor to ontology [199, Section 8.4.3.6.2]. For example, it is insufficient just to check that the autonomous vehicle brakes in all required situations, but that it does so *“for the correct reason”*: if the vehicle brakes as expected in front

New
requirements
for
conformance
checking

of a stop sign, the classification result leading to this braking action must not be that the sign has been interpreted as a ‘road entry forbidden’ traffic sign. This conformance checking requirement is consistent with insights stated in the research communities [192]. □

For checking the conformance of system functions based on **machine learning**, the standard explicitly addresses the need to justify the acceptability of the data sets used during **training** [199, Section 8.5.3].

The authors of UL 4600 claim that their standard for system-level safety assurance is suitable for other autonomous systems domains. It remains to be seen whether the certification authorities for the avionic and railway domains will really adopt UL 4600 or parts thereof.

UL 4600
applicable
in avionic
and
railway
domains?

Interestingly, the standard does *not* address the problems 2 and 3 discussed in Section 22.2 (problems with behavioural changes during system operation due to planning changes, and the implementation problems for rule-based behaviours). Therefore, significant safety-relevant problems of autonomous systems that we have identified here in this technical report are simply not addressed by UL 4600.

Criticism

Moreover, the requirements in UL 4600 for demonstrating conformance of **AI**-based system functions suggest that a trustworthy demonstration of conformance is already possible today, which is definitely not the case. Our evaluation of the standard indicates that its creation has been driven in a considerable way by the interesting business cases related to autonomous systems. Moreover, a considerable overlap between UL 4600 and ISO 21448 can be identified. The association of ISO 21448 in a layer below UL 4600 as shown in Figure 23.1 is not completely justified, because ISO 21448 also addresses questions of system-level safety, just as UL 4600.

Nonetheless, we acknowledge that UL 4600 contains very valuable certification-related material that is tailored to autonomous systems and contains at least some valuable guidelines for showing conformance.

23.2 Further Standards of Interest in the Automotive Domain

The pre-standard IEEE P2846/D7.1 considers reasonably foreseeable behaviour of road users in different traffic scenarios and specifies the physical boundary values to be considered [202]. It is stated there that [IEEE P2846/D7.1](#)

“The purpose of this standard is to define the assumptions about reasonably foreseeable behaviors of other road users that shall be considered for Automated Driving Systems.”

The authors of the pre-standard argue that human drivers in conventional vehicles continuously make assumptions that the subjects in the system environment will not behave in an unforeseeable and chaotic way. The authors argue that this assumption is adequate in most of the situations, so that the residual risk of having not taken chaotic behaviour into account is acceptable.⁶ If this thesis is accepted, then certain safety margins used during autonomous vehicle operation can be relaxed. The authors argue that this will improve the traffic flow, because the autonomous vehicle’s safety supervisors need to interfere less frequently with braking manoeuvres.

This pre-standard is certainly interesting for defining and justifying test scenarios on system level. IEEE P2846/D7.1, however, is not referenced in the automotive standards stack shown in Figure 23.1. Therefore, we do not expect that certification credit could be obtained in the future just by showing compliance to IEEE P2846/D7.1.

⁶No quantitative evidence is provided for this thesis.

Chapter 24

Standardisation Activities in the Aviation Domain

24.1 Overview

In the aviation domain, standards addressing novel technologies for autonomous flying systems and extending the existing standards described in Chapter 21 are being prepared, with special emphasis on **avionics**.

Preparation of novel standards in the aviation domain

- The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (**EASA**) has a dedicated **AI**-roadmap which is discussed here in Section 24.2.
- The Federal Aviation Administration (Federal Aviation Administration of the USA (**FAA**)) in the USA have elaborated extensive regulatory material for (potentially autonomous) **unmanned aircraft systems (UAS)** [221].
- In 2021, the SAE announced the formation of a new aerospace standards committee, focused on modelling, simulation and **training** for new emerging technologies.¹ This is further discussed in Section 24.3.

¹<https://www.sae.org/news/press-room/2021/09/sae-international-announces-the-formation-of-a-new-aerospace-standards-committee>

24.2 EASA AI Roadmap in Europe

The EASA has set up a roadmap to prepare for the certification of AI-based systems [55]. This roadmap states clearly that the current certification process needs to be extended to ensure that AI will further improve the current level of safety of air transport. The EASA concept paper [56] has been created to anticipate future EASA guidance and requirements for safety-related machine learning applications. It covers only an initial set of AI/ML techniques and will be enriched with more and more advanced techniques, as the EASA AI Roadmap [55] is implemented further.

Avionic
domain:
EASA AI
Roadmap

It is noteworthy that the EASA roadmap has a strict focus on machine learning effects in avionic applications. The potential and the safety-related implications of multi agent systems (MAS), for example, are not considered at all.

Typical future applications using AI methods envisioned by the EASA are

- autonomous flight,
- reduction of task performed by humans (in the cockpit), so that pilots can focus on the most important tasks,
- assistance systems for complex decision processes,
- assistance systems addressing human performance limitations,
- tools solving any kind of mathematical optimisation problem (sensor calibration, fuel tank quantity evaluation, ...),
- support tools for the design phase (e.g. selection of regression tests),
- support tools for physical modelling.

According to the EASA roadmap milestones specified in [55, p. 12], the certification basis for autonomous commercial air transport should be provided until 2035. The EASA sees the following aspects of AI applications

to be the most challenging ones regarding safety assurance and certification [55, p. 14]:

1. Establish traceability between (high-level) requirements and **training** data used for **neural networks** or other components defining and refining their behaviour through **machine learning**.
2. Verify the effectiveness of such data sets with respect to the intended function (observe that **ML**-based applications have **bias** and **variance** issues).
3. Lack of behavioural predictability for applications trained by **machine learning**.
4. Verify **robustness** and absence of unintended functionality for these applications.
5. Complexity of architectures and algorithms
6. Real-time learning in operation, leading to evolving behaviour, due to adaptive learning processes.

The **EASA** suggests three levels with increasing complexity for the classification of **AI/ML**-based applications. These levels are shown in Figure 24.1.

Figure 24.1: Classification of **AI/ML**-based applications according to [55].

It is clearly stated in [55, p. 17] that the current regulatory framework

New
design
assurance
paradigm

with its focus on development assurance cannot address design-level layers relying on learning processes in a sufficient way. For this type of processes, the focus of the assurance procedures need to be shifted to V&V of training and verification data. It is expected that this will result in a new (additional) design assurance paradigm. This might be called learning assurance. The key aspects of such an assurance paradigm as proposed by EASA are shown in Figure 24.2.

Figure 24.2: Key aspects of a learning assurance paradigm, as suggested in [55, pp. 17].

A particular aspect of assuring AI-based applications is their **explainability**: each relevant decision made autonomously by the application must be explained, so that – in particular, after occurrence of an **accident** or incident – the causal chain leading to a potentially undesired action performed by the application can be reconstructed. Obviously, this need for documentation requires extended means of data recording during flight.

An approach to mitigate the risk caused by naive black-box application

of AI/ML-based functionality is to introduce human or automated monitoring functions. The latter might be designed according to the Multi Agent System (MAS) paradigm.

EASA emphasises that their AI trustworthiness analysis is driven by the ethical guidelines of the European Commission, as sketched in Figure 24.3 and Figure 24.4. This addresses the problem that autonomous systems need to perform ethical decisions formerly performed by humans, as described in Section 22.1, in an adequate way.

Figure 24.3: From ethical guidelines to assurance building blocks [55, pp. 20].

Figure 24.4: Ethics Guidelines from the EC High Level Expert Group (from [55, Figure 2]).

24.3 SAE Activities in the USA

In 2021, the SAE announced the formation of a new aerospace standards committee, focused on modelling, simulation and **training** for new emerging technologies.² Among these new technologies, remotely controlled and autonomous aircrafts are explicitly addressed.

Highlights of the planned activities with relation to autonomous systems technology and its certification are the following.

- It is an explicit goal that application of novel technologies in the aviation domain should be facilitated without compromising safety.
- In general, the regulatory framework related to certification should become more efficient and cost-effective.

²<https://www.sae.org/news/press-room/2021/09/sae-international-announces-the-formation-of-a-new-aerospace-standards-committee>

- Guidelines for the use of **digital twins** and virtualisation for development and **V&V** will be elaborated.
- It is investigated whether and to which extent model-based simulations can replace flight tests.

It is interesting to observe that this initiative, which is obviously driven by industrial stakeholders of the aviation industry, simultaneously emphasises both cost reduction for certification and introduction of new technologies. From our perspective, this seems fairly naive, since – as explained throughout this technical report and in the citations given – the crucial technologies needed for autonomous systems will definitely *increase* the **V&V** effort, and, as can already be seen from the stack of standards that may be come relevant (Figure 23.1), lead to certification processes that are far more costly than the current ones, simply because the amount of standards to be considered has been at least doubled.

Criticism

The focus on virtualisation and the goal to obtain certification credit for trustworthy simulations in order to cope with the increasing load of test cases to be executed on all levels (from software module testing, via **HW/SW** integration testing, sub-system tests [e.g., network of cabin controllers], to flight tests, however, is in line with the objectives of the HiDyVe project.

Focal
points of
interest

Chapter 25

Standardisation Activities in the Railway Domain

In the European railway domain, the standardisation activities related to autonomous trains and other railway sub-domains are less advanced than in the automotive and aviation domains.

At least a road map has been specified how to incorporate certifiable autonomous systems in the future.¹ The roadmap has been published by the CENELEC, which also initiated the elaboration of the current railway standards listed in Chapter 21.

Note that this roadmap is not specialised for the railway domain, but represents a far more general framework, as shown in Figure 25.1. It is disappointing that the roadmap addresses use cases for AI in railways only for maintenance purposes. This is in strong contrast to Europe's railway authorities and manufacturers who have already defined a variety of challenging business cases, from autonomous freight trains to autonomous metros with AI-based supervision of passenger security on platforms.

¹https://standict.eu/sites/default/files/2021-03/CEN-CLC_FGR_RoadMapAI.pdf

Categorising the expected Standards Developments

Figure 25.1: CEN-CENELEC use cases for AI according to https://standict.eu/sites/default/files/2021-03/CEN-CLC_FGR_RoadMapAI.pdf.

Chapter 26

Certification Options Suggested by Research Communities

26.1 Consensus in the Research Communities

After several decades of research on autonomous systems, there seems to be a consensus on several certification-related topics of importance.

- AI needs to be explainable in order to enable certification to AI-based systems components [192].
- Certification requirements for autonomous systems can be derived from the licenses required for humans taken responsibility for similar conventional systems. Fisher et al. [61] state this as follows.

“The key idea is that, if the autonomous system is performing tasks that are currently done by humans, then knowledge about how these humans are currently licenced can be used to help identify requirements.”

- Training data for system components based on machine learning needs to qualified with respect to (see Section 26.2)
 - completeness for the situations to be expected in the application domain, and

- absence of **bias**.
- Modelling and testing will become so complex that it must be based on libraries of scenarios instead of monolithic models [73, 100].
- Since not every foreseeable behaviour of the system to be certified can be verified at type certification, additional re-certification activities are needed. This is called **runtime certification** [29, 176, 183].
- Just as **machine learning** and classification based on **neural networks**, multi-agent systems (**MAS**), in particular, **BDI** agents, will become essential for autonomous systems, in particular for collaboration of autonomous systems, security functions, and for rule-based behaviour in otherwise unforeseen situations [12, 43, 61, 155, 184, 214].
- Recording of **AI**-based autonomous decisions will become essential for incident and **accident** investigations [54, 61].
- Runtime system health monitoring (performed today by **built-in test equipment (BITE)**) will require higher “levels of sophistication”, based on runtime verification, runtime checks of emergent properties, and online root cause analysis [61, 96].
- In well-defined or anticipated exceptional situations, the expected behaviour of an autonomous system should be based on models and scenario libraries. For operational situations that could not be anticipated, the system behaviour should at least follow a set of rules (see Figure 26.1).

Figure 26.1: Layered reference **autonomy** framework suggested by Fisher et al. [61].

26.2 View of the Assuring Autonomy Project

In the context of the *Assuring autonomy* project described in Chapter 1, an assurance-oriented development life cycle for robotics and autonomous systems (RAS) has been proposed.¹ In Figure 26.2, the certification-related part of this life cycle is shown.

¹see

<https://www.york.ac.uk/assuring-autonomy/guidance/body-of-knowledge/>

Source (looked up on 2021-05-17):

https://www.york.ac.uk/media/assuring-autonomy/documents/BoK%20Update_July_Plain.pdf

Figure 26.2: Aspects of gaining approval for a robotic or/and autonomous systems.

As can be seen there, the four basic aspects to be ensured for gaining certification approval are

1. conforming to rules and regulations,
2. risk acceptance,
3. provision of sufficient confidence in the required behaviour, and
4. provision for investigation of **incidents** and accidents.

26.2.1 Conforming to Rules and Regulations

It has to be demonstrated that the **RAS** conforms to all applicable rules and regulations. To this end, the latter have first to be identified, taking into account all application contexts the **RAS** is planned to become operative in. Obviously, different application contexts may come with their own standards and norms to conform to. Next it has to be demonstrated that rules and regulations have been correctly understood, so that conformance of the **RAS** to the rules will result in the appropriate behaviour.

Finally, **V&V** cases are needed demonstrating that the **RAS** conforms to the rules and regulations. Note that in contrast to non-autonomous systems, the demonstration of conformance requires evidence that the rules and regulations have been correctly *implemented in the system*, as discussed above in Section 22.1.

Rules and regulations need to be implemented in the autonomous system

Example 29. A conventional car must only be fit for the human driver to conform to all traffic rules. For example, there must be a turn indication lever and turn indication lights implemented, so that the driver can conform to the “*flash before changing lanes on a motor way*” rule. For type certification of an autonomous car, however, it must be demonstrated by suitable system tests that the car controller activates left or right flashing before performing lane changes. □

26.2.2 Risk Acceptance

Approval for the residual risk of operating the **RAS** must be gained from the certification authorities. In contrast to conventional systems, complex autonomous systems cannot rely on a human-in-the-loop for risk mitigation actions in hazardous situations.

According to the state of the art, a **world model** is needed [73, 75] (see also Chapter 15) to gain acceptance: this is a probabilistic behavioural model, describing the **RAS** embedded into its operational environment. The world model needs to take into account all relevant behaviours in the environment (humans, vehicles, ...) that are needed to estimate the worst-case impact of faulty **RAS** behaviour. It has to be shown by probabilistic methods² that the safety mechanisms of the **RAS** reduce the residual risk to an acceptable level, provided that the world model is complete. **V&V** evidence for the world model's completeness and soundness has to be provided. The uncertainties in the probabilistic assumptions need to be documented.

World model for risk assessment

Residual risks may be justified by referring to benefits of the **RAS** operation (**risk-benefit trade-off analysis**). For example, the **RAS** operation

²for example, by probabilistic model checking

could eliminate other higher risks. This would justify the residual risk in the **RAS**.

Since human controllers have been removed from the risk mitigation loop, it has to be shown that all foreseeable risk mitigation actions conform to ethical rules. If the implemented mitigation mechanisms have been created by **training** procedures and/or are allowed to optimise during runtime by means of **machine learning**, it even has to be demonstrated that mitigation strategies in unavoidable **accident** situations are *unbiased*.

Autonomous
safety
supervisor
must
conform
to ethical
rules

Example 30. Automated safety supervisors in complex autonomous systems frequently need to apply **multi-objective (Pareto) optimisations**³ to select suitable risk mitigation strategies in hazardous situations where some damage cannot be avoided. It has to be demonstrated that these optimisations take ethical rules like “*the protection of human lives has priority over minimising the costs of equipment damage, if an **accident** cannot be avoided*” into account. □

26.2.3 Provision of Sufficient Confidence in the Required Behaviour

In conventional system developments, the confidence in the required system behaviour can be gained by first identifying a suitable **safety integrity level (SIL)** [102] (also called **design assurance level (DAL)** [206]) and then conforming to the thoroughness and rigour in development and **V&V** procedures required for this level by the standards.

Confidence
in
conventional
systems

While the SIL-dependent development and **V&V** effort certainly still applies to autonomous systems, it is no longer sufficient to demonstrate that confidence in the required system behaviour is justified. This has been explained already in Section 2.13: the correct implementation of **neural networks** or other algorithms based on **machine learning** does not yet guarantee compliance with their intended functionality, because the latter also depends on the **training** and learning phases.

Confidence
in
autonomous
systems

No universal guidance has yet been established how confidence into the

³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multi-objective_optimization

system behaviour can be justified. Acceptable demonstrations will certainly involve statistical tests (“*this module classifies traffic signs correctly with a probability greater than n%, and this hypothesis is correct with a probability of at least q%*”). However, these tests will have to be complemented by arguments that **training** procedures were unbiased and classification algorithms performed correctly during tests *for the right reasons* [192].

26.2.4 Provision for Investigation of Incidents and Accidents

In autonomous systems, the chain of events leading to an **incident** or **accident**, together with the decisions made by the safety supervisor, need to be adequately monitored and documented, so that the root cause leading to an **accident** can be identified. This monitoring and documentation is even more important than for conventional systems, where responsible humans can be interrogated or monitored⁴ with respect to their safety-related decisions. Therefore, it must be demonstrated that the related documentation can survive the anticipated accidents.

26.3 Runtime Certification

Recall Aspect 2 discussed in Section 22.2 about the technical insufficiency of current standards: ultra-complex autonomous systems can change their behaviour significantly *after* type certification, in particular, due to new plans synthesised and executed at runtime. None of the (pre-) standards discussed above addresses this problem. Significant contributions to its solution, however, have been suggested in the research communities [28, 29, 96, 176].

A significant change of behaviour *after* type certification should be preceded by

- a runtime risk assessment, followed by

⁴by the black box of an aircraft, for example

- an acceptance test suite executed at runtime, with the objective to obtain certification credit for the new behaviour, followed by
- a documentation of the compiled evidence and the certificate obtained,

before it becomes operative. This procedure is denoted by **runtime certification**.

Obviously, it might be hazardous to perform the test suite with the original equipment (OE) in its operational environment. This suggests to perform the acceptance test suite in the cloud with a **digital twin**. As discussed already in Chapter 19, this solution requires a methodological and technical testing framework allowing to obtain certification credit for tests performed in a cloud environment – this time even completely without OE involvement. As of today, it is unclear whether certification bodies will accept such an approach, and whether enough evidence can be provided that tests with **digital twins** are “sufficiently trustworthy representations” of reality. The business cases for collaborative autonomous systems, however, are so attractive that we expect that the runtime certification concept will be accepted in the near future.

Runtime certification with digital twins only?

As discussed before in Section 22.3, runtime certification for changed behaviours is only needed if the changed or new behaviour is safety-relevant. If an application behaviour can be changed without affecting the effectiveness of the existing safety supervisors, no runtime certification procedure is required. It should be emphasised, however, that changing application behaviour may require an Impact Analysis (IA) at runtime to check whether the change affects safety or not. An application behaviour without safety relevance may become critical after a behavioural change. This risk, however, can be avoided at design time by carefully segregating safety-critical and non-critical system components.

Impact analysis required?

Chapter 27

Heterogeneous Safety Cases

Whereas the elaboration of safety cases for conventional safety-critical systems is well understood, the challenges posed by autonomous ultra-complex systems, as described in this report, raises questions about the adequateness of safety cases that are still unsolved. Koopman et al. [128] have compiled an overview about both credible and insufficient assurance arguments for autonomous systems, with emphasis on road vehicles. Recall that safety cases are defined as follows¹:

Definition 7 (Safety Case)

A safety case is a structured argument, supported by a body of evidence that provides a compelling, comprehensible and valid case that a system is safe for a given application in a given operating environment.

For conventional safety-critical systems, one of the preferred ways to elaborate a safety case is to follow an accepted safety standard for the application domain: Following the steps of a standardised development process and producing the required artefacts (from design documents to hazard analyses, test cases, procedures and results) results in a safety case

¹definition according to *UK Ministry of Defence (2017) Defence Standard 00-56 Issue 7 (Part 1): Safety Management Requirements for Defence Systems, Feb. 2017.*

that will be accepted for certification credit if the artefacts are complete, traceable, and the verification results do not indicate any remaining errors threatening safety.

As pointed out in Chapter 14, some sub-components of the safety controllers in ultra-complex autonomous systems can be developed in a conventional way, while others use new technologies like ML. For the former, the established standards-based route to certification can be chosen, but for the latter, individual safety case elaboration is required since accepted standards do not exist. Therefore, safety cases need to be constructed individually on a per-sub-system basis, and the credibility of such cases need to be checked individually by the certification authorities. Koopman et al. [128] use the term **heterogeneous safety arguments** for this modus operandi. It is allowed, in principle, for all transportation domains, but it is significantly more costly than following an established safety standard for *all* system components.

Koopman et al. [128] argue that – even more important than new standards for autonomous ultra-complex systems – a public catalogue of strategies and associated argumentation patterns for setting up safety cases should be compiled. This argument is well-justified as soon as we accept that safety cases for these systems will necessarily remain heterogeneous in the future, since classic technologies will be combined with the AI-based designs, and re-use of safety arguments for those novel technologies will be come necessary to keep certification costs at an acceptable level.

<p>These considerations even challenge the call for novel comprehensive safety-standards covering all certification aspects of autonomous ultra-complex systems: with comprehensive catalogues at hand, such standards won't be needed; moreover, their creation may even be infeasible.</p>
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Chapter 28

Documentation of Safety Cases

The goal structuring notation (**GSN**) [195] has been introduced as a visual modelling formalism intended to document assurance cases and to demonstrate that artefacts compiled to achieve certification credit are complete and compliant with applicable standards. The formalism provides graphical widgets for

Goal
structuring
notation

1. **Goals.** Assurance-related claims whose validity should be demonstrated by artefacts created during hazard and risk analysis, **V&V**, by reference to external documents, or/and by associated arguments.
2. **Solutions.** Evidence supporting the truth of a claim.
3. **Strategies.** Arguments for decomposing goals into sub-goals.
4. **Context.** Information about the context in which strategies are applicable, goals are expected to hold, or solutions can be assumed to be valid.
5. **Assumptions.** Conditions that are assumed to be fulfilled when deciding to apply a certain strategy.
6. **Justifications.** References to an argument or a document justifying the application of certain strategies.

In addition, relationships between these widgets can be drawn in a way that is similar to SysML relationships connecting blocks.

An example of a GSN Model provided by the Assurance Case Working Group (ACWG) is shown in Figure 28.1.

Figure 28.1: Example GSN model provided by the ACWG [195].

Chapter 29

Requirements-driven versus Model-driven Testing

To the best of our knowledge, all standards related to the certification of safety-critical systems follow the **requirements-driven testing approach**: test cases have to be generated from or at least traced back to requirements specified for the system under test. A necessary condition to receive certification credit for testing activities is that

Requirements-driven testing

all requirements have been covered by the test cases performed in a justifiable way.

A naive **MBT** approach or grey-box checking approach would not be acceptable from the certification perspective:

Naive MBT test cases

- Naive **MBT** generates test cases to achieve some variant of model coverage, but the concept of model coverage is non-existent in standards for safety-critical systems [40, 105, 206].
- Naive grey-box checking verifies requirements only in the model checking phase, but does not produce requirements-driven test cases.

Achieving certification credit with MBT. In an advanced MBT approach, the reference model is extended by requirements tracing information: behavioural or structural model elements are linked by some kind

Advanced MBT test cases

of **satisfaction relation** to the requirements they help to implement. Such a relation is provided, for example, by the SysML modelling language [154, 194]. Then requirements-driven test cases are generated by creating witness paths through the model that cover the model elements associated with the given requirement [158, 161]. The concept of model coverage is then only used to justify that the generated test cases cover all requirements aspects *in a sufficient way*.

It is sometimes criticised that **MBT** creates a “detour” when trying to create test suites deserving certification credit: instead of directly relating test cases to requirements, test cases are constructed with the objective to cover model elements, and only the latter are traced back to requirements.

Achieving certification credit with grey-box checking. Recall that in basic grey-box checking, test cases are created by (a) the learning strategy (e.g. L*-strategy [9]) and (b) by the checking method used to decide whether the learning phase has been completed [157]. The learning phase does not “know” anything about requirements. The latter are only verified by model checking *after* the learning phase has been completed.

For advanced grey-box checking, the learning phase is enriched with test cases generated from each requirement. If requirements have been formalised, for example, in **LTL**, each requirement can be transformed into a Büchi automaton, and witness test cases for the requirement can be generated by traversing the automaton.

Requirements-based test cases in advanced grey-box checking

One might argue that once requirements-driven test cases are generated, the subsequent learning and model checking phases are redundant, since the safety-related standards only require test cases for each requirement. However, this overlooks the fact that the model checking phase can actually *prove* that a requirement has been implemented, and this significantly increases the effect of the verification phase: the requirements-driven test cases are hardly ever sufficient to prove that the **SUT** behaves consistently to the requirements *in every operational situation*. Moreover, the model checking phase allows to verify liveness properties. This is impossible for testing, since liveness properties can only be verified on infinite traces.

Summarising, advanced **MBT** creates test suites that are suitable to

achieve certification credit, and advanced grey-box checking even significantly improves the assurance of safety-critical systems.

Chapter 30

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Appendix A

NHTSA Definition: Levels of Vehicle Automation

In Figure A.1, the NHTSA definition of automation levels for vehicles is shown.

Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) Automation Levels

0	1	2	3	4	5
No Automation Zero autonomy; the driver performs all driving tasks.	Driver Assistance Vehicle is controlled by the driver, but some driving assist features may be included in the vehicle design.	Partial Automation Vehicle has combined automation functions, like acceleration and steering, but the driver must remain engaged with the driving task and monitor the environment at all time.	Conditional Automation Driver is a necessity, but is not required to monitor the environment. The driver must be ready to take control of the vehicle at all times with notice.	High Automation The vehicle is capable of performing all driving functions under certain conditions. The driver may have the option to control the vehicle.	Full Automation The vehicle is capable of performing all driving functions under all conditions. The driver may have the option to control the vehicle.

source: https://www.nhtsa.gov/sites/nhtsa.gov/files/nhtsa_sae_automation_levels.png

Figure A.1: NHTSA definition of automation levels for vehicles.

Appendix B

Metrics for the Performance of Neural Classification Networks

To assess the performance of a neural network used for classification purposes, the following metrics are used. The metrics are defined here for simple binary classifications like “*is there an obstacle present on the railroad track*” that can be answered with YES or NO. A **positive** result corresponds to a YES answer, a **negative** result to a NO answer. A **false positive** is an erroneous YES answer, a **false negative** an erroneous NO answer.

In a safety-relevant context, the YES answer should always be associated with the occurrence of the safety-critical event: “YES” means that an obstacle is present on the railroad track. This means that false positives are malfunctions impairing the availability, while false negatives (result NO [obstacle] though there is one on the track) represent safety violations.

We use the following abbreviations.

TP Number of true positives

FP Number of false positives

TN Number of true negatives

FN Number of false negatives

N Total number of samples that should be classified as negative

P Total number of samples that should be classified as positive

False positive rate. The false positive rate of a test suite for a classification NN is defined as

$$\text{FALSE POSITIVE RATE} = \frac{\text{FP}}{\text{FP} + \text{TN}} \in [0, 1] \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Note that $\text{FP} + \text{TN}$ equals the complete number N of classifications that should yield a negative result if the NN's performance were perfect.

False negative rate. The false negative rate of a test suite for a classification NN is defined as

$$\text{FALSE NEGATIVE RATE} = \frac{\text{FN}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \in [0, 1] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Note that $\text{FN} + \text{TP}$ equals the complete number P of classifications that should yield a positive result if the NN's performance were perfect.

Precision. The precision of a test suite for a classification NN is defined as

$$\text{PRECISION} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \in [0, 1] \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Precision specifies the ratio of the correct YES-classifications divided by the sum of correct YES-classifications and faulty YES-classifications.

Recall. The recall of a test suite for a classification NN is defined as

$$\text{RECALL} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \in [0, 1] \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Recall specifies the ratio of correct YES-classifications divided by *all* YES-classifications that would have been detected by a perfect NN.

With the convention that YES represents an occurrence of the safety-relevant event, the **safety-related metrics for the performance of neural classification networks** are

- false negative rate (B.2): ratio of erroneous NO-answers to all YES-answers that should have been produced, and
- recall (B.4): ratio of correct YES-answers to *all* YES-answers that should have been produced.

A low false negative rate or a high recall indicate that the NN performs *safe* classifications. A low false positive rate or a high precision indicate high availability.

Appendix C

Abbreviations

A/C Aircraft

ACAS Airborne collision avoidance system

ACWG Assurance Case Working Group

ADAS Advanced Driver Assistance Systems

ADS Automated Driving System

AEB Automated Emergency Braking System

AI Artificial Intelligence

A/IS Autonomous and Intelligent Systems

ALARP As Low As Reasonably Practicable (risk management principle)

ANN Artificial Neural Network

AOP Agent-Oriented Programming

AOSE Agent-Oriented Software Engineering

ATM Air Traffic Management

ATO Automated Train Operation

- ATP** Automated Train Protection
- ATTOL** Automatic Taxiing, Take-off, and Landing
- AV** Autonomous Vehicle
- BIP** Behavior, Interaction, Priority component framework
- BIST** Built-In Self Test
- BDI** Belief-Desire Intention (for agent programming)
- BITE** Built-in Test Equipment
- BMWi** Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy
- BSI** British Standards Institution
- CAT** Commercial Air Transport (passengers, cargo, mail)
- CCP** Coupon Collector's Problem
- CGF** Coverage-Guided Greybox Fuzzing
- CNN** Convolutional Neural Network
- CP** Conformal Prediction
- CPS** Cyber-Physical Systems
- CTMC** Continuous Time Markov Chain
- DDT** All of the real-time operational and tactical functions required to operate a vehicle in on-road traffic (Definition taken verbatim from [196].)
- DFA** Deterministic finite automaton
- DL** Deep Learning
- DNN** Deep Neural Network

DOT US Department of transportation

DP Driving policy

DSL Domain Specific Language

DTMC Discrete Time Markov Chain

DUV Design Under Verification

DTF Digital Twin Framework

EAI Embodied Artificial Intelligence

EASA European Union Aviation Safety Agency

ECU Electronic Control Unit (automotive domain)

E/E system Electrical and/or electronic system

ETCS European Train Control Systems

FAA Federal Aviation Administration of the USA

FMVSS Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards (USA)

FSM Finite State Machine

FT Fault Tree

GAN Generative adversarial network

GoA Grade of Automation

GSN Goal Structure Notation

GSMP Generalized Semi-Markov stochastic Process

HARA Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment

HIC Human in Command

HITL Human in the loop

HIL Hardware-in-the-Loop (testing)

HOA Hanoi Omega Automata

HRI Human Robot Interaction

HW Hardware

IA Impact Analysis

IID Independent and Identically Distributed

IMA Integrated Modular Avionics

IXL Railway Interlocking System

LBIST Logic Built-In Self Test

LIDAR Light Detection and Ranging device

LTL Linear Temporal Logic

MAPE Monitor, Analyse, Plan, Execute (execution cycle of autonomic managers)

MAS Multi-Agent System

MAV Micro Aerial Vehicles

MBSE Model-based Systems Engineering

MBT Model-based Testing

MC Markov Chain

MEM Minimal Endogenous Mortality principle: based on the idea that the introduction of a technical system should not significantly increase the death rate in society

MDP Markov Decision Process

MIL Model-in-the-Loop (testing)

ML Machine Learning

MRC minimal risk condition

NCAP New Car Assessment Programme

NHTSA National Highway Traffic Safety Administration

NN Neural Network

OE Original Equipment

OD Obstacle Detection

ODD Operational Design Domain

OGSA Open Grid Services Architecture

OMG Object Management Group

OSLC Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration

PAS A Publicly Available Specification or PAS is a standardization document that closely resembles a formal standard in structure and format but which has a different development model. The objective of a Publicly Available Specification is to speed up standardization. PASs are often produced in response to an urgent market need.(This definition has been taken verbatim from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Publicly_Available_Specification.) A PAS is co-branded with the BSI (British Standards Institution). (<https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/our-services/developing-new-standards/Develop-a-PAS/what-is-a-pas/>)

PBT Property-Based Testing

PIM Platform Independent Model

POT Property-Oriented Testing

PSM Platform Specific Model

QoS Quality of Service

RAS Robotics and Autonomous Systems

RBC Radio Block Centre

ReLU Rectified Linear Unit

RNN Recurrent Neural Networks

ROI Return of Investment

RQ Research Question

SAE Society of Automotive Engineers

SCSC Safety-Critical Systems Club (see <https://scsc.uk>)

SDF Simulation/Scene Description Format

SFSM Symbolic Finite State Machine

SiL Software-in-the-Loop (testing)

SIL Safety Integrity Level

SOAP Simple Object Access Protocol

SoS Systems of Systems

SOTIF Safety of the Intended Functionality

SPL Software Product Line

SUT System Under Test

SW Software

TAS Trustworthy Autonomous Systems

TQ Tool Qualification

TTC Time to Collision

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

UCL Upper Confidence Limit

UKRI UK Research and Innovation

UML Unified Modelling Language

USM Utility State Machine

USP Unique Selling Point

UTM Unmanned Aircraft System Traffic Management

VBI Vehicle Behaviour Interface

VLSS Vehicle level safety strategy

VP Virtual Prototype

VRU Vulnerable Road User

V&V Verification and Validation

V2X Vehicle to Infrastructure (communication)

WCET Worst Case Execution Time

WP Work Package

WPBS Work Package Break-down Structure

XAI Explainable Artificial Intelligence

XMI XML Metadata Interchange

XML Extensible Markup Language

Appendix D

Glossary

Accident An unexpected event that causes damage, injury, or harm. See also **incident**

Adaptivity The ability to improve performance by learning from experience. [In the Machine Learning context], a system is considered adaptive when it continues to learn in real-time operation

Artificial intelligence (AI) Technology that appears to emulate human performance typically by learning, coming to its own conclusions, appearing to understand complex content, engaging in natural dialogues with people, enhancing human cognitive performance (also known as cognitive computing) or replacing people on execution of non-routine tasks. Applications include autonomous vehicles, automatic speech recognition and generation, and detection of novel concepts and abstractions (useful for detecting potential new risks and aiding humans to quickly understand very large bodies of ever-changing information)

Artificial neural network (ANN) A computational graph that consists of connected nodes ('neurons') that define the order in which operations are performed on the input. Neurons are connected by edges, which are parameterised by weights (and biases). Neurons are organised in layers, specifically an input layer, several intermediate layers, and an output layer. This document refers to a specific type of neural

network that is particularly suited to process image data: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which use parameterised convolution operations to compute their outputs. Commonly used types of neural networks are to be highlighted: **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)**, **Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)**, **Generative adversarial networks (GANs)**

Automation The use of control systems and information technologies reducing the need for human input, typically for repetitive tasks

Autonomy The ability to perform tasks in complex environments without input by a human

Avionics Electronics (including computers), as applied in aviation

Bias An error from erroneous assumptions in the learning [process]. High bias can cause an algorithm to miss the relevant relations between attributes and target outputs (=underfitting)

Big Data A new technology, which allows the analysis of big amount of data (more than terabytes), with a high velocity (high speed of data processing), from various sources (sensors, images, texts, etc.), and which might be unstructured (not standardised format)

Brittle (deep neural network) A trained DNN is called brittle if seemingly small changes in the input data lead to drastic changes in the output, resulting, for example, in an erroneous image classification

cloud-native repository A data archive residing in the cloud which can be evaluated and manipulated in the cloud as well, without the necessity to download this data to local computers

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) - a specialised kind of neural network for processing data that has a known grid-like topology. Convolutional networks use convolution [a specialised kind of linear operation] in place of general matrix multiplication in at least one of their layers

DARPA (Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency) A US Government Agency whose mission is to make pivotal investments in breakthrough technologies for national security

Data for safety (EASA) Data4Safety (also known as D4S) is a data collection and analysis programme that supports the goal of ensuring the highest common level of safety and environmental protection for the European aviation system. The programme aims at collecting and gathering all data that may support the management of safety risks at European level. This includes safety reports (or occurrences), flight data (i.e. data generated by the aircraft via the flight data recorders), surveillance data (air traffic data), weather data - but those are only a few from a much longer list. As for the analysis, the programme's ultimate goal is to help to 'know where to look' and to 'see it coming'. In other words, it will support the performance-based environment and set up a more predictive system. More specifically, the programme will facilitate better knowledge of where the risks are (safety issue identification), determine the nature of these risks (risk assessment) and verify whether the safety actions are delivering the needed level of safety (performance measurement). It aims to develop the capability to discover vulnerabilities in the system across terabytes of data

Data science A broad field that refers to the collective processes, theories, concepts, tools and technologies that enable the review, analysis and extraction of valuable knowledge and information from raw data

Data-driven AI The data-driven [approach] focuses on building a system that can [learn] what is the right answer based on having [trained on] a large number of [labelled] examples

Deep learning (DL) A specific type of machine learning based on the use of large neural networks to learn abstract representations of the input data by composing many layers

Digital twin *"A digital twin is a virtual representation that serves as the*

*real-time digital counterpart of a physical object or process.*¹

Embodied artificial intelligence (EAI) In EAI, AI algorithms learn through embodied physical interactions with their environments, whether real or simulated

Epistemologic defeaters Conditions or events leading to the loss, reduction, or prevention of some positive epistemic status, that is, conditions or events counting *against* a belief

Epistemology The study of knowledge and the justification of beliefs

Explainable AI “*is artificial intelligence (AI) in which the results of the solution can be understood by humans.*”²

Functional safety is the part of the overall safety of a system or piece of equipment that depends on automatic protection operating correctly in response to its inputs or failure in a predictable manner (fail-safe). The automatic protection system should be designed to properly handle likely human errors, systematic errors, hardware failures and operational/environmental stress.³

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) - a type of construct in neural network technology that is composed of two neural networks: a generative network and a discriminative network. These work together to provide high-level simulation of conceptual tasks

Illocutionary force The intention of the sender in a message exchanged between agents

Impact analysis (also change impact analysis) “*is the analysis of changes within a deployed product or application and their potential consequences*”.⁴

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_twin

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Explainable_artificial_intelligence

³definition adopted verbatim from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_safety

⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Change_impact_analysis

Incident Any unexpected event that does not result in serious losses or injury, but *might* have caused an accident. For formally, an incident occurs if a system reaches a hazardous state from which it recovers without entering an accident state before

Inference The process of feeding the machine learning model an input and computing its output. See also related definition of ‘Training’

Internet of things (IoT) The network of physical objects that contain embedded technology to communicate and sense or interact with their internal states or the external environment

Machine learning (ML) Rooted in statistics and mathematical optimisation, machine learning is the ability of computer systems to improve their performance by exposure to data without the need to follow explicitly programmed instructions. [Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence]. Machine learning strategies go by three methods **Supervised learning**, **Unsupervised learning** and **Reinforcement learning**

Machine learning model A parametrised function that maps inputs to outputs. The parameters are determined during the training process

minimal risk condition Vehicle state in order to reduce the risk of harm, when a given trip cannot be completed

Mode confusion The actual system state differs from what a responsible human (e.g. driver, pilot) thinks the state is (e.g. pilot thinks that auto pilot is active while it is actually switched off)

Model-driven AI Model-driven AI (or symbolic AI), instead, attempts to capture knowledge and derive decisions through explicit representation and rules

Narrow AI Artificial intelligence that is focused on one narrow task

Neural network A computational graph that consists of connected nodes ('neurons') that define the order in which operations are performed on the input. Neurons are connected by edges, which are parameterised by weights (and biases). Neurons are organised in layers, specifically an input layer, several intermediate layers, and an output layer. This document refers to a specific type of neural network that is particularly suited to process image data: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which use parameterised convolution operations to compute their outputs. Commonly used types of neural networks are to be highlighted: **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)**, **Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)**, **Generative adversarial networks (GANs)**

Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration (OSLC) is an open community creating specifications for *interactions between tools*. The objective is to facilitate the development of IDEs, including issue tracking, testing, and other services relevant for the lifecycle of software-based products. In particular, IDEs should become more flexible with the help of OSLC, so that it will become easier to integrate tools of other providers, as long as these tools conform to the data exchange protocols provided by OSLC

Operational safety means the absence of unreasonable risk under the occurrence of hazards resulting from functional insufficiencies of the intended functionality (e.g. false/missed detection), operational disturbances (e.g. environmental conditions like fog, rain, shadows, sunlight, infrastructure) or by reasonably foreseeable misuse/errors by the driver, passengers and other road users (safety hazards — without system faults).⁵

Performative same meaning as *illocutionary force*

Predictability/determinism A system is predictable/deterministic if when given identical inputs, produces identical outputs

⁵definition adopted verbatim from <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/operational-safety>

- Rebutting defeater** A defeater (in epistemology) providing evidential support for the opposite thesis of a belief
- Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)** - a type of advanced artificial neural network (ANN) that involves directed cycles in memory. One aspect of recurrent neural networks is the ability to build on earlier types of networks with fixed-size input vectors and output vectors
- Reinforcement learning** In this algorithm, the neural network is reinforced for positive results, and punished for a negative result, forcing the neural network to learn over time
- Resilience** Attribute of systems and applications to ensure high service availability through monitoring and automatic adjustment of redundant or virtualized infrastructure components
- Road furniture (also street furniture)** A collective term for objects and pieces of equipment installed along streets and roads for various purposes. It includes benches, traffic barriers, bollards, post boxes, phone boxes, streetlamps, traffic lights, traffic signs, bus stops, tram stops, taxi stands, public lavatories, fountains, watering troughs, memorials, public sculptures, and waste receptacles
- Robustness** For an input varying in a region of the state space, the system is producing the same outputs
- Safety science** A broad field that refers to the collective processes, theories, concepts, tools and technologies that support safety management
- Safing mission** A behaviour triggered when sudden events increase the risk in an unacceptable way. The objective of this behaviour is to transfer the system into a stable safe state as quickly as possible [127]
- Supervised learning** - the process of learning a function that maps an input to an output based on example input-output training samples

Training The process of optimising the parameters (weights) of a machine learning model given a data set and a task to achieve on that data set. For example, in supervised learning, the training data consists of input (e.g. an image) / output (e.g. a class label) pairs and the machine learning model 'learns' the function that maps the input to the output, by optimising its internal parameters. See also related definition of 'Inference'

Undercutting defeater A defeater (in epistemology) removing support for a belief

Unsupervised learning - this strategy is used in cases where there is no labelled data set available to learn from. The neural network analyses the data set, and then a cost function tells the neural network how far off target it was. The neural network then adjusts to increase accuracy of the algorithm

Variance An error from sensitivity to small fluctuations in the training set. High variance can cause an algorithm to model the random noise in the training data, rather than the intended outputs (=overfitting)

Vehicle to everything (V2X) communication Communication between a (potentially autonomous) vehicle and "*any entity that may affect, or may be affected by, the vehicle.*"⁶

Vulnerable Road User (VRU) A road user who is not occupying a vehicle such as a passenger car, a public transit vehicle, or a train

A part of this glossary has been adopted verbatim from [56].

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vehicle-to-everything>